

Call identifier:
PRO-GRACE
Grant agreement no: 101094738

Promoting a plant genetic resource community for Europe

Deliverable No. D1.2

Standards for collecting and displaying genetic data

Contractual delivery date:

M11

Actual delivery date:

M11

Responsible partner:

CSIC

Contributing partners:

(CSIC, CREA, UNITO, ENEA, INIAV, MAICH, NASC, CNR, NORDGEN, UEB)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101094738.

Grant agreement no.	Horizon Europe – 101094738
Project full title	PRO-GRACE – Promoting a plant genetic resource community for Europe
Deliverable number	D1.2
Deliverable title	Standards for collecting and displaying genetic data
Type	R – Document, report
Dissemination level	Public
Work package number	WP1
Author(s)	CSIC (Clara Pons, Antonio Granell, Bruno Contreras Moreira, Ernesto Igartua Arregui, Luis Guash), IPK (Catherine Hazel Aguilar, Stephan Weise) with the contribution of CREA, UNITO, ENEA, INIAV, MAICH, NASC, CNR, NORDGEN, UEB
Keywords	

The research leading to these results has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101094738.

The author is solely responsible for its content, it does not represent the opinion of the European Commission and the Commission is not responsible for any use that might be made of data appearing therein.

SUMMARY

1. INTRODUCTION	3
2. ACTIVITIES	3
3. RESULTS	4
3.1. FAIRsharing survey to find available databases and standards to store EURISCO genetic data.	4
3.3 Review of existing standards for models, formats and syntax:	7
3.3.1 Standard formats	7
3.3.2. Models/syntax	12
3.4. Identifier (ID) schemes standards	14
3.5 Review of existing Semantic standards	17
3.6 Review of existing Minimum reporting guidelines	21
3.6.1. Minimum reporting guidelines for sequences	21
3.6.1. Review of existing Minimum reporting guidelines for tracks metadata	23
3.6.2 Review of existing standards for visual representation of genetic data	24
3.6.3 Review of existing standards and public repositories for linked genotype and phenotype data.	27
3.7 Quality control standards: how to QC data	30
3.8 Recommendations for linkage of genetic data with EURISCO	31
3.9. Discussion	32
DEVIATIONS	33
REFERENCES	33
ANNEXES	36

1. Introduction

Plant genetic resources (PGR) are crucial for sustainable crop production and for ensuring food and nutrition security both, today and in the future. To support efficient conservation and accessibility, the integration of genetic data has become essential through practices known as 'next-generation genebanking' (van Treuren and van Hintum, 2014; Wambugu *et al.*, 2018; Nybom and Lācis, 2021; Aubry, 2023).

The European Search Catalogue for Plant Genetic Resources (*EURISCO*; <http://eurisco.ecpgr.org/>) serves as a pivotal component of the European PGR information system. Developed within the European Cooperative Programme for Plant Genetic Resources (ECPGR; <https://www.ecpgr.cgiar.org/>), EURISCO acts as a centralized repository for passport and phenotypic data related to plant genetic resources conserved in European collections. However, it currently lacks representation of genetic data, which has seen significant advancements over the last two decades through EU-funded projects. Such valuable genetic information remains scattered across literature, specific websites, and databases from different projects, highlighting the pressing need for its integration into EURISCO.

Genetic data and metadata encompasses a wide array of types generated using diverse technologies, including whole genome sequencing, reduced genome sequencing (exome sequencing, genotyping, target sequencing, transcriptome sequencing), single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNP), simple sequence repeats (SSR), structural variations (SV), copy number variation (CNV), epigenomics, alternative splicing, gene expression, QTLs and GWAs trait-associated variants are some examples of genetic data produced using different technologies. Harmonizing, integrating, and making this genetic data FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, and re-usable) (Wilkinson *et al.*, 2016) has been a shared goal within the scientific community since 2000. To achieve this, employing Permanent Unique Identifiers, standardized metadata with controlled vocabularies, and open-source communication protocols and databases are essential.

By linking genetic data with EURISCO and adhering to FAIR principles (FAIRification, (Welter *et al.*, 2023)), researchers and stakeholders can leverage high-quality, curated data for better decision-making and sustainable use of plant genetic resources, contributing to global food security. Two models for data FAIRification exist: create new standards or exploiting (rather than replacing) existing resources and promote their use. In this deliverable we comprehensively reviewed existing standards and public repositories for nucleotide sequence, genetic polymorphisms, makers and, variants to identify currently implemented standards, requirements, and features related to the management and sharing of genetic data and its metadata. **The overall objective of D1.2 is to find and evaluate solutions to the challenges described above, in line with the ECPGR's Plant Genetic Resources Strategy for Europe, and to develop a viable concept for genetic (meta)data implementation and long-term operation to further establish EURISCO as a trusted open-access repository.**

2. Activities

We organized the D1.2 activities in two phases:

- 1) In the **first phase** we conducted a survey of the FAIRsharing repository (<https://fairsharing.org>), a curated catalogue on data and metadata standards, inter-related to databases and data policies (Sansone *et al.*, 2019). The FAIRsharing repository was filtered by the terms “genetic”, “nucleotide”, “sequence”, “DNA”, “genomics” to identify the existing

standards and databases for genetic data. Standards were then classified in four types according to Sansone (Sansone *et al.*, 2019):

- **Minimum reporting guidelines:** guiding principles or checklists that outline the necessary and sufficient information vital for contextualizing and understanding a digital object
- **Semantic standards:** ranging from dictionaries to ontologies, provide definitions and unambiguous identification for concepts and objects.
- **Model/formats or syntax:** define the structure and relationship of information for a conceptual model and include transmission formats to facilitate the exchange of data between different systems.
- **Identifier schemes:** formal systems for resources and other digital objects that allow their unique and unambiguous identification.

Then standards and databases for genetic data were annotated according to: (i) FAIRsharing status indicators (maintained, ready for use and recommended) (Sansone *et al.*, 2019), (ii) if they are organism-specific or not and, (iii) their source or provider (this only for non-organism specific). In addition, we included ELIXIR's (an European life sciences infrastructure to enable researchers to access and analyse life science data, elixir-europe.org) recommended resources for submission of experimental data. In addition, we extended the search for stable identifier schemes to identifiers.org (<http://identifiers.org/>) a resolving system for persistent identifiers in the form of Compact Identifiers and URLs that enable the referencing of scientific data for the scientific community.

- 2) In a **second phase**, we reviewed those databases and standards and evaluated which are the more suitable to link genetic data with EURISCO.

3. Results

3.1. FAIRsharing survey to find available databases and standards to store EURISCO genetic data.

In July 2023, FAIRsharing had a comprehensive collection of more than 3,868 entries for databases and standards. Within this collection, related to genetic data, there were 873 databases (knowledgebases and public repositories with standard-compliant data) and 297 standards (minimum reporting guidelines, models/formats or syntax and identifier schemes) (**Table 1** and **Annex 1**). A significant portion of these entries, constituting 32.5%, can handle data and metadata across all species for a particular domain or area of study (genome, molecule- or process-specific databases, variations and others). The remaining 67.5% of available standards and databases were species-specific, taxa-specific or family-specific, predominantly focussed on biomedical research and model species. For plants only, there are 129 entries (115 databases and public repositories and 14 standards) (**Table 1**), most of them capable to manage meta(data) across a wide spectrum of plant species (**Annex 1**).

Table 1. Summary of databases, public repositories and standards in FAIRsharing.org related to genetic information

Type	Total entries FAIRsharing	Maintained	Ready-to-use	Recommended	All species data	Plant data	ELIXIR recommended
Knowledgebases & public repositories	873	440	668	117	200	115	13

Standards	297	139	243	25	181	14	5
Identifier schemes	1		1				
Minimum reporting guidelines	50	23	39	10	24	4	
Model/formats or syntax:Format	74	29	66	2	61	1	1
Model/formats or syntax:models/syntax	45	30	36	5	31	2	4
Semantic standards	127	57	101	8	65	7	
Total	1170	579	911	142	381	129	18

Since the ultimate goal of D1.2 is to find a global solution to link genetic data with EURISCO, which comprises 6,737 genera and 45,175 species (Kotni *et al.*, 2023), we excluded species-specific, taxon-specific or family-specific entries related to genetic data to identify standards. In total, 440 databases, public repositories and standards related to genetic data and accepting an unlimited number of species remain. We used this list to review and evaluate the existing standards that can be used to link genetic data with EURISCO. Around 239 databases and 181 standards for genetic data and accepting all species are collected in the FAIRsharing catalogue (**Annex 1, Table 1** and **Table 2**). When we analyzed the sources and providers for databases and standards (**Figure 1**) related to genetic data accepting diverse range of species, including plants, we found that most are provided by the International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration (INSDC, <https://www.insdc.org/>) (Nakamura *et al.*, 2013; Cochrane *et al.*, 2016; Karsch-Mizrachi *et al.*, 2018) and its standard-developer collaborators. INSDC partners are (in alphabetical order): the DNA Data Bank of Japan (DDBJ; <http://www.ddbj.nig.ac.jp/>) at the National Institute for Genetics in Mishima, Japan; the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA, www.ebi.ac.uk/ena) at the EMBL European Bioinformatics Institute (EMBL-EBI) in Cambridge, UK; and GenBank (<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/genbank>) at the National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) in Bethesda, MD, (Nakamura *et al.*, 2013; Cochrane *et al.*, 2016; Karsch-Mizrachi *et al.*, 2018).

Figure 1. Main sources of databases and standards related to genetic (meta)data that accept a diverse range of species, including plants. *EMBL include countries outside EU (see <https://www.embl.org/about/member-states/>)

The INSDC repositories operate independently but synchronize periodically their data and apply similar quality standards (Nakamura *et al.*, 2013; Cochrane *et al.*, 2016; Karsch-Mizrachi *et al.*, 2018). These repositories are built to accommodate everything from raw data (i.e. next-generation sequencing

reads) to assembly data, experimental design details, taxonomic information, functional annotation and information about the projects and biological samples associated with sequencing efforts (Nakamura *et al.*, 2013; Cochrane *et al.*, 2016; Karsch-Mizrachi *et al.*, 2018). Further, the INSDC repositories work in concert with appropriate standards communities to ensure rich metadata capture for understanding the origin of the sequences (Nakamura *et al.*, 2013; Cochrane *et al.*, 2016; Karsch-Mizrachi *et al.*, 2018). From this primary repositories, source of sequence data, many other secondary and tertiary databases (or knowledge bases) providing much more specific tools and information are constructed (**Table 2**).

Table 2. Main public data repositories and knowledge bases for genetic data accepting all species or all plant species.

Abbreviation	Name	Type	Scope	Species	Provider/maintainer	URL
GenBank	NIH genetic sequence database	Repository	raw and annotated sequence data	all	NCBI	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/genbank/
ENA	European Nucleotide Archive	Repository	nucleotide sequencing information, covering raw sequencing data, sequence assembly information and functional annotation	all	EMBL-EBI	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/home
DDBJ	DNA Data Bank of Japan	Repository	nucleotide sequences, including raw data, annotated sequences, and metagenomic data	all	DDBJ	https://www.ddbj.nig.ac.jp/index-e.html
SRA	Sequence Read Archive	Repository	high-throughput sequencing data, including raw sequence reads	all	NCBI	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/sra
EVA	European Variation Archive	Repository	all types of genetic variation data	all	EMBL-EBI	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/eva/
UCSC Genome Browser	UCSC Genome Browser	Knowledgebase	visualizing and analyzing genomic data	all	NCBI	https://genome.ucsc.edu/
Ensembl	Ensembl	Knowledgebase	visualizing and analyzing genomic data	all	EMBL-EBI	https://www.ensembl.org , https://plants.ensembl.org
ArrayExpress	ArrayExpress	Repository	all functional genomics data generated from microarray or next-generation sequencing (NGS)	all	EMBL-EBI	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biostudies/arrayexpress
GEO	Gene Expression Omnibus	Repository	all functional genomics data generated from microarray or next-generation sequencing (NGS)	all	NCBI	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/
Track Hub Registry	Track Hub Registry	Repository	Traks for all kind of genetic data	all	EMBL-EBI	https://trackhubregistry.org/
PLAZA	PLAZA	Knowledgebase	comparative genomics, gene annotations, and sequence data	plants	GHENT University	https://bioinformatics.psb.ugent.be/plaza/
GERMINATE	GERMINATE	Repository	Phenotypic and genetic data	plants	The James	https://ics.hutton.ac.uk/germinate-demo/#/home

					Hutton Institute	
PlantGDB	Plant Genomics Database	Knowledgebase	comparative genomics, gene annotations, and sequence data	plants	NSF	https://www.plantgdb.org/
Gramene	Gramene	Knowledgebase	comparative genomics, gene annotations, and sequence data	plants	NSF	https://www.gramene.org/

Of course, there are many other databases (see **Table 2, Annex 1**) and standards related to genetic data provided by sources other than INSDC. databases or standards are specialized and crucial to the topic. These are typically maintained by researchers who specialize in the subject and are frequently generated as part of genome assembly/annotation projects. The data from these projects is ultimately submitted to INSDC.

3.3 Review of existing standards for models, formats and syntax:

Various scheme and syntax standards are used to structure and define the format of the data. These standards help ensure interoperability, consistent representation, and effective data sharing. They preferably should be widespread and open, readable and usable by a wide number of software and invisible to users (Sansone et al., 2019). A total of 91 standards for models, formats and syntax for genetic data and accepting data for all species are listed in FAIRsharing.

3.3.1 Standard formats

Several models and formats are commonly used for representing and storing genetic data. These models/syntaxes ensure that genetic information can be accurately captured, shared, and analysed across different tools and platforms. The choice of format often depends on the specific type of genetic data and the intended use case. Standard formats to store, interchange and display genetic data already exist for many types of data (see <https://genome.ucsc.edu/FAQ/FAQformat.html>). Some of these standards such as FASTA, FASTQ, SAM/BAM, GFF3 or VCF are stable, widely adopted and implemented in a diverse range of databases and analysis tools. The most common standards for file formats encoding genetic data are listed in **Table 3**.

Table 3. The most common file formats to store genetic data

	ACRONYM	NAME	Type of data	Codification	Extension
Sequence formats	FASTA	FASTA Sequence Format	nucleotide or peptide sequences	Plain text	.fa (others: .fasta, .fsa)
	FASTQ	FASTQ Sequence And Sequence Quality Format	Nucleotide sequence and PHRED quality scores	Plain text	.fq
	Genbank format	EMBL flat file format	Storing sequences nucleotide or peptide sequences and their associated meta-information, feature coordinates, and annotations	Plain text	.gb or .genbank
	EMBL format	EMBL flat file format	Storing sequences nucleotide or peptide sequences and their associated meta-information, feature coordinates, and annotations	Plain text	.embl
	DDBJ format	DDBJ flat file format	Storing sequences nucleotide or peptide sequences and their	Plain text	.ddbj

			associated meta-information, feature coordinates, and annotations		
Alignment formats	SAM	Sequence Alignment/Map Format	Alignments of sequencing reads to a reference genome	Plain text	.sam
	BAM	Binary Alignment Map Format	Alignments of sequencing reads to a reference genome	Binary	.bam
	CRAM	Compressed Reference-oriented Alignment Map	Alignments of sequencing reads to a reference genome	Byte	.cram
	VCF	Variant Call Format	DNA variation	Plain text	.vcf
	BCF2	Binary Variant Call Format version 2	DNA variation	Binary	.bcf
Discrete genomic feature data and tracks	BED format	Browser Extensible Data Format	Genomic intervals with additional information	Plain text	.bed
	Bedgraph	Browser Extensible Graphical Data Format	Genomic intervals with continuous-valued data	Plain text	.bb
	GTrack format	Genomic track	Genomic intervals with additional information	Plain text	.gtrak
	BTrack format	Genomic track	Genomic intervals with additional information	Binary	.btrak
	GFF3	Gene Feature File version 3	Features, positions and meta-feature information		.gff
	GTF	Gene transfer format	Genomic annotation with information and scores		.gtf

Sequence data files:

- FASTA format:** created in 1988 (Pearson and Lipman, 1988), **FASTA is the standard** most implemented by databases and repositories (Sansone et al., 2019). It is a very basic format with two minimum lines **to represent either nucleotide or peptide sequences** (see **Annex 2** for an example of FASTA file). First line referred as comment line starts with ‘>’ and gives basic information about sequence. There is no set format for comment line. Any other line that starts with ‘;’ will be ignored. Lines with ‘;’ are not a common feature of FASTA files. After comment line, sequence of nucleic acid or protein is included in standard one letter code. Any tabulators, spaces, asterisks etc in sequence will be ignored. A sequence file in FASTA format can contain several sequences. Each sequence will be separated by their "header" line, starting by ">".
- FASTQ format:** common file format for sharing sequencing read data combining both the sequence and an associated per base quality score (Cock *et al.*, 2010). It is the **standard for storing the output of high-throughput sequencing instruments including third-generation sequencing instruments**. Sequences are represented by four lines (see **Annex 2** for an example of FASTQ file). Line 1 begins with “@” followed by the sequence identifier and optional descriptions. Line 2 is raw sequence letters while Line 3 begins with the “+” character optionally followed by the same sequence identifier and descriptions. Line 4 are PHRED quality scores for nucleotide sequence or the estimated probability for a base to be erroneous (Ewing and Green, 1998; Ewing *et al.*, 1998). PHRED scores use a logarithmic scale, and are represented by ASCII characters, mapping to a quality usually going from 0 to 93. Single ASCII character codes from 33 to 126 are used in place of numeric values to denote the PHRED scores in Line 4. See <https://bioinformatics.uconn.edu/resources-and-events/tutorials-2/file-formats-tutorial/> for detailed information of PHRED scores and ASCII characters.
- Genbank/EMBL/DBJ formats:** Each of the **INSDC members** has a **sequence standard file format** that was designed to be rich and human readable. Despite some differences in the formatting of information, all of them contain almost the same fields and the same

information, making them interchangeable (see **Annex 2** for an example of Genbank/EMBL/DDBJ files). Each sequence entry in the INSDC sequence files is composed of lines (each with their own format) starting with a sequence unique identifier, followed by several annotation lines, the sequence and ended by two slashes ("/"). Annotation lines are used to record the various data including a concise description of the sequence, the scientific name and taxonomy of the source organism, and a table of features with controlled vocabulary (see <https://www.insdc.org/submitting-standards/feature-table/> for format details) that identifies coding regions and other sites of biological significance, such as transcription units, sites of mutations or modifications, and repeats, protein translations and bibliographic references. For more details see <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Sitemap/samplerecord.html>, <https://www.ddbj.nig.ac.jp/ddbj/flat-file-e.html> and <https://ena-docs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/submit/fileprep/flat-file-example.html>.

Alignment data files

- **SAM format:** SAM is the **standard for reads alignments against reference sequences** (Li *et al.*, 2009). It is a tab-delimited text-based format for storing single- and paired-end reads alignments against reference sequences. **It can support short and third generation sequencing long reads produced by different sequencing platforms.** The format has been extended to include unmapped sequences, and it may contain other data such as base-call & alignment qualities. The SAM format (see **Annex 2** for an example) consists of a header section (~metadata) and an alignment section (raw mapping information). Header lines contain metadata about the reference sequences, read and sample information, and (optionally) processing steps and comments. Each header line begins with @, followed by a two-letter code that distinguishes the different types of metadata records in the header: @HD file level metadata, @SQ reference sequence dictionary, @RG read group, @PG program. Each alignment record in a SAM file contains 11 mandatory fields in tab-separated columns describing the read, quality of the read, and nature alignment of the read to a region of the genome. SAM standard is maintained by the Large Scale Genomics work stream of the Global Alliance for Genomics & Health (GA4GH; <https://www.ga4gh.org/>). For detailed info see <https://samtools.github.io/hts-specs/SAMv1.pdf> and <https://pacbiofileformats.readthedocs.io/en/12.0/BAM.html>.
- **BAM format:** It is the lossless compressed binary version of the Sequence Alignment/Map (SAM) format. The data between SAM and BAM are exactly same, but BAM is compacted and indexed. BAM file requires an associated BAM.bai index file. Binary BAM files are small and ideal to store alignment files. **BAM is the most commonly used format for submission of reads to INSDC sequence repositories and analysis.** BAM is maintained by the Large-Scale Genomics work stream of the Global Alliance for Genomics & Health (GA4GH; <https://www.ga4gh.org/>). For a detailed info see <https://samtools.github.io/hts-specs/SAMv1.pdf>.
- **CRAM format:** CRAM is primarily a reference-based compressed format of SAM file, meaning that only differences between the stored sequences and the reference are stored. Additionally, each column in the SAM format is separated into blocks, improving compression ratio. It holds the same information as their SAM equivalent, offering significantly better lossless compression whilst maintaining backwards compatibility with BAM. Since CRAM files are **typically 30 to 60% smaller than their BAM equivalents**, some labs and repositories are implementing them. Usually, **CRAM files are used to store alignments and converted to the BAM format for processing.** CRAM is maintained by the Large-Scale Genomics work stream of

the Global Alliance for Genomics & Health (GA4GH; <https://www.ga4gh.org/>). For a detailed info see <https://samtools.github.io/hts-specs/CRAMv3.pdf>.

- VCF format:** is the **standard file format for storing DNA variation data** between a reference genome and sequences aligned to it, based on SAM/BAM alignments. VCF is a preferred format for databases and analysis tools because it is **unambiguous, scalable and flexible**, allowing extra information to be added to the info field and storing many millions of variants. The VCF format is a tab-delimited format that stores individual genotypes and variant calls including SNPs, insertions, deletions and structural variants, together with rich annotations (Danecek *et al.*, 2011). The current version VCF 4.3 consists of two parts: metadata lines and data section (See **Annex 2**). Metadata lines start with a ##, each line begins with a key=value pairs, and have a description of the settings, samples and general experimental design of the genotyping. The data section begins with a single #; this first line is the header line the eight fixed, mandatory fields, used to record the genotyping calls: chromosome (CHROM), a 1-base position of the start of the variant (POS), unique identifiers of the variant (ID), the reference allele (REF), a comma separated list of alternate non-reference alleles (ALT), a PHRED-scaled quality score (QUAL), site filtering information (FILTER) and a semicolon separated list of additional, user extensible annotation (INFO) and information contained within each subsequent genotype column (FORMAT). After the FORMAT field, the sample IDs define the samples included in the VCF file. The following lines of the data section contain the variant site records. Variant site records do not start with any symbol. VCF data and metadata information have a controlled vocabulary for describing variants, however, the VCF format defines a syntactic format but no vocabulary, unique identifier or recommended content for describing samples and reference genome. Recently, in the frame of ELIXIR, a minimal list of metadata recommended fields (**Table 4**) to describe plant samples in the VCF file has been proposed (Beier *et al.*, 2022). The goal of these recommendations is to link, through precise sample identifiers provided by BioSample (see below), variant data for plants to other information data sets (e.g. phenotypic, transcriptomic, metabolomic) submitted to EMBL-EBI repositories. The Global Alliance for Genomics & Health (GA4GH) maintains the specification of the VCF. See <http://samtools.github.io/hts-specs/> for more details.

Table 4. Summary of recommendations for metadata formatting (from Beier *et al.*, 2022)

Metadata field	Definition	Format	Example	Cardinality
##fileDate	Creation date of the VCF file	Date (ISO 8601, YYYYMMDD)	##fileDate=20120921	1
##bioinformatics_source	Chains of bioinformatics tools for creating the VCF file	URL, DOI	##bioinformatics_source=" doi.org/10.1038/s41588-018-0266-x "	1
##reference_ac	Accession number of reference genome assembly used in the VCF file	[[GCA/GCF]_{d}{9}\{0-9}*]/	##reference_ac=GCA_902498975.1	1
##reference_url	URL of the reference genome assembly used in the VCF file	URL, DOI	##reference_url=" ftp.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/genomes/all/GCA_902/498/975/GCA_902498975.1_Morex_v2.0/GCA_902498975.1_Morex_v2.0_genomic.fna.gz "	1
##contig	Metadata about a single sequence in the reference genome assembly	Composite below)	(see ##contig=<ID=chr1H,length=522466905,assembly=GCA_902498975.1,md5=8d21a35cc68340ecf40e2a8dec9428fa,species=NCBITaxon:4513>	1:N
	The primary identifier of the sequence	String	ID=chr1H	1
	The length in base pairs (bp) of the sequence	Integer	length=522466905	1
	The assembly accession number this sequence belongs to	this [[GCA/GCF]_{d}{9}\{0-9}*]/	assembly=GCA_902498975.1	1

Metadata field	Definition	Format	Example	Cardinality
	The md5 checksum of the sequence	MD5	md5=8d21a35cc68340ecf40e2a8dec9428fa	1
	The species of the sequence (NCBI Taxon ID)	/[NCBITaxon]:(\d+)/	species=NCBITaxon:4513	1
##SAMPLE	Metadata about a single genotype that is part of the genotyping experiment in the VCF file	Composite	(see ##SAMPLE=<ID=SAMEA104646767,DOI="doi.org/10.25642/IPK/GBIS/7811152">	1:N
	The primary identifier (Database identifier) of the genotyping sample	[(SAM)(E N D)(A GID=SAMEA104646767)		1
	The DOI of the genotyping sample (if available)	URL, DOI	DOI="doi.org/10.25642/IPK/GBIS/7811152"	0-1
	The external identifiers under which this genotyping sample is registered in other databases (either 'FAO-WIEWS_instcode:genus:accession_number' or 'DNS:database_identifier:identifier_scheme:identifier')	See Definition	ext_ID="DEU146:Hordeum:HOR 1361 BRG" or ext_ID="ipk-gatersleben.de:GBIS:akzessionId:7811152"	0:N

- **BCF2 format:** is a binary, compressed equivalent of VCF that can be indexed with tabix and can be efficiently decoded from disk or stream. The relationship between BCF and VCF is similar to that between BAM and SAM. The Global Alliance for Genomics & Health (GA4GH) maintains the specification of the VCF. See <http://samtools.github.io/hts-specs/> for more details.

Discrete genomic feature data and track files:

- **BED format:** is a simple, tab-delimited text format for representing track genomic features and their associated annotations linked to the genomic coordinates of a reference genome. Examples of such data are epigenetic DNA methylation data, ChIP-seq peaks, germline or somatic DNA variants, as well as RNA-seq expression levels. BED files are predominantly used for graphical display, but can also be queried by statistical analysis tools. BED files consist of one line per feature, with each line containing a minimum of three mandatory columns (chromosome, start, and end), and nine additional optional tab-separated columns for feature annotations (name, score, strand, etc). A BED file can optionally contain a header. However, there is no official description of the format of the header. It may contain one or more lines placed at the beginning of the list of features affected and be signified by different words or symbols, depending on its functional role or simply descriptive: genome browser options (browser); track name and configuration description (track) and other comments, such as the name of each column (#). **BED files do not contain any metadata associated to them excepting the track name.** See <https://github.com/samtools/hts-specs> and <http://genome.ucsc.edu/FAQ/FAQformat.html#format1> for more details.
- **BedGraph format:** is a variation of the BED format used for representing continuous-valued data in track format, such as read coverage or signal intensities, in a genome browser. BedGraph files are tab-delimited text files, but they contain four columns (chromosome, start, end, and value) representing the genomic region and the associated data value. The bedGraph format is line-oriented. BedGraph data are preceded by a track definition line, which adds a number of options for controlling the default display of this track. Strand information is provided in the value column, negative values represent reverse strand, whereas positive

values represent forward strand. For more detailed information see <http://genome.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/help/bedgraph.html>

- GTrack format:** a tabular format developed to provide a **uniform representation for tracks of most types of genomic datasets**. This track format data file format is capable of representing all 15 track types (Gundersen *et al.*, 2011) since they have a flexible column specification and declaring syntactic properties at the beginning of the file. The GTrack format consists of 5 different line types, distinguished by the leading characters and numbered here by order of appearance in the file. Comments preceded by the character # are ignored by parsers and may be present anywhere in the file. Header lines, preceded by ##, provide detailed information for the type of track. Column specification line, preceded by ###, provide detailed information about the origin of the track (reference, genome, sample, genomic coordinates, values, graphical representation...). Bounding region specification line, preceded by ####, specifies the region where we have information. Data lines, a tab-separated list of values without any preceding character, are defined by the column definition line. **GTrack is able to replace most common track file formats and had the advantage that all GTrack types are supported by the FAIRtracks metadata standard** (see below). For more detail see <https://github.com/gtrack/gtrack/tree/master/gtrack/spec> and <https://fairtracks.net/standards/#standards-01-fairtracks>.
- BTrack format:** supports the same variety of informational content as GTrack, but in binary form. See <https://fairtracks.net/standards/#standards-01-fairtracks>.
- GTF/GFF3 formats:** are tab-delimited text file formats used for describe functional regions of genomes. **GFF3 is the most widely used format to annotate genomes**. GFF/GTF lines have nine required fields that *must* be tab-separated. GFF/GTF share the same structure for the first 7 fields, while differing in the format of the ninth field (See **Annex 2**). The first seven lines define the sequence name, the source of the sequence, the feature type (Transcripts, exon, intron, promoter, 3' UTR, repetitive elements etc), the start and the end of the feature, the confidence score, the strand and the Frame (GTF) or Phase (GFF3). Column 9 contains attributes pertaining to the described feature. In GFF3 format, it contains a list of feature attributes (name, Id, alias, ontology, feature hierarchy, etc) in the format tag=value. Multiple tag=value pairs are separated by semicolons. In GTF, column 9 contains globally unique identifiers for the genomic locus of the transcript and the predicted transcript, respectively, separated by semicolon. For more details see <https://github.com/The-Sequence-Ontology/Specifications/blob/master/gff3.md> and <http://genome.ucsc.edu/FAQ/FAQformat.html#format1>.

3.3.2. Models/syntax

In FairSharing.org there are 45 models and syntax standards for genetic data storage and exchange across various fields and domains (**Annex 1**). These standards ensure consistency, interoperability, and efficient sharing of data among different systems and users. The most 5common models and syntax standards for genetic data storage and exchange are listed in **Table 5**.

Table 5. Models and syntax standards most common in genetic databases.

ACRONYM	NAME	Implementing databases or standards	Used for
XML	Extensible Markup Language,	NCBI Entrez Gene, ENA, DDBJ, UniProtKB, INSDC, Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO), InterPro, Phytozome, Gramene, PlantGBD, Planteome, BAR	data export, web services, or specific metadata representation

		(Bio-Analytic Resource) Plant Genome Database, MaizeGDB	
RDF	Resource Description Framework	Planteome, Agronomic Linked Data (AgroLD)	representing ontologies, linking data, and providing structured metadata
Json	JavaScript Object Notation	Gramene, PlantGDB, Phytozome	data retrieval and representation, especially when interacting with web-based services
CHADO, CHADO-XML	Modular scheme for biological database	Gramene, Solgenomics, TAIR	store diverse types of biological data, including sequences, annotations, ontologies, and genetic markers, among others.
ISA, ISA-TAB	Investigation Study Assay Tabular	EVA, ArrayExpress, MIAME, MINSEQE, MIGS/MIMS	Capturing, describing and exchanging of experimental data and metadata
OWL	Web Ontology language Format	Planteome, Agronomy Ontology Service (AO), Gene Ontology (GO), Sequence ontology (SO)	define the concepts, relationships, and semantics within these ontologies,
BRAPI	Breeding API specification for the communication of plant breeding data	The Triticeae Toolbox (T3), CassavaBase, Integrated breeding platform	exchange of plant breeding and agricultural data across different software systems and platforms

- XML:** is a versatile markup language used for structuring and encoding data in a machine-readable format. Several databases that store genetic data use **XML to represent, storage and exchange various types of genetic (meta)data, from sequences to annotations (Table 5)**. It is often chosen for its flexibility in structuring complex data and its compatibility with web-based data exchange. The specific usage of XML can vary between databases. For example, Gramene uses XML to provide structured data about genes, genomes, pathways, and annotations while Planteome uses XML to define and exchange ontology terms, annotations, and relationships. See <https://www.w3.org/TR/rdf-syntax-grammar/> for more detailed info
- RDF:** is a standard for describing resources on the web, using a graph-based model to represent data and their relationships. It is commonly used in the context of semantic web technologies and linked data, where it enables the creation of interconnected and machine-readable data networks. Some resources related to genomics and plant genetics might use RDF for specific purposes, such as **representing ontologies, linking data, and providing structured metadata (Table 5)**. Planteome uses RDF to represent and provide structured data about plant traits, anatomy, and growth stages. RDF is used to enable the integration of plant phenotype data across different species. For more details see <https://www.w3.org/RDF/>
- JSON:** is a lightweight data interchange format that is easy for both humans and machines to read and write. In the field of genomics and plant genetics, JSON is often **used for data exchange through web services and APIs**. It is commonly used to provide structured data to users and applications over the internet. While JSON may not be the primary format for data storage in these databases, it could be used for certain types of data retrieval and representation, especially when interacting with web-based services. For more details see <https://json-spec.readthedocs.io/index.html>
- CHADO/CHADOXML scheme:** is a relational database **modular scheme designed for storing, managing and integrating biological data. It is capable of representing many of the general classes of data frequently encountered in modern biology such as sequence, sequence comparisons, phenotypes, genotypes, ontologies, publications, and phylogeny (Mungall et al., 2007)**, particularly genomic and genetic data. It's an open-source scheme that provides a structured framework for representing diverse biological information in a consistent and standardized manner. Chado was developed to address the complex and interconnected nature of biological data and to support integration and querying across various data types and sources. CHADO is part of the Generic Model Organism Database (GMOD) suite

(www.gmod.org), a collection of open source software tools for managing, visualising, storing, and disseminating genetic and genomic data that include tools such as Jbrowse, Galaxy, Biomart or Tripal. For more detail see <http://gmod.org/wiki/Chado> and [http://gmod.org/wiki/Chado XML](http://gmod.org/wiki/Chado_XML)

- **ISA/ISA-tab:** The ISA (Investigation/Study/Assay) model is a general-purpose framework for **capturing and describing the metadata associated with experiments** in various scientific domains, including the life sciences (Sansone *et al.*, 2012). ISA-tab is the original format developed by the ISA team. It's a simple, tabular format for representing investigation, study, and assay metadata. It was developed to provide rich descriptions of experimental metadata (i.e. sample characteristics, technology and measurement types, sample-to-data relationships) so that the resulting data and discoveries are reproducible and reusable. The ISA model is not tied to a specific database or biological standard but rather serves as a flexible structure that can be implemented and adapted by various projects and databases. Different databases or standards dealing with genetic data such as EVA, ArrayExpress, MIAME, MINSEQE, MIGS/MIMS have implemented the ISA model with slight variations or customizations to suit their specific needs, but the core principles of capturing experimental metadata in an organized and standardized way remain consistent. See <https://isa-specs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/index.html> for more details.
- **OWL language:** is a powerful and expressive language used **for creating ontologies**—formal models that represent knowledge about a domain and the relationships between different concepts within that domain. OWL provides a rich set of constructs for describing classes, properties, individuals, and relationships between them, supporting the creation of hierarchies of classes and sub-classes, reflecting the inherent structure of the domain being modelled. Further, OWL ontologies can be serialized using RDF (Resource Description Framework), making them compatible with other Semantic Web technologies and allowing for easy integration with existing data. Some genetic resources or projects related to ontologies, functional annotations, and semantic integration currently (?) use OWL, for instance Gene Ontology (GO) and Sequence Ontology (SO). OWL is part of the Semantic Web stack, a set of technologies aimed at enhancing the meaning and interpretation of data on the World Wide Web. For more details see <https://www.w3.org/TR/owl-ref/>
- **BrAPI:** is an open standard and API (Application Programming Interface) designed to facilitate a **standardized exchange of plant breeding and agricultural (meta)data, such as germplasm information, phenotypic and genotypic data, trial and experiment details**, across different software systems and platforms. (Selby *et al.*, 2019). BrAPI is not a database itself but rather a set of standardized APIs that various databases and systems can implement to enable data exchange and integration. BrAPI re-uses existing data standards as much as possible and is compatible with both the FAO Multi-Crop Passport Descriptors and the minimum information standards for plant phenotyping. BrAPI aims to improve data interoperability and enable data sharing and integration among researchers, breeders, and organizations involved in plant breeding and crop improvement. BrAPI has gained popularity in the plant breeding and agricultural research communities because it addresses the challenges of data fragmentation, lack of interoperability and allow to develop software applications, databases, and tools. For more detail see www.brapi.org.

3.4. Identifier (ID) schemes standards

ID scheme standards serve for providing unambiguous and stable identification for individual objects of interest. Fairsharing has over 33 entries registered as ID scheme standards, however none has a direct relation exclusively with genetic data. In the case of Identifiers.org, **there are more than 350 ID scheme related to genetic data or their annotation** (see **Annex 3**). With the exception of centralized repositories and ontologies (Nucleotide Sequence Database, SRA, EVA, RefSeq, Ensembl, UniProt, InterPro, KEGG, Gene Ontology, Sequence ontology, etc), most identifiers in Identifiers.org are species-specific, taxa-specific or family-specific.

ID standards encompass various formats such as text, numbers, URLs/DOIs, and primary keys for genetic related objects that are **assigned when the objects (raw sequence, genome, alignment, gene, marker, variant locus, ontology term) are created in the repositories, knowledgebases or in ontologies for a particular domain or area of study.**

In the case of INSDC, sequence accession numbers have specific formats that might vary slightly between databases, but they generally follow a similar pattern. Here's the general format for sequence accession numbers in INSDC repositories:

- **Prefix:** The prefix indicates the type of submission and provides context for the sequence. Different prefixes are assigned to different types of data, such as genomic DNA, mRNA, coding sequences, non-coding RNAs, and more.
- **Numbers (Digits):** The numeric portion of the accession number follows the prefix and is unique to each sequence entry. It's usually a sequence of digits.

Each type of data is assigned a unique accession number following a specific format. For example:

- **Genomes:** all INSDC members use a standardized format for annotating genome assemblies. This format involves using the "GCA_XXXX" identifier followed by a unique numerical accession number to represent the entire genome assembly sequence and version of an organism. This standardized format ensures consistency and ease of reference when dealing with genome assemblies across different organisms and databases within the INSDC collaboration.
- **Genes and Transcripts:** The specific format can vary between databases, but it often includes a prefix that denotes the type of sequence. Accession numbers from GenBank often start with a two-letter prefix followed by digits. For example, "NM_001123456" for a RefSeq mRNA entry or "CP012345" for a genomic DNA entry. Accession numbers from ENA start with a letter prefix followed by digits. For example, "X12345" for a nucleotide sequence or "Y56789" for a transcript. Accession numbers from DDBJ also start with a letter prefix followed by digits. For example, "D12345" for a DNA sequence entry or "AB67890" for a transcript.
- **Splicing Forms:** Splicing forms, which represent alternative splicing isoforms of a gene, are often assigned to unique identifiers that are distinct from the primary gene or transcript accession numbers. These identifiers might include version numbers or other annotations to differentiate between different splicing forms.
- **Variants:** variants submitted in the context of a genomic study are accessioned with submitted SNP ID number ("ss#", that identifies the taxon, the reference genome, the study, the position and the ref/alt alleles) and a reference SNP ID number ("rs#"; "refSNP cluster"), that identifies a variant class in a genomic location of a taxon genome and which can be reported by one or more studies. Variants, such as single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs), insertions, deletions, and structural variants, are typically accessioned using unique identifiers.

Ideally, each genetic object should be assigned to a single ID to avoid confusion. However, most IDs found in Identifiers.org have synonyms in other databases, resulting in the assignation of different IDs to the same object. Detailed info of the IDs, such the pattern of the ID, resource URL and synonyms, used for different ontologies and databases are in **Annex 3**. To deal with multiple IDs, the concept of Persistent Unique Identifiers (PUID) has emerged as a potential solution. **PUIDs are designed to be**

permanent and steadfast identifiers, maintaining their validity on a global scale. It is crucial that PUIDs are never completely deleted but instead deprecated if necessary. Additionally, these identifiers should be effortlessly convertible between local IDs and URIs, allowing for seamless interoperability. A well-known example of a PID is a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) which is used to locate specific digital objects. Recently, the term Digital Genetic Object (DGO) has also been proposed (Manzella *et al.*, 2023), the idea is to create DGOs for each type of genetic information in INSDC repositories (e.g. nucleic acid sequence reads, data about gene expression and function, unsequenced markers and chromosomal segments) and link them to the DOI of the germplasm source material to facilitate discovery interoperability among genomic data and germplasm repositories. This proposal, however, is still in infancy (Manzella *et al.*, 2023).

Special case: Plant gene ID

The standardization description of gene nomenclature is of critical importance. It's important to note that the patterns for gene IDs can vary widely between organisms and databases (see **Annex 3**). The adoption of standardized nomenclature and IDs can be influenced by the research community, the organism's complexity, and the level of annotation available. Each one of the INSDC repositories uses their own centralized and stable ID pattern for genes. The gene ID patterns used in the repositories of the INSDC can vary depending on the organism and the type of gene annotation. Further, organism-specific communities have developed their own gene nomenclature standard system. **Table 6** shows plant gene nomenclature resources. Despite this, common formats and conventions are often followed:

- **Locus Tag or Systematic ID:** Many organisms use a systematic naming convention that often includes a short prefix followed by numbers. Organisms with well-defined genomes often use locus tags to identify genes in a sequential or systematic manner.
- **Gene Name:** Some genes are identified by their common or official names. They are often chosen based on their functions, characteristics, or roles in specific biological pathways. For example, the plant gene for Activating Transcription Factor 1 is often referred to as "ATF1."
- **Accession Number-Based:** Sometimes, genes might be linked to an accession number of a specific gene entry in the database. For instance, in GenBank, genes might be referenced using their associated accession number, such as "NM_001123456" for a RefSeq mRNA entry.
- **Synonyms or Aliases:** Genes might have synonyms or aliases that are used as identifiers. These can include both official and common names, as well as other identifiers used in the literature.
- **Standardized Gene Symbols:** For well-studied organisms, standardized gene symbols might be used. These symbols are usually short and informative names that represent the gene's function or role.
- **Unique Identifiers:** Some databases assign unique identifiers to genes that are independent of their names or other identifiers. These can be alphanumeric strings or combinations of letters and numbers.

Table 6. Plant Gene Nomenclature Resources (Adapted from (Reiser *et al.*, 2018))

Database name	URL	Species covered
Alfalfa Breeders Toolbox	alfalfatoolbox.org	Alfalfa
CassavaBase	cassavabase.org	Cassava
Citrus Genome Database	citrusgenomedb.org	Lemons, oranges, and more
Cool Season Food Legume Database	coolseasonfoodlegume.org	Lentil, pea, fava bean, chickpea
CottonGen	cottongen.org	Cotton, many species
Genome Database for Rosaceae	rosaceae.org	Apple, strawberry, rose, plums, pears, and more
Genome Database for Vaccinium	vaccinium.org	Blueberry, cranberry, bilberry, and more
GrainGenes	wheat.pw.usda.gov/GG3	Wheat, barley, oats

Gramene	https://www.gramene.org	Maize, rice
International Grape Genome Program	http://www.vitaceae.org	Grapevine
Hardwood Genomics	hardwoodgenomics.org	Oaks, poplars, maples, chestnuts, and more
KnowPulse	knowpulse.usask.ca	Chickpea, common bean, lentil
Legume Information System	legumeinfo.org	Soybean, Medicago, cowpea, chickpea, and more
MaizeGDB	maizegdb.org	Maize
<i>Medicago truncatula</i> Genome Database	medicagogenome.org	Clover
MusaBase	musabase.org	Banana
Oryzabase, Rap-Db	shigen.nig.ac.jp/rice/oryzabase/	Rice
PeanutBase	peanutbase.org	Peanuts
Solanaceae Genomics Network	solgenomics.net	Tomato, potato, eggplant, petunia, and more
Soybase	soybase.org	Soybean
Sweet Potato Database	sweetpotatobase.org	Sweet potato
T3	triticeaetoolbox.org/wheat	Wheat, barley, oats
TAIR	arabidopsis.org	<i>Arabidopsis thaliana</i>
TreeGenes	treegenesdb.org	1792 species of trees
YamBase	yambase.org	Yams

One of the main problems with gene ID is that researchers often encounter a mix of INSDC IDs and organism-specific gene IDs, names and gene products, which leads to confusion, missing information, and makes difficult to search or integrate data about genes (Reiser *et al.*, 2018). However, some resources provide cross-reference tools to help you map between different gene ID systems, enabling you to work with the IDs that best suit your research context. **Whether to use organism-specific gene IDs or INSDC gene IDs depends on the context of your research and the goals of data integration and analysis.** Both types of IDs have their advantages and considerations. Organism-specific gene IDs provide direct information about genes (gene annotations, including functional annotations, pathways, and other relevant data for that organism) in the context of a specific organism. Further, they are more intuitive and familiar to researchers working with that organism. INSDC gene IDs provide standardized access to genes across different organisms. This can be beneficial when working with multiple species or conducting comparative genomics or integrating genetic data from different organisms.

A solution to reduce the number of IDs assigned to the same gene and facilitate the integration gene data could be those used in Ensembl Plants (EMBL-EBI genome-centric portal for *plant* species of scientific interest, see below). Ensembl Plants, with genome for more than 150 species (see **Annex 4**), has adopted a combination of organism-specific gene IDs and INSDC IDs, depending on the gene and the organism being studied. **For well-studied model organisms and species with established annotations, Ensembl use organism-specific gene IDs that are consistent with the existing nomenclature for those species.** This helps Ensembl users from different organism communities to easily identify and locate genes they are familiar with, within the context of the species they are interested in.

3.5 Review of existing Semantic standards

Semantic standards play a crucial role in organizing, annotating, and exchanging metadata in a structured and machine-readable manner. They range from dictionaries to ontologies and provide definitions and unambiguous identification for concepts and objects (Sansone *et al.*, 2019). In addition, ontologies can provide a hierarchical structure of the terms. Hierarchical ontologies are the most common used, they organize concepts into a hierarchy of parent-child semantic relationships which provide a richer context for understanding the relationships between concepts (**Figure 2**). For identifying and accessing concepts, terms, and relationships ontologies use URLs and IDs. Both URLs and IDs are important components of ontology design and usage. URLs provide access to additional information and context, while IDs provide efficient and unique references for ontology terms.

GO:0004713

protein tyrosine kinase activity

Molecular Function

Definition (GO:0004713 GONUTS page)

Catalysis of the reaction: ATP + a protein tyrosine = ADP + protein tyrosine phosphate.

Secondary IDs

GO:0004718

99,433 annotations

Synonyms

Synonyms are alternative words or phrases closely related in meaning to the term name, with indication of the relationship between the name and synonym given by the synonym scope.

Synonym	Type
JAK	narrow
protein-tyrosine kinase activity	exact
Janus kinase activity	narrow

- Overview
- Synonyms
- Ancestor Chart
- Child Terms
- Annotation Guid
- GO Discussions
- Taxon Constrain
- Blacklist
- Cross-Referenc
- Cross-Ontology
- Protein Comple
- Replaces
- Replaced By
- Co-occurring Te
- GO Slims
- Change Log

Ancestor Chart

Ancestor chart for GO:0004713

Figure 2. Snapshot of the protein tyrosine kinase entry in GO, showing the richness of an ontology and highlighting the terms and hierarchies that are used to populate controlled vocabularies.

In Fairsharing.org there are 63 entries for semantic standards dealing with genetic data for all species (**Annex 1**). These ontologies provide a common language to enhance data integration, interoperability, and automated reasoning in genomics research.

In the context of genetics and genomics, especially for plant genetic metadata, several semantic standards are commonly used (**Table 7**).

Table 7. Common semantic standards used for annotating and standardizing genetic metadata

ACRONYM	NAME	Used for
GO	Gene Ontology	describing gene functions, biological processes, and cellular components in a hierarchical model
SO	Sequence Ontology	sequence features
OBI	Ontology for Biomedical Investigations	biological investigations, experiments, and assays (including genetics)
BAO	BioAssay Ontology	describing various types of assays
EDAM	Sequence Types and Features Ontology	analysis, modelling, optimisation, and data life-cycle
EFO	Experimental Factor Ontology	annotation, analysis and visualization of samples, phenotypes and studies
	DDBJ/ENA/GenBank Feature Table Definition	features and characteristics of genetic sequences
PATO	Phenotype And Trait Ontology	phenotypes

PO	Plant Ontology	plant anatomy, morphology and growth and development
TO	Trait Ontology	phenotypic traits in plants
AgrO	Agronomy Ontology	agronomic practices, techniques, variables
CO	Crop Ontology	crop-specific agronomic, morphological, physiological, quality, and stress traits
PECO	Plant Experimental Condition Ontology	Abiotic treatments, growing conditions and study types
NCBI Taxonomy	NCBI Taxonomic Database	Species taxonomic classification and nomenclature
ChEBI	Chemical Entities of Biological Interest	chemical compounds

Some of them such as GO and SO are strictly used for genetic annotations, while others like OBI, BAO, EDAM, EFO are used to describe metadata associated to the samples and protocols used to generate the genetic data:

- **GO:** it provides a standardized vocabulary for describing more than 84.220 terms related to gene functions, biological processes, and cellular components associated with genes and gene products (The Gene Ontology Consortium, 2017). GO is one of the **most widely used ontologies in genomics and implemented** in major public databases. See more details in <http://www.geneontology.org>
- **SO:** The Sequence Ontology (Eilbeck *et al.*, 2005) defines 1,454 terms to describe sequence features, such as exons, introns, and regulatory elements. It's used to annotate genomic sequences and variants. While not exclusively for experimental features, SO includes terms related to experimental features, such as "assembly", "SNP," "SSR," and "AFLP," allowing genetic markers to be annotated within a genomic context. See <http://www.sequenceontology.org/> for more details.
- **OBI:** While broader in scope, OBI is an ontology for investigations, materials, protocols and instrumentation used, the data generated and the types of analysis performed on it (Bandrowski *et al.*, 2016). It contains 4,887 terms, among them terms related to genomics research as well as terms for various biological and molecular entities as methods, which can be used to annotate genetic markers and their properties. This ontology is the foundry of new ontologies such as Next generation biobanking ontology (NGBO) (Alghamdi *et al.*, 2023). See <https://obi-ontology.org/> for more detailed description and <https://github.com/Dalalghamdi/NGBO>.
- **BAO:** is a semantic description of bioassays and high-throughput screening results (Visser *et al.*, 2011). It includes more than 8700 terms for describing various types of assays, which can include genetic assays and techniques used to analyze genetic material. See <http://bioassayontology.org/>
- **EDAM:** is domain ontology of data analysis and data management in bio- and other sciences, and science-based applications (Ison *et al.*, 2013). It comprises more around 3500 concepts related to analysis, modelling, optimisation, and data life-cycle including those used in genomics. EDAM is used in numerous resources, for example Bio.tools, Galaxy, Debian, or the ELIXIR Europe training portal TeSS. See <http://edamontology.org/page#> and https://edamontology.github.io/edam-browser/#topic_3175 for more details.
- **EFO:** provides a systematic description of more than 50.600 experimental variables available in EBI databases (Malone *et al.*, 2010), and for projects such as the EMBL-EBI GWAS catalogue. It combines parts of several biological ontologies such as OBI, GO, Cell ontology, Environment ontology (see <https://agroportal.lirmm.fr/ontologies/EFO/?p=mappings>) and aims to support the annotation, analysis and visualization of samples, phenotypes and studies. See <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/efo/> for detailed info.
- **DDBJ/ENA/GenBank Feature Table Definition:** The Feature Table Definition provides a **structured format for annotating and describing the features and characteristics of genetic sequences** in a standardized manner in the frame of INSDC (Cochrane *et al.*, 2016). This format

allows to provide detailed information about various elements within a genetic sequence, such as genes, coding regions, promoters, introns, exons, and more. While not include the rich semantics and relationships seen in more complex semantic ontologies, it does establish a standardized way of representing and communicating important information about genetic features within a sequence. For detailed info see <https://www.insdc.org/submitting-standards/feature-table/>.

- **Phenotypic Quality Ontology (PATO):** PATO provides a standardized vocabulary for describing phenotypic qualities, such as color, size, shape, and behaviour (Gkoutos *et al.*, 2004). It's used to describe phenotypes associated to genetic data in a consistent and structured manner. See <http://obofoundry.org/ontology/pato.html> for more detail

In addition, there are several ontologies specifically designed for representing plant genetics and genomics concepts and relationships related to phenotype. While most common are generic, some of them are designed specifically for an organism (for specific ontologies see databases in **Table 6**). The most common are:

- **PO:** it is a structured vocabulary and database resource that links plant anatomy, morphology and growth and development to plant genomics data (Jaiswal *et al.*, 2005). It contains more than 200 terms used to annotate metadata for genetic studies, gene expression data, phenotypic traits, and other plant-related information. For detailed info see <https://github.com/Planteome/plant-ontology>
- **TO:** it provides more than 5000 standardized terms for describing phenotypic traits in plants, including morphological, physiological, and molecular traits (Jaiswal *et al.*, 2002; Arnaud *et al.*, 2012). It supports data integration and analysis across different plant species. See <https://github.com/Planteome/plant-trait-ontology> for more information.
- **AgrO:** is an ontology for representing agronomic practices, techniques, variables and related entities. AgrO provides more than 4000 terms provides terms from the agronomy domain such data on field management, soil, weather and crop phenotypes. For detailed info see <https://bigdata.cgiar.org/resources/agronomy-ontology/> for more information.
- **CO:** provides crop-specific ontology descriptions of agronomic, morphological, physiological, quality, and stress traits along with a standard nomenclature for different plant species (Shrestha *et al.*, 2012). In August 2023 CO comprises 4,235 traits and 6,151 variables for 31 plant species. See <https://cropontology.org/> for more detailed info.
- **PECO:** it describes the treatments, growing conditions, and/or study types used in plant biology experiments (Jaiswal *et al.*, 2002). Currently has more than 3000 entries. See <https://github.com/Planteome/plant-experimental-conditions-ontology> for more information.
- **NCBI Taxonomy:** is a comprehensive hierarchical classification system that organizes and categorizes all known living organisms. It provides a curated and standardized classification and nomenclature for all of the organisms in the public sequence databases. NCBI Taxonomy provides a unique taxonomic identifier (TaxID) for each species, allowing researchers to accurately identify and reference organisms in genetic studies and to integrate genetic data from different sources by providing a common framework for species classification. Currently represents about 10% of the described species of life on the planet. For more details see <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/taxonomy>.
- **ChEBI:** is a dictionary of molecular entities focused on 'small' chemical compounds (Hastings *et al.*, 2016). It incorporates an ontological classification of 183,420 compounds, whereby the

relationships between molecular entities or classes of entities and their parents and/or children are specified. See <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/chebi/init.do>.

3.6 Review of existing Minimum reporting guidelines

Minimum reporting guidelines outline the necessary and sufficient information vital for contextualizing and understanding a digital object. They are conformed by rules, guidelines, or recommendations established by consensus and approved by a recognized body. They accurately describe the plurality of relevant attributes of experiments, protocols, and their results by harmonizing both the structure of the (meta)data and their descriptions using a controlled vocabulary. The ISA (Investigation/Study/Assay) model is often used as a framework for capturing and organizing experimental metadata to ensure compliance with Minimum Information Reporting Standards. Our survey has rendered 26 Minimum reporting guidelines for genetic data that can be used for all species (**Annex 1**).

3.6.1. Minimum reporting guidelines for sequences

The most accepted at this moment for genetic data are Minimum Information about any (x) Sequence (MIxS) developed (Field *et al.*, 2008; Yilmaz *et al.*, 2011) by the Genomic Standards Consortium (GSC) (<http://www.genesc.org/pages/standards/checklists.html>). They have been adopted by several public repositories for genetic data, including those appertaining to the INSDC and The Genomes Online Database (GOLD; <https://gold.jgi.doe.gov/>). MixS initiative provides a set of standards and guidelines for reporting biological sequence data in a consistent and informative manner. These standards are designed to ensure that essential contextual information accompanies sequence data submissions to public databases, improving the quality and usability of the data for researchers and data users. The following checklists are under the MIxS umbrella:

- MIGS: Minimum information about a genome sequence
- MIMS: Minimum information about a metagenome sequence
- MIMARKS: Minimum information about a marker gene sequence
- MISAG: Minimum information about a single amplified genome sequence
- MIMAG: Minimum information about a metagenome-assembled genome sequence
-

MIGS and MIMARKS are further divided into additional subchecklists, based on the genome sequence in question, or the sequencing type.

- MIGS-EU: MIGS for eukaryotic genome sequences
- MIGS-BA: MIGS for bacterial and archaeal genome sequences
- MIGS-PL: MIGS for plasmid sequences
- MIGS-VI: MIGS for viral genome sequences
- MIGS-ORG: MIGS for organelle sequences
- MIMARKS-SP: MIMARKS-survey for marker gene sequences obtained directly from the environment
- MIMARKS-SU: MIMARKS-specimen for marker gene sequences from cultured or voucher-identifiable specimens

In general, all MIxS checklist covered the following concepts for describe and structure metadata:

Sample, Environmental Context and Investigation:

- **Project name:** Name of the project within which the sequencing was organized.
- **Biological Source:** Information about the biological origin of the sample, including taxonomic classification and ecological context.
- **Geographical Location:** Geographic coordinates and environmental context of the sampling site.
- **Environmental Parameters:** Relevant environmental conditions of the sampling site.

Sequencing and Experimental Details:

- **Sequencing Platform:** Information about the sequencing instrument or platform used.
- **Sequencing Method:** Details about the sequencing method employed, such as shotgun or targeted sequencing.
- **Library Preparation:** Information about how the sequencing library was prepared.

Bioinformatics and Data Processing:

- **Data Processing Steps:** Description of the steps taken during data processing and analysis.
- **Assembly and Annotation:** Details about genome assembly and annotation methods used.
- **Quality and Reliability:**
- **Quality Control:** Information about quality control measures applied to the data.
- **Coverage and Read Statistics:** Data on read depth, coverage, and other relevant statistics.

Accession and Submission:

- **Accession Numbers:** Any accession numbers associated with the data submission.
- **Database and Repository:** Information about the public database or repository where the data is being submitted.

The whole list of minimum information required for the current release (v6.0) for each MIxS checklist is in **Annex 5**. This file contains the complete list of core descriptors, which are shared by all MIxS checklists and, the checklist sequence type-specific descriptors. Users of MIxS should first determine the type of genome or marker gene sequence that they have, and then proceed to complement the core descriptors with the checklist specific mandatory descriptors to achieve MIxS compliant metadata. See <http://www.gensc.org/pages/standards/checklists.html> and <https://github.com/GenomicsStandardsConsortium/mixs/tree/main> for more detailed information.

In addition, MIxS team have developed a series of environmental packages which expand on the basic set of mandatory terms to help flesh out metadata expectations for more specific environmental samples (**Annex 5**). These packages and the combination of MixS with environmental packages are described in more detail on <https://genomicsstandardsconsortium.github.io/mixs/>

One of the weaknesses of MIxS in relation to linkage with EURISCO is that MIxS Sample, Environmental Context and Investigation information is not fully compliant with other standards widely recognized for plants such as The FAO/Biodiversity Multicrop Passport Descriptors (MCPD; <https://alliancebioversityciat.org/publications-data/faoipgri-multi-crop-passport-descriptors-mcpd>) and Minimal Information About Plant Phenotyping Experiments (MIAPPE, <http://www.miappe.org/>). Despite this, MIxS enable to link plant genetic resources in EURISCO to sequences in INSDC repositories (such as BioSamples) through source materials identifiers (MIXS:0000026: source_mat_id), that can be used for PGR DOIs and (MIXS:0001107: samp_name) for BiosampleID.

3.6.1. Review of existing Minimum reporting guidelines for tracks metadata

A genetic data track refers to a visual representation of genetic or sequence-related information plotted along a linear or two-dimensional axis. These tracks are commonly used in genomics and bioinformatics to display various types of genetic and genomic data, such as DNA sequences, gene annotations, sequence variants, epigenetic modifications but they can also be queried by statistical analysis tools (Raney *et al.*, 2011; Thorvaldsdóttir *et al.*, 2013; Martin *et al.*, 2023). The visualization of data in tracks allows researchers to explore and analyse complex genetic information in a comprehensible manner. Genetic data tracks are often displayed in genome browsers or visualization tools, where they are stacked vertically or horizontally to provide an overview of the genome or a specific region of interest. Each track may represent different types of data, with its own unique visual representation and annotations. File formats used to represent tracks were not designed with FAIR data principles <https://f1000research.com/articles/10-268/v1>(Wilkinson *et al.*, 2016), in particular with respect to metadata (Gundersen *et al.*, 2011). Thus, their potential impact through re-use is greatly limited. Recently a draft for genomic track metadata (FAIRtracks) has been proposed (Gundersen *et al.*, 2021). Metadata are implemented as a set of JSON Schemas organized around four (meta)data models, namely studies, samples, experiments and track (see https://github.com/fairtracks/fairtracks_standard#overview-of-structure-of-the-fairtracks-standard and <https://fairtracks.net/fair/#fair-02-metadata-models>). The minimal set of attributes of each metadata model are:

- FAIRtracks document: Version id, version date, ontology versions, URL to original source
- Track Collection: Name, description, URL to original source, contact info
- Study: Name, publications, contact info
- Sample: Species, biospecimen class, sample type (e.g., specific cell type, cell line, tissue), phenotype
- Experiment: (Sample OR upstream experiment), technique, biological target (e.g., gene, motif, phenotype), lab/compute protocols
- Track: Assembly details, file URL, label, description, ID of source collection, IDs of raw files, file format, type of condensed data, genomeric track type, checksum

Each metadata FAIRtrack model can be mapped to objects in other revelat metadata models (**Table 8**).

Table 8. Mapping of FAIRtracks objects to objects in other metadata standards (Source (Gundersen *et al.*, 2021)).

FAIRtrack	INSDC	ISA	Other	Comments
Track collection	SRA: Submission EGA: Dataset	Investigation	Track Hub Registry: Track Hub GSuite: Track collection	Can represent both original repository submissions, as well as other sets of track files, e.g., as analysed in a research paper.
Study	Study	Study		
Sample	Sample	Sample		
Experiment	Experiment & Analysis	Assay & Process		"aggregated_from" attribute allows provenance through all experimental steps
Track	Analysis	Data	Track Hub Registry/ GSuite: Track	"raw_file_ids" can link to original data files in case a full experiment trace is not available "source_coll_ref" links to the source track collection if current collection is an <i>ad hoc</i> mix

Metadata recommendations for FAIRtracks applied to Ensembl TrackHub tracks (<https://www.ensembl.org/info/website/trackhubs/index.html>) recommend to store track file in binary formats such as BigBed, BigWig or BCF, link experiments and studies to the European Genome-phenome Archive (EGA) <https://f1000research.com/articles/10-268/v1> and Samples to as described in BioSamples. For more detail of FairTracks and tools see <https://fairtracks.net/>.

3.6.2 Review of existing standards for visual representation of genetic data

Visual representation of genetic data plays a crucial role in understanding the complexity and relationships within genomes, including the presentation of variants. There are some standards developed.

One of the most used standards for visual representation of genetic data is the Synthetic Biology Open Language Visual (SBOL Visual) (Baig *et al.*, 2021). This is a standard notation and visual representation system designed specifically to represent synthetic biology designs and genetic constructs in a standardized and intuitive way. It provides a graphical language for depicting biological parts, devices, and genetic circuits, making it easier for researchers to communicate complex synthetic biology concepts and designs. See more details in <https://sbolstandard.org/>.

Key features of SBOL Visual include:

- **Standardized Symbols:** SBOL Visual provides a set of standardized symbols and glyphs that represent various biological components, such as promoters, coding sequences, terminators, and more. These symbols are designed to be easily recognizable and consistent across different design representations.
- **Hierarchy and Composition:** SBOL Visual allows for the hierarchical representation of genetic constructs. Complex designs, such as genetic circuits composed of multiple components, can be depicted in a way that shows the arrangement and connectivity of the different parts.
- **Visual Annotation:** Annotations can be added to the symbols to provide additional information, such as the name of the component, its sequence, and other relevant metadata.

Since this SBOL Visual aims to enhance the communication and sharing of synthetic biology designs is not directly applicable for the integration of genetic data into EURISCO, however it would be useful for illustrating future genetic engineered plants.

In addition, genome browsers offer powerful **visualization** tools for genetic data, an interactive interface that allows users to navigate, analyse, and interpret genomic information, including genes, regulatory elements, variants, and more **in the context of the genome** and gain insights into **their functional effects and relationships**, which is crucial for interpreting complex genomic information and making informed research decisions. Some of the most widely used genome browsers include:

- **UCSC Genome Browser** (<https://genome.ucsc.edu/>): is one of the most widely used genome browsers. It provides a user-friendly interface to explore genomes of various species and offers a wide range of tracks for genes, transcripts, regulatory elements, genetic variants, epigenetic marks, and more, allowing multiple annotation tracks and data visualization options (**Figure 3**). UCSC Genome Browser allows users to upload and visualize their own data alongside the reference genome.

Figure 3. Snapshot of UCSC Genome Browser multiple track view

- Ensembl Genome Browser** (<http://www.ensembl.org>, <https://plants.ensembl.org>) (Figure 4): it offers a comprehensive genome annotation for a wide range of species. Ensembl provides gene annotations, transcripts, regulatory elements, variation data, and more (Yates *et al.*, 2022). It allows users to visualize their data in the context of the Ensembl genome, supports advanced searching and filtering options and offers a REST API for programmatic access to data.

Figure 4. Snapshot of Ensembl Genome Browser

- NCBI Genome Data Viewer** (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/genome/gdv/>) (Figure 5): developed by the National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI), it integrates data from GenBank, RefSeq, and other NCBI databases and provides interactive visualization of genomes with features such as genes, transcripts, and genetic variations. Also allows users to upload custom tracks.

Figure 5. Snapshot of NCBI Genome Data Viewer

In addition, genetic variants, such as single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) and insertions/deletions (indels), can be visually represented in genome browsers. Besides visual representation, these browsers also often include the position of the variant on the genome, allele frequencies, functional annotations, linkage disequilibrium (LD) pattern and phenotypic associations (Figures 6-7)

Figure 6. Snapshot variant description in EnsemblPlants.

Common (1000 Genomes Phase 3 MAF >= 1%) Short Genetic Variants from dbSNP Release 155 (rs117018032)

dbSNP: [rs117018032](#)
 Position: [chr11:71904432-71904432](#)
 Band: 11q13.4
 Genomic Size: 1
[View DNA for this feature](#) (hg19/Human)

Reference allele: G
 Alternate allele: A

Allele frequency counts:

Allele	1000Genomes	dbGaP_PopFreq	TOPMED	KOREAN	SGDP_PRJ	TOMMO	GnomAD	Korea1K
G	4949/5008 (0.988219)	14411/14420 (0.999376)	263922/264690 (0.997098)	2836/2922 (0.970568)	6/12 (0.500000)	16440/16758 (0.981024)	138612/138842 (0.998343)	1767/1832 (0.964520)
A	59/5008 (0.011781)	9/14420 (0.000624)	768/264690 (0.002902)	86/2922 (0.029432)	6/12 (0.500000)	318/16758 (0.018976)	230/138842 (0.001657)	65/1832 (0.035480)

Functional effects: [intron_variant](#)
 Submitted by: [1000GENOMES](#), [EVA](#), [GNOMAD](#), [GRF](#), [HUMAN_LONGEVITY](#), [JMKIDD_LAB](#), [KHV_HUMAN_GENOMES](#), [KOGIC](#), [KRGDB](#), [SGDP_PRJ](#), [SSMP](#), [TOMMO_GENOMICS](#), [TOPMED](#)
 Variation class/type: snv

Interesting or anomalous conditions noted by UCSC:

- Variant is "common", i.e. has a Minor Allele Frequency of at least 1% in some, but not all, projects reporting frequencies.
- Variant is "rare", i.e. has a Minor Allele Frequency of less than 1% in some, but not all, projects reporting frequencies.
- This variant overlaps another variant with a different type/class.

UCSC's predicted function relative to selected gene tracks:
 UCSC Genes FOLR1 (uc001osd.2) [intron_variant](#)
 UCSC Genes FOLR1 (uc001osb.2) [intron_variant](#)
 UCSC Genes FOLR1 (uc001osa.2) [intron_variant](#)
 UCSC Genes FOLR1 (uc001orz.2) [intron_variant](#)

[Data schema/format description and download](#)
[Go to dbSNP 155 track controls](#)

Data last updated at UCSC: 2023-03-27 11:28:33

Description

This track shows short genetic variants (up to approximately 50 base pairs) from dbSNP build 155: single-nucleotide variants (SNVs), small insertions, deletions, and complex deletion/insertions (indels), relative to the reference genome assembly. Most variants in dbSNP are rare, not true polymorphisms, and some variants are known to be pathogenic.

For hg38 (GRCh38), approximately 998 million distinct variants (RefSNP clusters with rs# ids) have been mapped to more than 1.06 billion genomic locations including alternate haplotype and fix patch sequences. dbSNP remapped variants from hg38 to hg19 (GRCh37); approximately 981 million distinct variants were mapped to more than 1.02 billion genomic locations including alternate haplotype and fix patch sequences (not all of which are included in UCSC's hg19).

This track includes four subtracks of variants:

Figure 7. Snapshot variant description in UCSC Genome Browser

3.6.3 Review of existing standards and public repositories for linked genotype and phenotype data.

Characterization/sequencing of PGRFA is regularly performed on cultivars, landraces, farmer’s breeds, or even crop wild relatives. This aims at linking phenotype and genotype (QTL and GWAS) and generally produces large amounts of (digital) data, but underlying genotype data and the associated sample and population metadata have not been routinely submitted to appropriate archives. Actually there are some standards for (meta)data of GWAs such as seqGWAS (McMahon *et al.*, 2021) and those used in GWAS Catalog (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/gwas/home>) or in the database of Genotypes and Phenotypes (dbGaP) dbGAP (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/gap/>) that can handle with array-based genotyping and sequencing-based association studies, however they are only dedicated to human biomedical research.

Several other international initiatives are on-going to agree on data models that specify standards and for different types of data in relation to linking plant phenotype to genotype facilitating the exploration of genetic variations, QTLs, genetic markers, and phenotypic traits, enabling researchers to better understand the genetic basis of plant traits and develop improved crop varieties. Most of these initiatives to standardize QTL and GWAs studies and their results are private or organism-specific initiatives , such as Gramene (<https://archive.gramene.org/qtl/>; (Tello-Ruiz *et al.*, 2021)), SoyBase (https://www.soybase.org/search/qtllist_by_symbol.php, <https://www.soybase.org/GWAS/list.php>) , MaizeGDB (<https://curation.maizegdb.org/qtl.php>), WheatIS (<https://urgi.versailles.inrae.fr/wheatis/>), CottonGen (https://www.cottongen.org/tripal_megasearch?datatype=tripal_megasearch_qtl) or Solgenomics (<https://solgenomics.net/search/phenotypes/qtl>)

Only a few initiatives aim to involve many species. The earliest one was **Minimum Information for QTLs and Association Studies (MIQAS)**. MIQAS is a standard composed by a series of file formats

designed to describe in a standardized way the results from a QTL or association study (**Figure 8**). They include

- **Experiment description file:** Contains meta-information and provides links to the rest of the data.
- **Population description file:** Describes the population used for the analysis.
- **Pedigree file:** Contains sex and pedigree for the individuals.
- **Trait description file:** Describes the trait(s) under investigation. More than one trait can be covered in a single file.
- **Marker description file:** Provides accession numbers and possible alleles for all markers.
- **Map file:** Provides the genetic map for the markers as generated on the study sample.
- **Genotype data file:** Contains the genotypes for all markers vs individuals.
- **Phenotype data file:** Contains the phenotypes for all traits vs individuals.
- **Results file:** Contains specifics for the analysis and location of qtls and associated markers.

Despite the huge effort done for built MIQAS, it is not currently maintained and no widely implemented.

Figure 8. Overview of experiment design that is covered by the MIQAS_TAB specification (source https://miqas.sourceforge.net/specification/MIQAS_TAB/MIQAS_TAB_specification.html)

In addition, the French National Institute for Agricultural, Food and Environment (INRAE) initiative GnpIS (Steinbach *et al.*, 2013) (<http://urgi.versailles.inra.fr/gnpis>) links phenomic, genetic, and genomic data and handles different types of data in the scope of genetics and genomics for plants including forest trees and fungi: genetic resources, polymorphisms and genotyping data, phenotyping data, association data, genetic maps and QTLs data.

GnpIS provides a series of complete and agreed FAIR compliant standards and ontologies for QTLs and GWAs (meta)data (**GnpisQTL**, **GnpisMetaQTL** and **GnpisAsso**) that are relevant for all species. See <https://urgi.versailles.inrae.fr/Data> for more details. See **Table 9** for a summary of main (meta)data to be submitted in these standards.

Table 9. Main information required for submission in GnpisQTL, GnpisMetaQTL and GnpisAsso standards

Sheet	Description	QTL	MetaQTL	Association
Contact	Professional information about persons involved in the project	Mandatory	Mandatory	Mandatory
Project	Information about projects	Mandatory	Mandatory	Mandatory

Institution	Information about institutions	-	-	Mandatory
Map	Information about maps	Mandatory	Mandatory	
Plant material	Information about plant accessions studied	-	-	Mandatory
Population	Information about populations studied	Mandatory	Mandatory	
Experiment	Information on experimentations	Mandatory	Mandatory	Mandatory
Variable	List of variables observed in this trial. Ideally they are part of a well identified ontology.	-	-	Mandatory
Measure	Measures for each experimentation	Mandatory	Mandatory	-
Marker	Description of the marker genomic location associated with the data.	Mandatory	Mandatory	Mandatory
Mapping	Localization of markers on a map	Mandatory	Optional	-
QTLDetection	Information on QTL detections	Mandatory	Mandatory	-
QTL	Localisation of QTLs on a map	Mandatory	Mandatory	-
QTL XREF	Description of the references for the QTL	Optional	-	-
MetaQTL	Information about metaQTLs	-	Mandatory	-
MetaAnalysis	Information about meta-analysis	-	Mandatory	-
MappingExperiment	Parameters needed for MetaQTL algorithm	-	Mandatory	-
Software	Software used	-	Mandatory	
Association analysis	associations analyses performed for this experiment	-	-	Mandatory
Linkage disequilibrium	Description of the Linkage Disequilibrium associated with the data.	-	-	Optional
Kinship	Description of the kinship associated with the data.	-	-	Optional
Structure	Description of the structure associated with the data.	-	-	Mandatory
Association results	results of association associated with the data	-	-	Mandatory
Software	Software used	-	Mandatory	-
Publication	References of each publication	Optional	Optional	Optional

The last initiative for linking plant genetic data to phenotypic data comes from the ELIXIR Plant Community (<https://elixir-europe.org/communities/plant-sciences>). ELIXIR Plant Community has created **The plant genomics tool assembly** (https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/plant_genomics_assembly), a Research Data Management Kit (RDMkit) for FAIR-ification of Plant Genotyping Data and its linking to Phenotyping (**Figure 9**). This online guide contains a set of instructions for managing plant genomics and genotyping data throughout their life cycle, with a particular focus on ensuring traceability of the biological material to enable interoperability with plant

phenotyping data.

Figure 9. The plant genomics tool assembly (source https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/plant_genomics_assembly).

The roadmap of the Plant Genomics Tool Assembly recommends to submit samples to Biosamples, before submitting genomic data, with MIAPPE compliance validated using BioSamples' [plant-miappe.json](#) template. To ensure interoperability with plant phenotyping and genotyping data, the same PUIDs must be used in both the genotyping and phenotyping experiments as well in germplasm repository, preferably EURISCO. It is recommended that the biological plant material is accurately described using MCPD. Submission of sample descriptions to BioSamples can be done as early as the data collection stage, but at the latest, must accompany submission of the genomic data to the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA) or of genotyping data to the European Variation Archive (EVA). Reference genomes for genome assembly and annotation should be obtained from Ensembl Plants or PLAZA (<https://bioinformatics.psb.ugent.be/plaza/>), if available. Genetic variant data must be produced in the VCF format enriched with VCF metadata specifications (Beier *et al.*, 2022). All sequencing data collected in plant genotyping experiments should be submitted to ENA together with metadata compliant to the GSC MixS plant associated checklist. The final results of such studies in the form of VCF files should be submitted to EVA. Variant data and its associated phenotype can be visualized and reused from Ensembl Plants, PLAZA or FAIR Data-finder for Agronomic REsearch FAIDARE (<https://urgi.versailles.inrae.fr/faidare/>).

3.7 Quality control standards: how to QC data

Quality control (QC) thresholds are often used to assess the quality and reliability of genetic data, including data related to plant genetics. One point does not record in standards and file reviewed is quality control (QC) thresholds for submitting genetic data to public repositories. While there is no specific universal QC threshold standards that apply exclusively to plant genetics, many general QC practices and guidelines are commonly followed to ensure the quality of genetic data across various organisms, including plants. In fact, the responsibility to submit high quality sequence data to public repositories lies on the authors. Some common QC steps and considerations for plant genetics data might include:

- Sequence Quality:
 - Evaluating sequence quality scores and base-call accuracy.
 - Trimming low-quality bases and adapters from sequencing reads.
- Read Mapping:
 - Assessing the alignment quality of sequencing reads to the reference genome.
 - Filtering out poorly aligned or ambiguous reads.
- Variant Calling:
 - Applying filters to variant calls to exclude low-quality or spurious variants.
 - Considering variant depth and allele frequency thresholds.
- Duplicate Removal:
 - Identifying and removing PCR or sequencing duplicates that can affect downstream analyses.
- Coverage Analysis:
 - Evaluating the coverage depth across the genome to ensure even and sufficient coverage.
- Contamination Detection:
 - Checking for potential sample cross-contamination or contamination with other species.
- Batch Effects:
 - Identifying and addressing potential batch effects or technical variations in data.

- Replication and Validation:
 - Ensuring that results are reproducible and validated using independent methods or replicates.
- Genotype Concordance:
 - Comparing genotypes with known standards or replicate samples to assess concordance.
- Variant Annotation:
 - Annotating variants with functional information and considering the impact on genes and regulatory regions.

3.8 Recommendations for linkage of genetic data with EURISCO

Following the principle of requiring minimal changes to existing systems while maximizing advantages for users (standardization, long term storage, interoperability and funding), **one practical pathway of linking genetic data with germplasm sources, such as EURISCO, is to use repositories, knowledgebases and standards implemented by the International INSDC repositories** (Manzella *et al.*, 2023), **especially those hosted in the EMBL-EBI.**

For linking genetic metadata between INSDC and EURISCO, we must consider the following steps:

- **Data Identification and Linking:** Use shared identifiers or accession numbers to link genetic data in INSDC with corresponding metadata in EURISCO.
- **Use Common Standards:** both INSDC and EURISCO support common metadata standards, we recommend using those standards to ensure data consistency and exchangeability.
- **Custom Integration:** Develop custom integration methods or middleware that can bridge the gap between the two systems, translating and transferring data as needed.
- **Data Transformation:** Convert the data from the format used by one system to a format understood by the other, ensuring data integrity and consistency.
- **Web Services and APIs:** Explore the use of web services or APIs that are specific to the types of data you're exchanging. INSDC and EURISCO might offer APIs or services that facilitate data exchange.
- **Consult Experts:** It's advisable to involve experts in data integration, biodiversity informatics, and genomics to guide the integration process effectively.

Considering these steps, we recommend:

- Follow The plant genomics tool assembly (https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/plant_genomics_assembly) for genetic data submission to EMBL-EBI
- Use the standard file formats (or their compressed versions) described in **Table 3** and if possible to use for metadata on these file header the same identifier scheme and vocabulary proposed in minimal list of metadata fields for VCF (**Table 4**) (Beier *et al.*, 2022), specially for the equivalents of reference, contig and sample (BioSample, germplasm DOI). This will allow to link, through precise sample identifiers provided by BioSamples, raw and aligned sequences and variant data to other information recorded in the same sample (e.g. phenotypic, transcriptomic, metabolomic) but also to passport data in germplasm resources such as EURISCO.

- For Gene ID use the established nomenclature standards for the genome version of the organism you are studying (**Table 6**). In addition, it should ensure that gene IDs correspond exactly to the gene/gene products for a given assembly.
- Genetic marker data use as unique ID the EVA #SS and #RS codes.
- For tracks, we recommend following FAIRtracks metadata standards, use GTrack files with rich metadata and submit them to the ENA or SRA and register in Track hub.
- Use preferentially ontologies reported in **Table 7**
- Redefine plants MixS standards to be MCPD and MIAPPE compliant.
- For GWAs and QTLs there is a need to agree standards for the plant community. A good solution would be the GnpisQTL, GnpisMetaQTL and GnpisAssso standards, however they need be MCPD and MIAPPE compliant.
- Create a centralized repository similar to those GWAS Catalog (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/gwas/home>) or database of Genotypes and Phenotypes (dbGaP) dbGAP (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/gap/>) for submitting standardized QTL and GWAS data, including those that are published in the literature
- Use Ensembl plants as standard for genome, genes and variant visualization tool.
- Define QC thresholds standards for each type of sequence submitted to the EMBL-EBI repositories.
- Promote the use of BrAPI by developing APIs to exchange associated metadata or phenotypic data linked to genetic data between INSDC and EURISCO and between INSDC and EURISCO and other repositories
- Join PRO-GRACE to ELIXIR plant community

3.9. Discussion

To better describe and understand the genome and PGR genetic diversity stored in EURISCO, whether through genotyping/re-sequencing studies or de novo sequencing of new genotypes, it is essential to integrate passport, phenotypic, and genotypic (meta)data. Both data and metadata should also be formatted in standardized representations to enable automated processing and prevent errors arising from manual manipulations, particularly in the case of extensive datasets. This necessitates a community-wide consensus on annotation guidelines and tools for data preparation.

In this deliverable, we assess the strengths and weaknesses of the most common standards and databases to evaluate their suitability for linking genetic data with EURISCO. Additionally, we propose a set of recommendations that the PRO-GRACE community can follow in pursuing this objective.

The success of these standards resides on community adoption, influenced by factors such as publisher enforcement and the availability and user-friendliness of associated tools (Adam-Blondon et al., 2016; Pommier et al., 2019; Papoutsoglou et al., 2020). To foster universal adoption of the recommended standards and their future implementation, we propose the following steps:

- Develop detailed guides and tutorials
- Store them at the EURISCO central hub for direct download, along with comprehensive guides and tutorials
- Host them on GitHub for collaborative editing and versioning
- Include them in RDMKit and Fairsharing collections to achieve wider dissemination
- Conduct training courses in collaboration with WP1 partners to educate and encourage the PGR research community to embrace reporting standards from the outset of their research

- Advocate for journal adherence to PGR reporting standards to ensure consistency in published datasets

Deviations

No deviations

References

Alghamdi D, Dooley DM, Samman M, Hsiao WWL. 2023. NGBO: Introducing -omics metadata to biobanking ontology. *bioRxiv*, 2023.05.09.539725.

Arnaud E, Cooper L, Shrestha R, Menda N, Nelson RT, Matteis L, Skofic M, Bastow R, Jaiswal P, Mueller L. 2012. Proceedings of the International Conference on Knowledge Engineering and Ontology Development.

Aubry S. 2023. Genebanking plant genetic resources in the postgenomic era. *Agriculture and Human Values*.

Baig H, Fontanarossa P, McLaughlin J, Scott-Brown J, Vaidyanathan P, Gorochofski T, Misirli G, Beal J, Myers C. 2021. Synthetic biology open language visual (SBOL visual) version 3.0. **18**.

Bandrowski A, Brinkman R, Brochhausen M, et al. 2016. The Ontology for Biomedical Investigations. *PLOS ONE* **11**, e0154556.

Beier S, Fiebig A, Pommier C, et al. 2022. Recommendations for the formatting of Variant Call Format (VCF) files to make plant genotyping data FAIR [version 2; peer review: 2 approved]. *F1000Research* **11(ELIXIR)**, 231.

Cochrane G, Karsch-Mizrachi I, Takagi T, Sequence Database Collaboration IN. 2016. The International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration. *Nucleic Acids Research* **44**, D48–D50.

Cock PJA, Fields CJ, Goto N, Heuer ML, Rice PM. 2010. The Sanger FASTQ file format for sequences with quality scores, and the Solexa/Illumina FASTQ variants. *Nucleic Acids Research* **38**, 1767–1771.

Danecek P, Auton A, Abecasis G, et al. 2011. The variant call format and VCFtools. *Bioinformatics* **27**, 2156–2158.

Eilbeck K, Lewis SE, Mungall CJ, Yandell M, Stein L, Durbin R, Ashburner M. 2005. The Sequence Ontology: a tool for the unification of genome annotations. *Genome Biology* **6**, R44.

Ewing B, Green P. 1998. Base-Calling of Automated Sequencer Traces Using Phred. II. Error Probabilities. *Genome Research* **8**, 186–194.

Ewing B, Hillier L, Wendl MC, Green P. 1998. Base-Calling of Automated Sequencer Traces Using Phred. I. Accuracy Assessment. *Genome Research* **8**, 175–185.

Field D, Garrity G, Gray T, et al. 2008. The minimum information about a genome sequence (MIGS) specification. *Nature Biotechnology* **26**, 541–547.

Gkoutos G V, Green ECJ, Mallon A-M, Hancock JM, Davidson D. 2004. Using ontologies to describe mouse phenotypes. *Genome Biology* **6**, R8.

Gundersen S, Boddu S, Capella-Gutierrez S, Drabløs F, Fernández JM, Kompova R, Taylor K, Titov D, Zerbino D, Hovig E. 2021. Recommendations for the FAIRification of genomic track metadata [version 1; peer review: 2 approved]. *F1000Research* **10(ELIXIR)**, 268.

Gundersen S, Kalaš M, Abul O, Frigessi A, Hovig E, Sandve GK. 2011. Identifying elemental genomic track types and representing them uniformly. *BMC Bioinformatics* **12**, 494.

Hastings J, Owen G, Dekker A, Ennis M, Kale N, Muthukrishnan V, Turner S, Swainston N, Mendes P,

- Steinbeck C.** 2016. ChEBI in 2016: Improved services and an expanding collection of metabolites. *Nucleic acids research* **44**, D1214-9.
- Ison J, Kalaš M, Jonassen I, Bolser D, Uludag M, McWilliam H, Malone J, Lopez R, Pettifer S, Rice P.** 2013. EDAM: an ontology of bioinformatics operations, types of data and identifiers, topics and formats. *Bioinformatics* **29**, 1325–1332.
- Jaiswal P, Avraham S, Ilic K, et al.** 2005. Plant Ontology (PO): a Controlled Vocabulary of Plant Structures and Growth Stages. *Comparative and Functional Genomics* **6**, 373740.
- Jaiswal P, Ware D, Ni J, et al.** 2002. Gramene: Development and Integration of Trait and Gene Ontologies for Rice. *Comparative and Functional Genomics* **3**, 432674.
- Karsch-Mizrachi I, Takagi T, Cochrane G, Collaboration on behalf of the INSD.** 2018. The international nucleotide sequence database collaboration. *Nucleic Acids Research* **46**, D48–D51.
- Kotni P, van Hintum T, Maggioni L, Oppermann M, Weise S.** 2023. EURISCO update 2023: the European Search Catalogue for Plant Genetic Resources, a pillar for documentation of genebank material. *Nucleic Acids Research* **51**, D1465–D1469.
- Li H, Handsaker B, Wysoker A, Fennell T, Ruan J, Homer N, Marth G, Abecasis G, Durbin R, Subgroup 1000 Genome Project Data Processing.** 2009. The Sequence Alignment/Map format and SAMtools. *Bioinformatics* **25**, 2078–2079.
- Malone J, Holloway E, Adamusiak T, Kapushesky M, Zheng J, Kolesnikov N, Zhukova A, Brazma A, Parkinson H.** 2010. Modeling sample variables with an Experimental Factor Ontology. *Bioinformatics* **26**, 1112–1118.
- Manzella D, Marsella M, Jaiswal P, Arnaud E, King B.** 2023. Digital Sequence Information and Plant Genetic Resources: Global Policy Meets Interoperability BT - Towards Responsible Plant Data Linkage: Data Challenges for Agricultural Research and Development. In: Williamson HF,, In: Leonelli S, eds. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 183–200.
- Martin FJ, Amode MR, Aneja A, et al.** 2023. Ensembl 2023. *Nucleic Acids Research* **51**, D933–D941.
- McMahon A, Lewis E, Buniello A, Cerezo M, Hall P, Sollis E, Parkinson H, Hindorff LA, Harris LW, MacArthur JAL.** 2021. Sequencing-based genome-wide association studies reporting standards. *Cell Genomics* **1**.
- Mungall CJ, Emmert DB, Consortium TF.** 2007. A Chado case study: an ontology-based modular scheme for representing genome-associated biological information. *Bioinformatics* **23**, i337–i346.
- Nakamura Y, Cochrane G, Karsch-Mizrachi I, Collaboration on behalf of the INSD.** 2013. The International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration. *Nucleic Acids Research* **41**, D21–D24.
- Nybom H, Lācis G.** 2021. Recent Large-Scale Genotyping and Phenotyping of Plant Genetic Resources of Vegetatively Propagated Crops. *Plants* **10**.
- Pearson WR, Lipman DJ.** 1988. PNAS. Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences **85**, 2444–2448.
- Raney BJ, Cline MS, Rosenbloom KR, et al.** 2011. ENCODE whole-genome data in the UCSC genome browser (2011 update). *Nucleic Acids Research* **39**, D871–D875.
- Reiser L, Harper L, Freeling M, Han B, Luan S.** 2018. FAIR: A Call to Make Published Data More Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable. *Molecular Plant* **11**, 1105–1108.
- Sansone S-A, McQuilton P, Rocca-Serra P, Gonzalez-Beltran A, Izzo M, Lister AL, Thurston M, Community the Fair.** 2019. FAIRsharing as a community approach to standards, repositories and policies. *Nature Biotechnology* **37**, 358–367.
- Sansone S-A, Rocca-Serra P, Field D, et al.** 2012. Toward interoperable bioscience data. *Nature Genetics* **44**, 121–126.

- Selby P, Abbeloos R, Backlund JE, et al.** 2019. BrAPI—an application programming interface for plant breeding applications. *Bioinformatics* **35**, 4147–4155.
- Shrestha R, Matteis L, Skofic M, Portugal A, McLaren G, Hyman G, Arnaud E.** 2012. Bridging the phenotypic and genetic data useful for integrated breeding through a data annotation using the Crop Ontology developed by the crop communities of practice . *Frontiers in Physiology* **3**.
- Steinbach D, Alaux M, Amselem J, et al.** 2013. GnpIS: an information system to integrate genetic and genomic data from plants and fungi. *Database* **2013**, bat058.
- Tello-Ruiz MK, Naithani S, Gupta P, et al.** 2021. Gramene 2021: harnessing the power of comparative genomics and pathways for plant research. *Nucleic Acids Research* **49**, D1452–D1463.
- The Gene Ontology Consortium.** 2017. Expansion of the Gene Ontology knowledgebase and resources. *Nucleic Acids Research* **45**, D331–D338.
- Thorvaldsdóttir H, Robinson JT, Mesirov JP.** 2013. Integrative Genomics Viewer (IGV): high-performance genomics data visualization and exploration. *Briefings in Bioinformatics* **14**, 178–192.
- van Treuren R, van Hintum TJL.** 2014. Next-generation genebanking: plant genetic resources management and utilization in the sequencing era. *Plant Genetic Resources* **12**, 298–307.
- Visser U, Abeyruwan S, Vempati U, Smith RP, Lemmon V, Schürer SC.** 2011. BioAssay Ontology (BAO): a semantic description of bioassays and high-throughput screening results. *BMC Bioinformatics* **12**, 257.
- Wambugu PW, Ndjiondjop M-N, Henry RJ.** 2018. Role of genomics in promoting the utilization of plant genetic resources in genebanks. *Briefings in Functional Genomics* **17**, 198–206.
- Welter D, Juty N, Rocca-Serra P, et al.** 2023. FAIR in action - a flexible framework to guide FAIRification. *Scientific Data* **10**, 291.
- Wilkinson MD, Dumontier M, Aalbersberg IJJ, et al.** 2016. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Scientific Data* **3**, 160018.
- Yates AD, Allen J, Amode RM, et al.** 2022. Ensembl Genomes 2022: an expanding genome resource for non-vertebrates. *Nucleic Acids Research* **50**, D996–D1003.
- Yilmaz P, Kottmann R, Field D, et al.** 2011. Minimum information about a marker gene sequence (MIMARKS) and minimum information about any (x) sequence (MIXS) specifications. *Nature Biotechnology* **29**, 415–420.

Annex 1. Databases, public repositories and standards in FAIRsharing.org
related to genetic information

FAIRsharing URL	FAIRsharing DOI	Record Name	Record homepage URL	Resource Type	Maintenance	Ready-to-use	FAIRorg recommended	plant accepted	species	Applied to	Type	ELIXIR recommended	provider
		BrAPI The Breeding API	https://brapi.org/	standard	maintained	ready-to-use	recommended	All plant species		Model/formats or syntax:models/syntax		recommended	
https://fairsharing.org/93	10.25504/FAIRsharing.hfgman	.ACE format	http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/ACE_%28genomic_file_format%29	standard		ready-to-use			All species	Model/formats or syntax:Format			
https://fairsharing.org/2115	10.25504/FAIRsharing.anpa6	A Systematic Annotation Package	https://asap.ahabs.wisc.edu/asap/home.php	database		ready-to-use			All species	Knowledgebase			
https://fairsharing.org/1494	10.25504/FAIRsharing.7lx4ac	Access to Biological Collection Data DNA extension	http://www.tdwg.org/standards/640/	standard		ready-to-use			All species	Minimum reporting guidelines			
https://fairsharing.org/1738	10.25504/FAIRsharing.8hcckc	Addgene	http://www.addgene.org/	database	maintained	ready-to-use	recommended		All species	Knowledgebase			
https://fairsharing.org/2584	10.25504/FAIRsharing.83wDfe	Ag Data Commons	https://data.nsl.usda.gov/	database	maintained	ready-to-use	recommended		All species	Knowledgebase			
https://fairsharing.org/1742	10.25504/FAIRsharing.kn4ycg	AgBase	http://www.agbase.msstate.edu/	database	maintained	ready-to-use		All plant species		Knowledgebase			
https://fairsharing.org/2847	10.25504/FAIRsharing.ZPRtFG	Agronomic Linked Data	http://www.agroid.org/	database	maintained	ready-to-use		All plant species		Knowledgebase			
https://fairsharing.org/2673	10.25504/FAIRsharing.ale95A	Allosteric Mutation Analysis and Polymorphism of Signaling database	http://allomaps.bii.a-star.edu.sg	database	maintained	ready-to-use			All species	Knowledgebase			
https://fairsharing.org/4894	N/A	AlphaFill	https://www.alphafill.eu	database	maintained	ready-to-use			All species	Knowledgebase			
https://fairsharing.org/1050	10.25504/FAIRsharing.9zpcgj	Amino Acid Ontology	https://robertdavidstevens.wordpress.com/2010/08/09/an-ontology-of-amino-acids/	standard	maintained	ready-to-use			All species	Semantic standards			
https://fairsharing.org/1552	10.25504/FAIRsharing.s8vrb1	Apo and Holo structures DataBase	http://ahdb.ee.ncku.edu.tw/	database					All species	Knowledgebase			
https://fairsharing.org/2894	10.25504/FAIRsharing.a308a0	DBDJ BioProject	https://www.ddbj.nig.ac.jp/bioproject/index-e.html	database		ready-to-use	recommended		All species	Data repository			DBDJ
https://fairsharing.org/1572	10.25504/FAIRsharing.k337f0	DNA Data Bank of Japan	https://www.ddbj.nig.ac.jp/ddbj	database	maintained	ready-to-use	recommended		All species	Data repository			DBDJ
https://fairsharing.org/3013	10.25504/FAIRsharing.23823e	DBDJ Sequence Read Archive	https://www.ddbj.nig.ac.jp/dra/index-e.html	database		ready-to-use	recommended		All species	Data repository			DBDJ
https://fairsharing.org/3188	10.25504/FAIRsharing.b67925	DBDJ Trace Archive	https://www.ddbj.nig.ac.jp/dta/index-e.html	database		ready-to-use			All species	Data repository			DBDJ
https://fairsharing.org/2743	10.25504/FAIRsharing.nH5Bcy	Genomic Expression Archive	https://www.ddbj.nig.ac.jp/gea	database	maintained	ready-to-use	recommended		All species	Data repository			DBDJ
https://fairsharing.org/1577	10.25504/FAIRsharing.j1wj7d	Evolutionary Genealogy of Genes: Non-supervised Orthologous Groups	http://egglog.embl.de	database		ready-to-use			All species	Knowledgebase			EMBL-EBI(EU)
https://fairsharing.org/861	10.25504/FAIRsharing.cp0fs9	ARLEQUIN Project Format	http://cmpg.unibe.ch/software/arlequin35/	standard		ready-to-use			All species	Model/formats or syntax:Format			
https://fairsharing.org/1645	10.25504/FAIRsharing.hsbpq3	Simple Modular Architecture Research Tool	http://smart.embl.de	database		ready-to-use			All species	Knowledgebase			EMBL-EBI(EU)
https://fairsharing.org/1895	10.25504/FAIRsharing.sed5tq	BAIIBASE	http://www.ligi.fr/balibase/	database		ready-to-use			All species	Knowledgebase			
https://fairsharing.org/2380	10.25504/FAIRsharing.k4yzh	BCCM/GeneCorner Plasmid Collection	http://www.genecorner.ugent.be/	database	maintained	ready-to-use			All species	Knowledgebase			UGENT(Belgium)
https://fairsharing.org/1859	10.25504/FAIRsharing.hjybwv	Ligand-Gated Ion Channel database	http://www.ebi.ac.uk/compneur-srv/LGICdb/	database					All species	Knowledgebase			EMBL-EBI(EU)
https://fairsharing.org/2156	10.25504/FAIRsharing.tkxh36	Database of Genomic Variants Archive	http://www.ebi.ac.uk/dgva/	database	maintained		recommended		All species	Knowledgebase			EMBL-EBI(EU)
https://fairsharing.org/2401	10.25504/FAIRsharing.4njvzy	BCCM/MUCL Agro-food & Environmental Fungal Collection	http://bccm.belspo.be/about-us/bccm-mucl	database	maintained	ready-to-use		All plant species		Knowledgebase			
https://fairsharing.org/188	10.25504/FAIRsharing.lkfVQ7	BcForms Grammar	https://www.bcforms.org/#grammar	standard	maintained	ready-to-use			All species	Semantic standards			
https://fairsharing.org/2630	10.25504/FAIRsharing.lf98c	BCL-2 Database	https://bcl2db.lyon.inserm.fr/BCL2DB/	database		ready-to-use			All species	Knowledgebase			
https://fairsharing.org/2240	10.25504/FAIRsharing.k5a3yt	Big Data Nucleic Acid Simulations Database	http://mmb.iribarcelona.org/BIGNASim	database	maintained	ready-to-use			All species	Knowledgebase			
https://fairsharing.org/380	10.25504/FAIRsharing.b52795	BIM	https://www.cog-genomics.org/plink2/formats#bim	standard		ready-to-use			All species	Model/formats or syntax:Format			
https://fairsharing.org/4822	N/A	Binary Call Format	http://samtools.github.io/hts-specs/BCFv2_qref.pdf	standard		ready-to-use			All species	Model/formats or syntax:Format			
https://fairsharing.org/4475	10.25504/FAIRsharing.b2f583	BioData.pt Data Management Portal	https://dmportal.biodata.pt/	database	maintained	ready-to-use		All plant species		Knowledgebase			
https://fairsharing.org/2592	10.25504/FAIRsharing.qqfxf	Bioinformatics Platform for Agroecosystem Arthropods	https://biopaa.genouest.org	database	maintained	ready-to-use		All plant species		Knowledgebase			
https://fairsharing.org/1246	10.25504/FAIRsharing.3fyavr	Bioinformatics Web Service Ontology	https://github.com/obi-webservice/OBIws	standard					All species	Semantic standards			github
https://fairsharing.org/2512	10.25504/FAIRsharing.pjj4gd	Biological and Chemical Oceanography Data Management Office	https://www.bco-dmo.org/	database	maintained	ready-to-use			All species	Knowledgebase			
https://fairsharing.org/1080	10.25504/FAIRsharing.8ktkqy	Biological Collections Ontology	https://github.com/BiodiversityOntologies/bco	standard	maintained	ready-to-use			All species	Semantic standards			github
https://fairsharing.org/2114	10.25504/FAIRsharing.p06nme	Biological Magnetic Resonance Data Bank	https://bmr.bio/	database	maintained	ready-to-use	recommended		All species	Data repository			
https://fairsharing.org/2212	10.25504/FAIRsharing.73reht	Bio-Mirror	http://www.bio-mirror.net/	database	maintained	ready-to-use			All species	Knowledgebase			
https://fairsharing.org/467	N/A	Bioversity Molecular Markers Ontology	https://croponontology.org/term/CO_500-ROOT	standard				All plant species		Semantic standards			
https://fairsharing.org/3604	10.25504/FAIRsharing.0ef9f5	Bologna Annotation Resource	https://bar.biocomp.unibo.it/bar3/	database		ready-to-use			All species	Knowledgebase			
https://fairsharing.org/2856	10.25504/FAIRsharing.2cw3HU	BonaRes Repository	https://datenzentrum.bonares.de/research-data.php	database	maintained	ready-to-use			All species	Data repository			
https://fairsharing.org/1850	10.25504/FAIRsharing.dj8nt8	European Nucleotide Archive	http://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena	database	maintained	ready-to-use	recommended		All species	Data repository	recommended		EMBL-EBI(EU)
https://fairsharing.org/1098	10.25504/FAIRsharing.Hbvvle	BpForms Grammar	https://www.bpforms.org/#grammar	standard	maintained	ready-to-use			All species	Semantic standards			
https://fairsharing.org/3186	10.25504/FAIRsharing.ac95d5	Bridges	https://bridges.monash.edu/	database	maintained	ready-to-use			All species	Knowledgebase			
https://fairsharing.org/3566	10.25504/FAIRsharing.313630	CABRI Guidelines for Catalogue Production	http://cabri.org/guidelines/catalogue/CPcover.html	standard	maintained	ready-to-use		All plant species		Model/formats or syntax:models/syntax			
https://fairsharing.org/1333	10.25504/FAIRsharing.2b3at8	Marine Microbial Biodiversity, Bioinformatics, Biotechnology Checklist	http://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/submit/microb3-checklist	standard		ready-to-use			All species	Minimum reporting guidelines			EMBL-EBI(EU)
https://fairsharing.org/2155	10.25504/FAIRsharing.6824pv	European Variation Archive	http://www.ebi.ac.uk/eva/	database	maintained	ready-to-use	recommended		All species	Data repository	recommended		EMBL-EBI(EU)
https://fairsharing.org/1560	10.25504/FAIRsharing.r3pbp3	CAPS-DB : a structural classification of helix-capping motifs	http://www.bioinsilico.org/CAPSDb	database		ready-to-use			All species	Knowledgebase			
https://fairsharing.org/1730	10.25504/FAIRsharing.dkbt9j	Carbohydrate Structure Database	http://csdb.glycoscience.ru/database/	database	maintained	ready-to-use		All plant species		Knowledgebase			
https://fairsharing.org/1852	10.25504/FAIRsharing.7fjfgc	Gene Ontology Annotation Database	http://www.ebi.ac.uk/GOA	database	maintained	ready-to-use	recommended		All species	Knowledgebase			EMBL-EBI(EU)
https://fairsharing.org/1588	10.25504/FAIRsharing.f5zx00	Expression Atlas	http://www.ebi.ac.uk/gxa	database	maintained	ready-to-use	recommended		All species	Data repository			EMBL-EBI(EU)
https://fairsharing.org/2047	10.25504/FAIRsharing.2s4n8r	MEROPS	http://www.ebi.ac.uk/merops/	database		ready-to-use	recommended		All species	Knowledgebase			EMBL-EBI(EU)
https://fairsharing.org/1847	10.25504/FAIRsharing.e58gcm	Chemical Component Dictionary	http://www.ebi.ac.uk/pdbe-srv/pdbechem/	database		ready-to-use			All species	Knowledgebase			EMBL-EBI(EU)
https://fairsharing.org/227	10.25504/FAIRsharing.qz0rvm	Variant Effect Predictor data format	http://www.ensembl.org/info/docs/tools/vep/vep_formats.html	standard		ready-to-use			All species	Model/formats or syntax:Format			EMBL-EBI(EU)
https://fairsharing.org/2386	10.25504/FAIRsharing.923a0p	Ensembl Genomes	https://ensemblgenomes.org/	database	maintained	ready-to-use		All plant species		Knowledgebase	recommended		EMBL-EBI(EU)

FAIRsharing URL	FAIRsharing DOI	Record Name	Record homepage URL	Resource Type	Maintenance	Ready-to-use	FAIRorg recommended	plant accepted species	species	Applied to	Type	ELIXIR recommended	provider
https://fairsharing.org/2404	10.25504/FAIRsharing.j8g2cv	Ensembl Plants	https://plants.ensembl.org/index.html	database	maintained	ready-to-use		All plant species		Knowledgebase	recommended	EMBL-EBI(EU)	
https://fairsharing.org/1845	10.25504/FAIRsharing.6k0kw	ArrayExpress	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/arrayexpress/	database	maintained	ready-to-use	recommended		All species	Data repository	recommended	EMBL-EBI(EU)	
https://fairsharing.org/1554	10.25504/FAIRsharing.ewjdq6	BioSamples at the European Bioinformatics Institute	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biosamples/	database	maintained	ready-to-use	recommended		All species	Data repository	recommended	EMBL-EBI(EU)	
https://fairsharing.org/1280	10.25504/FAIRsharing.q72e3w	Short Read Archive eXTensible Markup Language	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/submit/read-xml-format-1-5	standard		ready-to-use	recommended		All species	Model/formats syntax:models/syntax	or	EMBL-EBI(EU)	
https://fairsharing.org/2691	10.25504/FAIRsharing.A0ozDj	Genome Properties	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/interpro/genomeproperties	database	maintained	ready-to-use			All species	Knowledgebase		EMBL-EBI(EU)	
https://fairsharing.org/2129	10.25504/FAIRsharing.dxj07r	MGNify	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/	database	maintained	ready-to-use	recommended		All species	Knowledgebase		EMBL-EBI(EU)	
https://fairsharing.org/1851	10.25504/FAIRsharing.p3n3fn	Patent Data Resources	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/patentdata	database		ready-to-use			All species	Knowledgebase		EMBL-EBI(EU)	
https://fairsharing.org/378	10.25504/FAIRsharing.h4rs6h	GO-PLUS	http://geneontology.org/docs/download-ontology/#go_plus_owl	standard		ready-to-use			All species	Semantic standards		GBC(USA)	
https://fairsharing.org/1466	10.25504/FAIRsharing.rtm51	Gene Product Annotation Data	http://geneontology.org/docs/gene-product-association-data-gpad-format/	standard	maintained	ready-to-use			All species	Model/formats syntax:Format	or	GBC(USA)	
https://fairsharing.org/1468	10.25504/FAIRsharing.820ebm	Gene Product Information Format	http://geneontology.org/docs/gene-product-information-gpi-format/	standard	maintained	ready-to-use			All species	Model/formats syntax:Format	or	GBC(USA)	
https://fairsharing.org/1095	10.25504/FAIRsharing.IIMCe0	Gene Ontology Gene Association File Format 2.0	http://geneontology.org/docs/go-annotation-file-gaf-format-2.0/	standard	maintained				All species	Model/formats syntax:Format	or	GBC(USA)	
https://fairsharing.org/766	10.25504/FAIRsharing.FGJ2T8	Gene Ontology (GO) Gene Association File Format 2.1	http://geneontology.org/docs/go-annotation-file-gaf-format-2.1/	standard	maintained	ready-to-use			All species	Model/formats syntax:Format	or	GBC(USA)	
https://fairsharing.org/1418	10.25504/FAIRsharing.77bbf	Gene Ontology (GO) Gene Association File Format 2.2	http://geneontology.org/docs/go-annotation-file-gaf-format-2.2/	standard	maintained	ready-to-use			All species	Model/formats syntax:Format	or	GBC(USA)	
https://fairsharing.org/2077	10.25504/FAIRsharing.s1ne3g	UniProt Knowledgebase	https://www.uniprot.org	database	maintained	ready-to-use	recommended		All species	Knowledgebase		GBC(USA)	
https://fairsharing.org/1237	10.25504/FAIRsharing.xhwrnr	Cell Cycle Ontology	https://www.biogateway.eu/tools/#CCO	standard	maintained	ready-to-use			All species	Semantic standards			
https://fairsharing.org/2069	10.25504/FAIRsharing.ntv8pe	Chemical Effects in Biological Systems	https://doi.org/10.22427/NTP-DATA-1	database		ready-to-use			All species	Knowledgebase			
https://fairsharing.org/2748	10.25504/FAIRsharing.9bRrVC	China National GeneBank DataBase	https://db.cngb.org/	database	maintained	ready-to-use	recommended		All species	Data repository			
https://fairsharing.org/3966	10.25504/FAIRsharing.b52cce	CIRAD Dataverse	https://doi.org/10.18167/infrastructure/00003	database	maintained	ready-to-use		All plant species		Knowledgebase			
https://fairsharing.org/122	10.25504/FAIRsharing.jx6ea0	CLUSTAL-W Alignment Format	http://www.clustal.org/clustal2/	standard	maintained	ready-to-use			All species	Model/formats syntax:Format	or		
https://fairsharing.org/1429	10.25504/FAIRsharing.8y5ayx	Common Workflow Language	http://www.commonwl.org	standard	maintained	ready-to-use			All species	Model/formats syntax:models/syntax	or		
https://fairsharing.org/1155	10.25504/FAIRsharing.kay31r	Comparative Data Analysis Ontology	https://github.com/evoinfo/cdao	standard	maintained	ready-to-use			All species	Semantic standards		github	
https://fairsharing.org/1902	10.25504/FAIRsharing.wyz5he	Conformation Angles Database	http://cluster.physics.iisc.ernet.in/cadb/	database		ready-to-use			All species	Knowledgebase			
https://fairsharing.org/292	10.25504/FAIRsharing.695abb	Connectivity Table file format	http://rna.urmc.rochester.edu/Text/File_Formats.html#CT	standard		ready-to-use			All species	Model/formats syntax:Format	or		
https://fairsharing.org/889	10.25504/FAIRsharing.VJDEtI	Cooler file format	https://cooler.readthedocs.io/en/latest/datamodel.html	standard	maintained	ready-to-use			All species	Model/formats syntax:Format	or		
https://fairsharing.org/2688	10.25504/FAIRsharing.02xjaW	CyVerse Data Common Repository	http://datacommons.cyverse.org/	database	maintained	ready-to-use			All species	Data repository			
https://fairsharing.org/841	10.25504/FAIRsharing.hgsFle	Darwin Core Germplasm	https://github.com/dagendresen/darwincore-germplasm	standard	maintained	ready-to-use			All species	Semantic standards		github	
https://fairsharing.org/1566	10.25504/FAIRsharing.evt6z5	Database of Aligned Ribosomal Complexes	http://darcsite.genzentrum.lmu.de/darc/	database		ready-to-use			All species	Knowledgebase			
https://fairsharing.org/2385	10.25504/FAIRsharing.m58329	Database Of Local Biomolecular Conformers	http://dolbico.org/	database		ready-to-use			All species	Knowledgebase			
https://fairsharing.org/2350	10.25504/FAIRsharing.hjnp0	Database of local DNA conformers	http://ich.vsch.tz/projects/dolce/viewHome	database	maintained	ready-to-use			All species	Knowledgebase			
https://fairsharing.org/1743	10.25504/FAIRsharing.1bnhyh	Databases of Orthologous Promoters	http://doop.abc.hu/	database		ready-to-use		All plant species		Knowledgebase			
https://fairsharing.org/3010	10.25504/FAIRsharing.Nmigg9	Datanator	https://www.datanator.info	database	maintained	ready-to-use			All species	Knowledgebase			
https://fairsharing.org/2414	10.25504/FAIRsharing.yf778h	DataONE	https://www.dataone.org	database	maintained	ready-to-use	recommended	All plant species		Knowledgebase			
https://fairsharing.org/2040	10.25504/FAIRsharing.52qw6p	Description of Plant Viruses	http://www.dpweb.net	database		ready-to-use		All plant species		Knowledgebase			
https://fairsharing.org/3314	10.25504/FAIRsharing.8d2e5c	DIGITAL.CSIC	https://digital.csic.es/	database	maintained	ready-to-use			All species	Knowledgebase			
https://fairsharing.org/2765	10.25504/FAIRsharing.23bdba	DISNOR	https://disnor.uniroma2.it/	database		ready-to-use			All species	Knowledgebase			
https://fairsharing.org/2526	10.25504/FAIRsharing.r4gyp	Disordered Binding Sites Database	http://dbs.enzim.ttk.mta.hu	database	maintained	ready-to-use			All species	Knowledgebase			
https://fairsharing.org/143	10.25504/FAIRsharing.mcgj5b	Distributed Sequence Annotation System	http://www.biodas.org/documents/spec-1.6.html	standard		ready-to-use			All species	Model/formats syntax:models/syntax	or		
https://fairsharing.org/2860	10.25504/FAIRsharing.qgMKai	DNA Modification Database	https://dnamod.hoffmanlab.org/	database	maintained	ready-to-use			All species	Knowledgebase			
https://fairsharing.org/2865	10.25504/FAIRsharing.VXoFlf	Domain-centric GO	http://supfam.org/SUPERFAMILY/dcGO/index.html	database	maintained	ready-to-use			All species	Knowledgebase			
https://fairsharing.org/144	10.25504/FAIRsharing.4xrwz1	Dot Bracket Notation (DBN) - Vienna Format	https://www.tbi.univie.ac.at/RNA/ViennaRNA/doc/html/rna_structure_notations.html#dot-bracket-notation	standard		ready-to-use			All species	Model/formats syntax:Format	or		
https://fairsharing.org/3015	10.25504/FAIRsharing.04fcf5	EMDataResource	http://www.emdataresource.org/	database		ready-to-use	recommended		All species	Knowledgebase			
https://fairsharing.org/1478	10.25504/FAIRsharing.q9nh66	ENA Sequence Flat File Format	https://ena-docs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/submit/fileprep/flat-file-example.html	standard	maintained	ready-to-use			All species	Model/formats syntax:Format	or	recommended	
https://fairsharing.org/1061	10.25504/FAIRsharing.9ed958	ENA Sequence XML Schema	https://ena-docs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/submit/general-guide/programmatic.html	standard		ready-to-use			All species	Model/formats syntax:models/syntax	or	recommended	
https://fairsharing.org/2683	10.25504/FAIRsharing.OVV4KB	Environmental Data Portal	https://www.envdat.ch/	database	maintained	ready-to-use			All species	Knowledgebase			
https://fairsharing.org/511	10.25504/FAIRsharing.xmmsmr	Epigenome Ontology	https://github.com/EGO-ontology	standard		ready-to-use			All species	Semantic standards		github	
https://fairsharing.org/4329	10.25504/FAIRsharing.1a0bbf	ERIC/open	https://opendata.eawag.ch/	database	maintained	ready-to-use		All plant species		Knowledgebase			
https://fairsharing.org/1484	10.25504/FAIRsharing.9hr9j	Eukaryotic Pathogen, Host & Vector Genomics Resource Ontology	https://github.com/VEUPathDB-ontology/VEUPathDB-ontology	standard	maintained	ready-to-use			All species	Semantic standards		github	
https://fairsharing.org/4715	10.25504/FAIRsharing.c3521d	EvolclustDB	http://evolclustdb.org/	database	maintained	ready-to-use		All plant species		Knowledgebase			
https://fairsharing.org/1757	10.25504/FAIRsharing.4eanvm	Evolutionary Trace	http://mammoth.bcm.tmc.edu/ETserver.html	database		ready-to-use			All species	Knowledgebase			
https://fairsharing.org/1581	10.25504/FAIRsharing.z20e8b	ExoCarta	http://www.exocarta.org	database		ready-to-use			All species	Knowledgebase			

FAIRsharing URL	FAIRsharing DOI	Record Name	Record homepage URL	Resource Type	Maintenance	Ready-to-use	FAIROrg recommended	plant accepted	species	Applied to	Type	ELIXIR recommended	provider
https://fairsharing.org/2262	10.25504/FAIRsharing.nnvcr9	FAIRDOMHub	https://fairdomhub.org/	database	maintained	ready-to-use				All species	Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/3640	10.25504/FAIRsharing.807b9d	FAIRtracks	https://fairtracks.net	standard	maintained	ready-to-use				All species	Model/formats syntax:models/syntax	or recommended	
https://fairsharing.org/985	10.25504/FAIRsharing.cz2fa	Fanconi Anemia Ontology	http://lab.rockefeller.edu/smogorzewska/far/	standard		ready-to-use				All species	Semantic standards		
https://fairsharing.org/114	10.25504/FAIRsharing.r2ts5t	FASTQ Sequence and Sequence Quality Format	http://news.open-bio.org/news/2009/12/nar-fastq-format/	standard		ready-to-use				All species	Model/formats syntax:Format	or	
https://fairsharing.org/478	10.25504/FAIRsharing.haxp7g	Feature Annotation Location Description Ontology	http://biohackathon.org/resource/faldo	standard	maintained	ready-to-use				All species	Semantic standards		
https://fairsharing.org/2516	10.25504/FAIRsharing.7zfq1a	FlavorDB	http://cosylab.iitd.edu.in/flavordb	database	maintained	ready-to-use				All species	Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/3102	10.25504/FAIRsharing.5fXDoZ	French Biodiversity (meta)data repository	https://data.pndb.fr/	database	maintained	ready-to-use				All species	Data repository		
https://fairsharing.org/868	10.25504/FAIRsharing.8xecy7	FuGEFlow	http://flowcyt.sourceforge.net/fugeflow/	standard						All species	Minimum reporting guidelines	or	sourceforge(USA)
https://fairsharing.org/1270	10.25504/FAIRsharing.namxmf	Functional Genomics Experiment Markup Language	http://fuge.sourceforge.net/dev/index.php	standard						All species	Model/formats syntax:models/syntax	or	sourceforge(USA)
https://fairsharing.org/1586	10.25504/FAIRsharing.556qpw	FunTree: A Resource For Exploring The Functional Evolution Of Structurally Defined Enzyme Superfamilies	http://www.funtree.info/FunTree/	database		ready-to-use				All species	Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/2163	10.25504/FAIRsharing.zv1j13	GBIF.org	https://www.gbif.org	database	maintained	ready-to-use	recommended			All species	Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/1660	10.25504/FAIRsharing.fyqk5z	Gene3D	http://gene3d.biochem.ucl.ac.uk	database						All species	Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/414	10.25504/FAIRsharing.o257ar	GenePattern GeneSet Table Format	http://software.broadinstitute.org/cancer/software/genepattern/file-formats-guide	standard	maintained	ready-to-use				All species	Model/formats syntax:Format	or	
https://fairsharing.org/2136	10.25504/FAIRsharing.qmygaa	GeneProf	http://www.geneprof.org	database	maintained					All species	Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/1348	10.25504/FAIRsharing.dnk0f6	Generic Feature Format Version 3	https://github.com/The-Sequence-Ontology/Specifications/blob/master/gff3.md	standard	maintained	ready-to-use				All species	Model/formats syntax:Format	or	github
https://fairsharing.org/1590	10.25504/FAIRsharing.1ety1h	GeneSigDB: a manually curated database and resource for analysis of gene expression signatures	http://www.genesigdb.org	database						All species	Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/1062	10.25504/FAIRsharing.qjzx96	Genetic Testing Ontology	http://qianzhu-lab.umbc.edu/	standard						All species	Semantic standards		
https://fairsharing.org/57	10.25504/FAIRsharing.sbbbf6	Genome Biology Ontology Language	http://gbol.life	standard	maintained					All species	Model/formats syntax:models/syntax	or	
https://fairsharing.org/379	10.25504/FAIRsharing.pkw5bj	Genome Variation Format	https://github.com/The-Sequence-Ontology/Specifications/blob/master/gvf.md	standard	maintained	ready-to-use				All species	Model/formats syntax:Format	or	github
https://fairsharing.org/69	10.25504/FAIRsharing.2hh7g7	Genomic Contextual Data Markup Language	https://www.liebertpub.com/doi/10.1089/omi.2008.0A10	standard	maintained	ready-to-use				All species	Model/formats syntax:models/syntax	or	
https://fairsharing.org/279	10.25504/FAIRsharing.y1mmbv	Genomic Epidemiology Ontology	https://genepio.org/	standard	maintained	ready-to-use				All species	Semantic standards		
https://fairsharing.org/1328	10.25504/FAIRsharing.vbejb6	Genomic Feature and Variation Ontology	https://github.com/BioInterchange/Ontologies	standard		ready-to-use				All species	Semantic standards		github
https://fairsharing.org/3019	10.25504/FAIRsharing.wOCTaM	Genomic Observatories Meta-Database	https://geome-db.org/	database	maintained	ready-to-use				All species	Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/3626	10.25504/FAIRsharing.3da56b	Genomics Cohorts Knowledge Ontology	https://github.com/IHCC-cohorts/GECKO	standard	maintained	ready-to-use				All species	Semantic standards		github
https://fairsharing.org/688	10.25504/FAIRsharing.kpbna7	Genotype Ontology	https://github.com/monarch-initiative/GENO-ontology/	standard		ready-to-use				All species	Semantic standards		github
https://fairsharing.org/2125	10.25504/FAIRsharing.rcbwsf	Giga Science Database	http://gigadb.org/	database	maintained	ready-to-use	recommended			All species	Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/4445	10.25504/FAIRsharing.84b518	Gigwa	https://gigwa.southgreen.fr/	database	maintained	ready-to-use				All species	Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/787	10.25504/FAIRsharing.fff3b2	Global Genome Biodiversity Network Data Standard	https://wiki.ggbn.org/ggbn/GGBN_Data_Standard	standard		ready-to-use				All species	Minimum reporting guidelines		
https://fairsharing.org/632	10.25504/FAIRsharing.9ry4cz	GoMapMan	https://gomapman.nib.si/	database	maintained	ready-to-use			All plant species		Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/2086	10.25504/FAIRsharing.wfrsvq	gpDB	http://bioinformatics.biol.uoa.gr/gpDB	database		ready-to-use				All species	Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/2235	10.25504/FAIRsharing.fe9kyy	Green Non-Coding Database	http://greenc.sequentiabiotech.com/wiki2/Main_Page	database	maintained	ready-to-use			All plant species		Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/1947	10.25504/FAIRsharing.bpxgb6	Greengenes	http://greengenes.lbl.gov	database		ready-to-use				All species	Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/1827	10.25504/FAIRsharing.j98570	GreenPhylDB: A phylogenomic database for plant comparative genomics	http://www.greenphyl.org	database	maintained	ready-to-use			All plant species		Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/1084	10.25504/FAIRsharing.y49yj6	Herbarium information standards and protocols for interchange of data	https://github.com/tdwg/prior-standards/tree/master/hispid3	standard		ready-to-use			All plant species		Minimum reporting guidelines		github
https://fairsharing.org/698	10.25504/FAIRsharing.gaqfk4	HGeneCodonOntology	http://blog.51.ca/u-345129/	standard						All species	Semantic standards		
https://fairsharing.org/472	10.25504/FAIRsharing.n3rt95	HMMER Profile File Format	http://www.hmmer.org	standard		ready-to-use				All species	Model/formats syntax:Format	or	
https://fairsharing.org/4454	10.25504/FAIRsharing.a945b0	HostDB	https://hostdb.org/hostdb/app	database	maintained	ready-to-use				All species	Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/1595	10.25504/FAIRsharing.m4a6d3	HotRegion	http://prism.cccb.ku.edu.tr/hotregion	database						All species	Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/342	10.25504/FAIRsharing.8drfwh	ICM binary file Format	http://www.molsoft.com/icm/files.html	standard		ready-to-use				All species	Model/formats syntax:Format	or	
https://fairsharing.org/4293	10.25504/FAIRsharing.bbd7df	IEEE 2791-2020	https://standards.ieee.org/ieee/2791/7337/	standard	maintained	ready-to-use				All species	Minimum reporting guidelines		
https://fairsharing.org/2777	10.25504/FAIRsharing.PeLjos	iGEM Registry of Standard Biological Parts	http://parts.igem.org	database	maintained	ready-to-use				All species	Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/2303	10.25504/FAIRsharing.6wf1zw	Image Data Resource	https://idr.openmicroscopy.org	database	maintained	ready-to-use	recommended		All plant species		Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/1664	10.25504/FAIRsharing.a4ybgg	Indel Flanking Region Database	http://indel.bioinfo.sdu.edu.cn	database						All species	Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/1600	10.25504/FAIRsharing.smq7y7	InterEvol database	http://biodev.cea.fr/interevol/	database		ready-to-use				All species	Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/2908	N/A	Internal Control Genes	http://icg.big.ac.cn/index.php/Main_Page	database						All species	Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/1501	10.25504/FAIRsharing.yhLgTV	Investigation Study Assay JSON	https://isa-specs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/isajson.html	standard	maintained	ready-to-use				All species	Model/formats syntax:models/syntax	or	
https://fairsharing.org/1497	10.25504/FAIRsharing.53gp75	Investigation Study Assay Tabular	https://isa-specs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/isatab.html	standard	maintained	ready-to-use	recommended			All species	Model/formats syntax:models/syntax	or	
https://fairsharing.org/2750	N/A	ionomicHUB	https://www.ionomicshub.org/home/PiIMS	database					All plant species		Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/2492	10.25504/FAIRsharing.ekdqe5	iReceptor Public Archive	https://www.i-receptor.org/	database	maintained	ready-to-use				All species	Knowledgebase		

FAIRsharing URL	FAIRsharing DOI	Record Name	Record homepage URL	Resource Type	Maintenance	Ready-to-use	FAIRorg recommended	plant species accepted	Applied to species	Type	ELIXIR recommended	provider
https://fairsharing.org/950	10.25504/FAIRsharing.dee5fb	IUPAC-IUB Commission on Biochemical Nomenclature - Abbreviations and Symbols for Nucleic Acids, Polynucleotides and their Constituents	https://www.qmul.ac.uk/sbcs/iupac/misc/naabb.html	standard		ready-to-use			All species	Semantic standards		
https://fairsharing.org/959	10.25504/FAIRsharing.d5a210	IUPAC-IUB Joint Commission on Biochemical Nomenclature - Nomenclature and Symbolism for Amino Acids and Peptides	https://www.qmul.ac.uk/sbcs/iupac/misc/naabb.html	standard		ready-to-use			All species	Semantic standards		
https://fairsharing.org/1936	10.25504/FAIRsharing.vd25jp	J-GLOBAL	https://jglobal.jst.go.jp/en	database		ready-to-use			All species	Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/1661	10.25504/FAIRsharing.5q1p14	Joint Genome Institute, Genomes OnLine Database	https://gold.jgi.doe.gov/	database	maintained	ready-to-use	recommended		All species	Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/3618	10.25504/FAIRsharing.826b4a	KnetMiner	https://knetminer.com	database	maintained	ready-to-use		All plant species		Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/4783	10.25504/FAIRsharing.d30a2a	KNOTTIN database	https://www.dsimb.inserm.fr/KNOTTIN/	database		ready-to-use			All species	Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/2189	10.25504/FAIRsharing.327nbg	Kyoto Encyclopedia of Genes and Genomes	http://www.genome.jp/kegg/	database		ready-to-use			All species	Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/2325	10.25504/FAIRsharing.dq46p7	Life Science Database Archive	http://dbarchive.biosciencedbc.jp/index-e.html	database	maintained	ready-to-use	recommended		All species	Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/2043	10.25504/FAIRsharing.2ma4gq	Ligand Expo	http://ligand-depot.rutgers.edu/	database		ready-to-use			All species	Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/2623	N/A	Longhorn Array Database	http://darwin.biochem.okstate.edu/lad/liat/	database					All species	Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/3674	N/A	LUCAPedia	http://eebgroups.princeton.edu/luccapedia/index.html	database					All species	Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/2469	10.25504/FAIRsharing.gdj215	Madagascar Biodiversity Information Facility IPT - GBIF France	http://ipt.madbif.mg/	database	maintained				All species	Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/430	10.25504/FAIRsharing.53edcc	MAP	https://www.ccg-genomics.org/plink2/formats#map	standard		ready-to-use			All species	Model/formats syntax:Format	or	
https://fairsharing.org/2419	10.25504/FAIRsharing.11eyq2	mentha	http://mentha.uniroma2.it/	database	maintained				All species	Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/115	10.25504/FAIRsharing.wjwb5c	CHADO XML	http://gmod.org/wiki/Chado_XML	standard	maintained	ready-to-use			All species	Model/formats syntax:models/syntax	or	GMOD
https://fairsharing.org/1347	10.25504/FAIRsharing.bfqdc8	Generic Feature Format Version 2	http://gmod.org/wiki/GFF2	standard					All species	Model/formats syntax:Format	or	GMOD
https://fairsharing.org/2051	10.25504/FAIRsharing.z1cxj	PeroxiBase	http://peroxidebase.toulouse.inra.fr/	database		ready-to-use			All species	Knowledgebase		INRA(FRA)
https://fairsharing.org/2608	10.25504/FAIRsharing.1788mT	Portail Data INRAE	https://data.inrae.fr/	database	maintained			All plant species		Data repository		INRA(FRA)
https://fairsharing.org/1499	10.25504/FAIRsharing.l9wne	Open Data for Access and Mining Structural Metadata	https://inrae.github.io/ODAM/data-preparation/	standard	maintained	ready-to-use			All species	Minimum reporting guidelines		INRA(FRA)
https://fairsharing.org/2263	10.25504/FAIRsharing.dw22y3	Genetic and Genomic Information System	https://urgi.versailles.inra.fr/gnpgis	database	maintained	ready-to-use		All plant species		Data repository		INRA(FRA)
https://fairsharing.org/1427	10.25504/FAIRsharing.4c7c1c	DDBI/ENA/GenBank Feature Table	http://www.insdc.org/documents/feature-table	standard		ready-to-use			All species	Model/formats syntax:models/syntax	recommended	INSDC
https://fairsharing.org/438	10.25504/FAIRsharing.tn873z	INSD sequence record XML	http://www.insdc.org/documents/xml-status	standard		ready-to-use			All species	Model/formats syntax:models/syntax	or	INSDC
https://fairsharing.org/4211	10.25504/FAIRsharing.209c8e	Metadata Schema for the Persistent Identification of Instruments (1.0)	https://doi.org/10.15497/ROA00070	standard		ready-to-use			All species	Model/formats syntax:models/syntax	or	
https://fairsharing.org/768	10.25504/FAIRsharing.xfje21	Metagenome Sample Vocabulary	http://mdb.bio.titech.ac.jp/msv	standard					All species	Semantic standards		
https://fairsharing.org/1682	10.25504/FAIRsharing.htzqwqf	PASS2	http://caps.ncbs.res.in/pass2/	database		ready-to-use			All species	Knowledgebase		Lab 25 NCBS (INDIA)
https://fairsharing.org/354	10.25504/FAIRsharing.rvvbCB	Meta-omics Data and Collection Objects	https://www.mod-co.net/wiki/Schema_Representations	standard	maintained	ready-to-use			All species	Model/formats syntax:models/syntax	or	
https://fairsharing.org/3569	10.25504/FAIRsharing.fa85ba	MetaPhOres	http://orthology.phylomedb.org/	database	maintained	ready-to-use			All species	Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/849	10.25504/FAIRsharing.k893xa	MHC Restriction Ontology	https://github.com/IEDB/MRO	standard	maintained	ready-to-use			All species	Semantic standards		github
https://fairsharing.org/1193	10.25504/FAIRsharing.qs4x5m	Microarray and Gene Expression Data Ontology	http://mged.sourceforge.net/ontologies/MGEDontology.php	standard	maintained		recommended		All species	Semantic standards		sourceforge(USA)
https://fairsharing.org/1962	10.25504/FAIRsharing.cwn40y	Sequence-Structural Templates of Single-member Superfamilies	http://caps.ncbs.res.in/SSTOSS/index.htm	database		ready-to-use			All species	Knowledgebase		Lab 25 NCBS (INDIA)
https://fairsharing.org/620	10.25504/FAIRsharing.rz4vfj	FASTA Sequence Format	http://blast.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/blastcgihelp.shtml	standard	maintained	ready-to-use			All species	Model/formats syntax:Format	or	NCBI (USA)
https://fairsharing.org/1973	10.25504/FAIRsharing.wk5azf	Database of Sequence Tagged Sites	http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/dbSTS/index.html	database					All species	Knowledgebase		NCBI (USA)
https://fairsharing.org/1222	10.25504/FAIRsharing.x964fb	MicroArray Gene Expression Markup Language	http://www.mged.org/Workgroups/MAGE/mage-ml.html	standard					All species	Model/formats syntax:models/syntax	or	
https://fairsharing.org/1254	10.25504/FAIRsharing.ak8p5g	MicroArray Gene Expression Tabular Format	https://www.fged.org/projects/mage-tab	standard		ready-to-use			All species	Model/formats syntax:models/syntax	or	
https://fairsharing.org/4456	10.25504/FAIRsharing.z73460	MicrobiomeDB	https://microbiomedb.org/mbio/app/	database	maintained	ready-to-use			All species	Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/1606	10.25504/FAIRsharing.bv0zjz	Mimotope Database	http://immunet.cn/mimodb	database					All species	Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/1607	10.25504/FAIRsharing.wqtfkv	MINAS - A Database of Metal Ions in Nucleic Acids	http://www.minas.uzh.ch	database					All species	Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/1986	10.25504/FAIRsharing.b5ann2	Plant Genome Central	http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/genomes/PLANTS/PlantList.html	database				All plant species		Data repository		NCBI (USA)
https://fairsharing.org/217	10.25504/FAIRsharing.gaey8	MIAME Notation in Markup Language	http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/info/MINIAML.html	standard	maintained	ready-to-use	recommended		All species	Model/formats syntax:models/syntax	or	NCBI (USA)
https://fairsharing.org/1206	10.25504/FAIRsharing.a5Sz32	Minimal Information about a high throughput SEQUencing Experiment	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5706412	standard	maintained	ready-to-use	recommended		All species	Minimum reporting guidelines		
https://fairsharing.org/94	10.25504/FAIRsharing.ca48xs	Minimal Information About a Phylogenetic Analysis	http://www.ovoio.org/wiki/MIAPA	standard		ready-to-use			All species	Minimum reporting guidelines		
https://fairsharing.org/599	10.25504/FAIRsharing.vy4hj	Minimal Information for QTLs and Association Studies	http://miqas.sourceforge.net/	standard		ready-to-use			All species	Minimum reporting guidelines		sourceforge(USA)
https://fairsharing.org/375	10.25504/FAIRsharing.wgv0r2	Minimal Information for QTLs and Association Studies Tabular	http://miqas.sourceforge.net/specification/MIQAS_TAB/MIQAS_TAB_specification.html	standard		ready-to-use			All species	Minimum reporting guidelines		sourceforge(USA)

FAIRsharing URL	FAIRsharing DOI	Record Name	Record homepage URL	Resource Type	Maintenance	Ready-to-use	FAIRorg recommended	plant accepted	species	Applied to	Type	ELIXIR recommended	provider
https://fairsharing.org/881	10.25504/FAIRsharing.ckg5a2	Minimal Metagenome Sequence Analysis Standard	http://mibbi.sf.net/projects/MINIMISS.shtml	standard						All species	Minimum reporting guidelines		
https://fairsharing.org/250	10.25504/FAIRsharing.9mfexc	Minimum Information About a Genotyping Experiment	http://migen.sourceforge.net/	standard		ready-to-use				All species	Minimum reporting guidelines		sourceforge(USA)
https://fairsharing.org/96	10.25504/FAIRsharing.32b10v	Minimum Information About a Microarray Experiment	http://www.fged.org/projects/miame/	standard		ready-to-use	recommended			All species	Minimum reporting guidelines		
https://fairsharing.org/36	10.25504/FAIRsharing.3gxr9b	Simple Omnibus Format in Text	http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/info/soft2.html	standard	maintained	ready-to-use				All species	Model/formats or syntax:Format		NCBI (USA)
https://fairsharing.org/1980	10.25504/FAIRsharing.sgf4n	MapViewer	http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/mapview/	database						All species	Knowledgebase		NCBI (USA)
https://fairsharing.org/1971	10.25504/FAIRsharing.64b6fp	NCBI Probe Database	http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/probe	database			recommended			All species	Knowledgebase		NCBI (USA)
https://fairsharing.org/1991	10.25504/FAIRsharing.4jg0qw	Reference Sequence Database	http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/RefSeq/	database		ready-to-use				All species	Knowledgebase		NCBI (USA)
https://fairsharing.org/1978	10.25504/FAIRsharing.g7t2hv	Sequence Read Archive	http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/sra	database		ready-to-use	recommended			All species	Data repository		NCBI (USA)
https://fairsharing.org/1974	10.25504/FAIRsharing.6brxe	Genetic Codes	http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Taxonomy/Utils/wprintrgc.cgi	database		ready-to-use				All species	Knowledgebase		NCBI (USA)
https://fairsharing.org/2164	10.25504/FAIRsharing.abwvhp	NCBI Trace Archive	http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Traces/home/	database		ready-to-use	recommended			All species	Data repository		NCBI (USA)
https://fairsharing.org/877	10.25504/FAIRsharing.nn7bf2	Standard Flowgram Format	http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Traces/trace.cgi?cmd=show&f=formats&m=doc&s=format#sf	standard		ready-to-use				All species	Model/formats or syntax:Format		NCBI (USA)
https://fairsharing.org/1993	10.25504/FAIRsharing.ge1c3p	UniGene gene-oriented nucleotide sequence clusters	http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/unigene	database						All species	Knowledgebase		NCBI (USA)
https://fairsharing.org/1994	10.25504/FAIRsharing.81dw2c	NCBI UniSTS	http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/unists	database						All species	Knowledgebase		NCBI (USA)
https://fairsharing.org/1995	10.25504/FAIRsharing.p4dt2	UniVec	http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/VecScreen/UniVec.html	database		ready-to-use				All species	Knowledgebase		NCBI (USA)
https://fairsharing.org/664	10.25504/FAIRsharing.mq1mdc	A Gold Path format	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/assembly/agg/AGP_Specification/	standard		ready-to-use				All species	Model/formats or syntax:Format		NCBI (USA)
https://fairsharing.org/2210	10.25504/FAIRsharing.aqhvly	NCBI BioProject	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/bioproject/	database		ready-to-use	recommended			All species	Data repository		NCBI (USA)
https://fairsharing.org/2211	10.25504/FAIRsharing.qr6pqq	NCBI BioSample	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/biosample	database	maintained	ready-to-use	recommended			All species	Data repository		NCBI (USA)
https://fairsharing.org/95	10.25504/FAIRsharing.pvdrzm	Minimum Information About a Microarray Experiment Involving Plants	http://miame-plant.sourceforge.net/	standard		ready-to-use			All plant species		Minimum reporting guidelines		sourceforge(USA)
https://fairsharing.org/1215	10.25504/FAIRsharing.mad142	Minimum Information about a Nutrigenomics experiment	http://mibbi.sourceforge.net/projects/MIAME-Nutr.shtml	standard						All species	Minimum reporting guidelines		sourceforge(USA)
https://fairsharing.org/180	10.25504/FAIRsharing.my19zk	Minimum Information About a RNAi Experiment	http://miare.sourceforge.net	standard		ready-to-use				All species	Minimum reporting guidelines		sourceforge(USA)
https://fairsharing.org/1258	10.25504/FAIRsharing.zrmjr7	Minimum Information about an array-based toxicogenomics experiment	http://mibbi.sourceforge.net/projects/MIAME-Tox.shtml	standard						All species	Minimum reporting guidelines		sourceforge(USA)
https://fairsharing.org/560	10.25504/FAIRsharing.x6dcc7	Minimum Information about an ENVIRONMENTAL transcriptomic experiment	http://necb.nox.ac.uk/miame/miame_env.html	standard						All species	Minimum reporting guidelines		
https://fairsharing.org/106	10.25504/FAIRsharing.t8g7yc	Minimum Information About an RNAi Experiment Tabular	http://miare.sourceforge.net/HomePage	standard		ready-to-use				All species	Minimum reporting guidelines		sourceforge(USA)
https://fairsharing.org/262	10.25504/FAIRsharing.9aa0zp	Minimum Information about any (x) Sequence	https://www.genec.org/pages/standards-intro.html	standard	maintained	ready-to-use	recommended			All species	Minimum reporting guidelines		
https://fairsharing.org/3922	10.25504/FAIRsharing.c2e4ab	Minimum Information about Tissue Imaging	https://www.miti-consortium.org/	standard		ready-to-use				All species	Minimum reporting guidelines		
https://fairsharing.org/865	10.25504/FAIRsharing.mx24jy	Minimum Information for Publication of Quantitative Real-Time PCR Experiments	https://rdml.org/miqe.html	standard		ready-to-use	recommended			All species	Minimum reporting guidelines		
https://fairsharing.org/45	10.25504/FAIRsharing.jw7rq3	Minimum Information for Reporting Next Generation Sequencing Genotyping	http://miring.immunogenomics.org	standard	maintained	ready-to-use				All species	Minimum reporting guidelines		
https://fairsharing.org/4740	10.25504/FAIRsharing.9a2f48	MIRAGE reporting guidelines for lectin microarray analysis	https://www.beilstein-institut.de/en/projects/mirage/guidelines/#lectin_microarrays	standard	maintained	ready-to-use				All species	Minimum reporting guidelines		
https://fairsharing.org/2100	10.25504/FAIRsharing.hmgt8	miRBase	http://www.mirbase.org/	database		ready-to-use	recommended			All species	Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/1345	N/A	mirGFF3	https://github.com/miRTop/mirGFF3	standard	maintained					All species	Model/formats or syntax:Format		github
https://fairsharing.org/1667	10.25504/FAIRsharing.5pfx4r	miRNEST	http://mirnest.amu.edu.pl	database						All species	Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/3195	10.25504/FAIRsharing.Ql6K87	ModelSEED Biochemistry Database	https://models.eed.org/biochem	database	maintained	ready-to-use			All plant species		Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/1964	10.25504/FAIRsharing.w2eeqr	NCBI BioSystems Database	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/biosystems/	database						All species	Knowledgebase		NCBI (USA)
https://fairsharing.org/2205	10.25504/FAIRsharing.djy2kc	MoonProt	http://www.moonlightingproteins.org	database	maintained	ready-to-use				All species	Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/299	10.25504/FAIRsharing.1dd23d	Multiple Alignment using Fast Fourier Transform	https://mafft.cbrc.jp/alignment/software/	standard		ready-to-use				All species	Model/formats or syntax:models/syntax		
https://fairsharing.org/2520	10.25504/FAIRsharing.bwswf3	Mutual Folding induced by Binding Database	http://mfib.enzim.ttk.mta.hu	database	maintained	ready-to-use				All species	Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/548	10.25504/FAIRsharing.95n1ns	National Agricultural Library Thesaurus	https://agclass.nal.usda.gov/	standard	maintained	ready-to-use				All species	Model/formats or syntax:models/syntax		
https://fairsharing.org/2658	10.25504/FAIRsharing.EivZlw	National Omics Data Encyclopedia	https://www.biosino.org/node	database	maintained	ready-to-use				All species	Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/490	10.25504/FAIRsharing.tej5wx	New Hampshire eXtended Format	http://www.phylosoft.org/NHX/nhx.pdf	standard		ready-to-use				All species	Model/formats or syntax:Format		
https://fairsharing.org/4	10.25504/FAIRsharing.ezznsh	Newick tree Format	http://evolution.genetics.washington.edu/phylip/newicktree.html	standard		ready-to-use				All species	Model/formats or syntax:Format		
https://fairsharing.org/297	10.25504/FAIRsharing.knr06	Nexus XML	https://github.com/nexml	standard	maintained	ready-to-use				All species	Model/formats or syntax:models/syntax		github
https://fairsharing.org/436	10.25504/FAIRsharing.rk682s	BioProject XML Schema	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/data_specs/schema/other/bioproject/	standard		ready-to-use				All species	Model/formats or syntax:models/syntax		NCBI (USA)
https://fairsharing.org/1547	10.25504/FAIRsharing.9kahy4	GenBank Nucleotide Sequence Database	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/genbank/	database		ready-to-use	recommended			All species	Data repository		NCBI (USA)
https://fairsharing.org/1969	10.25504/FAIRsharing.v9fyab	Expressed Sequence Tags database	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/genbank/dbest/	database		ready-to-use	recommended			All species	Data repository		NCBI (USA)
https://fairsharing.org/1983	10.25504/FAIRsharing.5h3maw	NCBI Gene	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/gene	database		ready-to-use	recommended			All species	Knowledgebase		NCBI (USA)

FAIRsharing URL	FAIRsharing DOI	Record Name	Record homepage URL	Resource Type	Maintenance	Ready-to-use	FAIRorg recommended	plant accepted	species	Applied to	Type	ELIXIR recommended	provider
https://fairsharing.org/3653	10.25504/FAIRsharing.7ad252	NCBI Genome	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/genome	database		ready-to-use				All species	Knowledgebase		NCBI (USA)
https://fairsharing.org/3337	10.25504/FAIRsharing.b05f99	NCBI Genome Data Viewer	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/genome/gdv/	database		ready-to-use				All species	Knowledgebase		NCBI (USA)
https://fairsharing.org/1975	10.25504/FAIRsharing.5hc8vt	Gene Expression Omnibus	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/	database	maintained	ready-to-use	recommended			All species	Data repository		NCBI (USA)
https://fairsharing.org/1977	10.25504/FAIRsharing.mz0c66	NCBI HomoloGene Database	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/homologene	database		ready-to-use	recommended			All species	Knowledgebase		NCBI (USA)
https://fairsharing.org/997	10.25504/FAIRsharing.kx4bgf	NGS ontology	https://github.com/mickaelsilva/NGSOnto	standard						All species	Semantic standards		github
https://fairsharing.org/833	10.25504/FAIRsharing.rg2vmt	GenBank Sequence Format	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Sitemap/samplerecord.html	standard		ready-to-use	recommended			All species	Model/formats syntax:Format	or	NCBI (USA)
https://fairsharing.org/1981	10.25504/FAIRsharing.zqzvyv	NCBI Structure	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/structure	database	maintained	ready-to-use				All species	Knowledgebase		NCBI (USA)
https://fairsharing.org/1967	10.25504/FAIRsharing.b9st5p	Conserved Domain Database	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Structure/cdd/cdd.shtml	database	maintained	ready-to-use				All species	Knowledgebase		NCBI (USA)
https://fairsharing.org/731	10.25504/FAIRsharing.xk98ez	NimbleGen Gene Description	https://dmac.cbs.dtu.dk/service/data-formats	standard						All species	Model/formats syntax:Format	or	
https://fairsharing.org/1620	10.25504/FAIRsharing.hmb1f4	NONCODE	http://www.noncode.org	database						All species	Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/1670	10.25504/FAIRsharing.hgrpah	NRG-CING	http://nmr.cmbi.ru.nl/NRG-CING	database						All species	Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/1621	10.25504/FAIRsharing.8ecbxx	NucleaRDB	http://www.receptors.org/nucleardb	database						All species	Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/2046	10.25504/FAIRsharing.bh0k78	Nucleic Acid Database	http://ndbserver.rutgers.edu/	database			recommended			All species	Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/1220	10.25504/FAIRsharing.fj07xj	NCBI Taxonomy	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/taxonomy	standard	maintained	ready-to-use	recommended			All species	Semantic standards		NCBI (USA)
https://fairsharing.org/395	10.25504/FAIRsharing.cfhbvn	Observ-Tab	http://wiki.gcc.rug.nl/wiki/ObservStart	standard	maintained					All species	Model/formats syntax:models/syntax	or	
https://fairsharing.org/2519	10.25504/FAIRsharing.re1278	Omics Discovery Index	http://www.omicsdi.org/home	database	maintained	ready-to-use				All species	Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/2704	10.25504/FAIRsharing.58HsV	OmicsDB	http://www.omicsdb.org/	database	maintained					All species	Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/282	10.25504/FAIRsharing.2hq97	OmicsDI XML format	https://github.com/OmicsDI/specifications/blob/master/docs/schema/OmicsDISchema.xsd	standard		ready-to-use				All species	Model/formats syntax:Format	or	github
https://fairsharing.org/1622	10.25504/FAIRsharing.hsy066	Online Gene Essentiality database	https://v3.ogee.info/#/home	database		ready-to-use				All species	Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/2568	10.25504/FAIRsharing.9hklvp	Online Resource for Community Annotation of Eukaryotes	http://bioinformatics.psb.ugent.be/orcae/	database	maintained	ready-to-use			All plant species		Knowledgebase		UGENT(Belgium)
https://fairsharing.org/1488	10.25504/FAIRsharing.284e1z	Ontology for Biomedical Investigations	http://obi-ontology.org/	standard	maintained	ready-to-use	recommended			All species	Semantic standards		
https://fairsharing.org/1250	N/A	Ontology for Experimental Phenotypic Objects	https://github.com/OpenSILEX/ontology-phs-oepo-field	standard						All species	Semantic standards		github
https://fairsharing.org/363	10.25504/FAIRsharing.zmx7nn	Ontology of Genes and Genomes	https://bitbucket.org/hgroup/ogg	standard	maintained	ready-to-use				All species	Semantic standards		bitbucket
https://fairsharing.org/3937	N/A	Open Digital Specimen	https://github.com/DISSCO/openDS	standard	maintained					All species	Model/formats syntax:models/syntax	or	github
https://fairsharing.org/1790	10.25504/FAIRsharing.8dak0r	Open Regulatory Annotation	http://www.oreganno.org/	database		ready-to-use				All species	Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/2393	10.25504/FAIRsharing.g3j5qj	Orthologous MAtRix	http://omabrowser.org/oma/about/	database		ready-to-use				All species	Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/77	10.25504/FAIRsharing.4877h0	Orthology Ontology	https://github.com/qfo/OrthologyOntology	standard		ready-to-use				All species	Semantic standards		github
https://fairsharing.org/3692	10.25504/FAIRsharing.45bf5b	Pacific Northwest National Laboratory DataHub: Scientific Data Repository	https://data.pnl.gov/	database	maintained	ready-to-use	recommended			All species	Data repository		
https://fairsharing.org/3306	10.25504/FAIRsharing.9289d4	Paired Omics Data Platform	https://pairedomicsdata.bioinformatics.nl/	database		ready-to-use				All species	Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/813	10.25504/FAIRsharing.RvBRMp	Pairs file format	https://github.com/4dn-dcic/pairix/blob/master/pairs_format_specification.md	standard	maintained	ready-to-use				All species	Model/formats syntax:Format	or	github
https://fairsharing.org/2987	10.25504/FAIRsharing.oalCAI	PathosSystems Resource Integration Center Repository	https://www.patricrc.org/	database	maintained	ready-to-use				All species	Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/2032	10.25504/FAIRsharing.33yggg	PAZAR	http://www.pazar.info/	database		ready-to-use				All species	Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/1014	10.25504/FAIRsharing.zsnv69	Multiple alignment	http://bioportal.bioontology.org/ontologies/1026	standard						All species	Semantic standards		NCBO(USA)
https://fairsharing.org/3301	10.25504/FAIRsharing.d02054	PDB-REDO	https://pdb-redo.eu	database	maintained	ready-to-use				All species	Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/1839	10.25504/FAIRsharing.k4sp7m	PDB-REPRDB	http://mbs.cbr.jp/pdbreprdb/cgi/reprdb_menu.pl	database						All species	Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/1925	10.25504/FAIRsharing.rxe7r2	PDZBase	http://abc.med.cornell.edu/pdzbase	database						All species	Data repository		Cornell University
https://fairsharing.org/2648	N/A	PDZscape	http://www.actrec.gov.in:8080/pdzscape/	database						All species	Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/2613	10.25504/FAIRsharing.654822	PGDBJ Ortholog Database	http://pgdbj.jp/pages/index.html?dir=&page=od&ln=en	database		ready-to-use			All plant species		Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/398	10.25504/FAIRsharing.kfs4pj	Pseudogene	http://bioportal.bioontology.org/ontologies/1135	standard		ready-to-use				All species	Semantic standards		NCBO(USA)
https://fairsharing.org/930	10.25504/FAIRsharing.23th83	GeoSpecies Ontology	http://bioportal.bioontology.org/ontologies/1247	standard		ready-to-use				All species	Semantic standards		NCBO(USA)
https://fairsharing.org/635	10.25504/FAIRsharing.ngn3a6	Genome Component Ontology	http://bioportal.bioontology.org/ontologies/GCO	standard		ready-to-use				All species	Semantic standards		NCBO(USA)
https://fairsharing.org/48	10.25504/FAIRsharing.efv7gw	HOMology	http://bioportal.bioontology.org/ontologies/HOM/?p=summary	standard		ready-to-use				All species	Semantic standards		NCBO(USA)
https://fairsharing.org/899	10.25504/FAIRsharing.b7evv9	MeGO	http://bioportal.bioontology.org/ontologies/MEGO/?p=summary	standard		ready-to-use				All species	Semantic standards		NCBO(USA)
https://fairsharing.org/535	10.25504/FAIRsharing.vppypa	Non-coding RNA Ontology	http://bioportal.bioontology.org/ontologies/NCRO	standard		ready-to-use				All species	Semantic standards		NCBO(USA)
https://fairsharing.org/550	10.25504/FAIRsharing.vdenk6	Phylogenetic Ontology	http://bioportal.bioontology.org/ontologies/PHYLON	standard		ready-to-use				All species	Semantic standards		NCBO(USA)
https://fairsharing.org/703	10.25504/FAIRsharing.fbn4sh	Reference Sequence Annotation	http://bioportal.bioontology.org/ontologies/RSA	standard		ready-to-use				All species	Semantic standards		NCBO(USA)
https://fairsharing.org/280	10.25504/FAIRsharing.zbf4z	Gene Regulation Ontology	http://purl.bioontology.org/ontology/GRC	standard						All species	Semantic standards		NCBO(USA)
https://fairsharing.org/903	10.25504/FAIRsharing.vh9jbb	Ontology for Genetic Interval	http://purl.bioontology.org/ontology/OGI	standard	maintained	ready-to-use				All species	Semantic standards		NCBO(USA)
https://fairsharing.org/88	10.25504/FAIRsharing.ngv2xx	Apollo-SV	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/apollo_sv.owl	standard	maintained	ready-to-use				All species	Semantic standards		NCBO(USA)

FAIRsharing URL	FAIRsharing DOI	Record Name	Record homepage URL	Resource Type	Maintenance	Ready-to-use	FAIRorg recommended	plant species accepted	Applied to species	Type	ELIXIR recommended	provider
https://fairsharing.org/1303	10.25504/FAIRsharing.bnx9cf	Molecular Connections Cell Line Ontology	https://bioportal.bioontology.org/ontologies/MCLL	standard					All species	Semantic standards		NCBO(USA)
https://fairsharing.org/263	10.25504/FAIRsharing.4qy0f0	Regulation of Transcription Ontology	https://bioportal.bioontology.org/ontologies/RETO	standard	maintained	ready-to-use			All species	Semantic standards		NCBO(USA)
https://fairsharing.org/2415	10.25504/FAIRsharing.tdtkc6	Genome Sequence Archive	https://bigd.big.ac.cn/gsa/	database	maintained	ready-to-use	recommended		All species	Data repository		NGDC (China)
https://fairsharing.org/2903	10.25504/FAIRsharing.91c279	Genome Variation Map	https://bigd.big.ac.cn/gvm/	database		ready-to-use		All plant species		Data repository		NGDC (China)
https://fairsharing.org/2905	10.25504/FAIRsharing.7qBaJ0	Genome Warehouse	https://bigd.big.ac.cn/gwh/	database	maintained	ready-to-use			All species	Data repository		NGDC (China)
https://fairsharing.org/2910	10.25504/FAIRsharing.86ec7a	Leaf Senescence Database	https://bigd.big.ac.cn/lsd/	database		ready-to-use		All plant species		Knowledgebase		NGDC (China)
https://fairsharing.org/2913	10.25504/FAIRsharing.4ef690	Plant Editosome Database	https://bigd.big.ac.cn/pep/	database		ready-to-use		All plant species		Knowledgebase		NGDC (China)
https://fairsharing.org/2763	10.25504/FAIRsharing.52da68	National Genomics Data Center Repository	https://ngdc.cnpc.ac.cn/	database		ready-to-use			All species	Data repository		NGDC (China)
https://fairsharing.org/2911	10.25504/FAIRsharing.d199bd	MethBank	https://ngdc.cnpc.ac.cn/methbank/	database		ready-to-use			All species	Data repository		NGDC (China)
https://fairsharing.org/4333	10.25504/FAIRsharing.45990b	Open Archive for Miscellaneous Data	https://ngdc.cnpc.ac.cn/omix/	database	maintained	ready-to-use			All species	Knowledgebase		NGDC (China)
https://fairsharing.org/1417	10.25504/FAIRsharing.6xq0ee	Gene Ontology	http://www.geneontology.org	standard	maintained	ready-to-use	recommended		All species	Semantic standards		NHGRI(USA)
https://fairsharing.org/554	10.25504/FAIRsharing.7y955w	Gene Ontology Extension	http://www.geneontology.org	standard		ready-to-use			All species	Semantic standards		NHGRI(USA)
https://fairsharing.org/1072	10.25504/FAIRsharing.9gx9at	Gene Ontology Annotation File Format 1.0	https://github.com/geneontology/geneontology.github.io/blob/e6e554c2cf75312784ecdbca44f858633990e99/docs/goc-annotation-file-gaf-format-1.0.md	standard	maintained				All species	Model/formats syntax:Format	or	NHGRI(USA)
https://fairsharing.org/2048	10.25504/FAIRsharing.xshwbf	Sanger Pfam Mirror	http://pfam.sanger.ac.uk/	database	maintained				All species	Knowledgebase		Sanger institute (UK)
https://fairsharing.org/953	10.25504/FAIRsharing.qaaJ0q	Gene Feature File version 1	http://www.sanger.ac.uk/resources/software/gff/spec.html	standard					All species	Model/formats syntax:Format	or	Sanger institute (UK)
https://fairsharing.org/427	10.25504/FAIRsharing.820ef3	GenePix Results Format	https://support.moleculardevices.com/s/article/GenePix-File-Formats#gr	standard		ready-to-use			All species	Model/formats syntax:Format	or	SIB(Swiss)
https://fairsharing.org/311	10.25504/FAIRsharing.rbpqg	PGxO	https://pgxo.loria.fr	standard		ready-to-use			All species	Semantic standards		
https://fairsharing.org/1273	10.25504/FAIRsharing.9xsgcr	Phenotype eXchange Format	https://github.com/phenopackets/phenopacket-format	standard		ready-to-use	recommended		All species	Model/formats syntax:Format	or	github
https://fairsharing.org/1760	10.25504/FAIRsharing.73cdk	PHI-base	http://www.phi-base.org/	database	maintained	ready-to-use		All plant species		Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/3297	10.25504/FAIRsharing.625fde	Phylogenies	http://www.phylogenies.org/	database		ready-to-use		All plant species		Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/1838	10.25504/FAIRsharing.7hxxc4	PhyloMeDB	http://phylomedb.org/	database	maintained	ready-to-use			All species	Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/2727	10.25504/FAIRsharing.w7Yuyx	PhytoMine	https://phytozone.jgi.doe.gov/phytozone/	database	maintained	ready-to-use		All plant species		Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/2734	10.25504/FAIRsharing.83406b	Phytozone	https://phytozone.jgi.doe.gov/pz/portal.html	database		ready-to-use		All plant species		Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/1288	10.25504/FAIRsharing.tghhc4	Pipeline Patterns Ontology	https://bitbucket.org/PlantExpAssay/ontology	standard		ready-to-use			All species	Semantic standards		bitbucket
https://fairsharing.org/2035	10.25504/FAIRsharing.vssch2	PIR SuperFamily	https://proteininformationresource.org/pirwww/dbinfo/pirsf.shtml	database		ready-to-use			All species	Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/1025	10.25504/FAIRsharing.nft558	Plant Diversity Ontology	http://gooa.las.ac.cn/external/index.jsp	standard				All plant species		Semantic standards		
https://fairsharing.org/2141	10.25504/FAIRsharing.7qexb2	Plant DNA C-values database	http://data.kew.org/cvalues/	database	maintained	ready-to-use		All plant species		Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/1314	10.25504/FAIRsharing.fgmzk8	Plant Experimental Assay Ontology	https://bitbucket.org/PlantExpAssay/ontology	standard		ready-to-use		All plant species		Semantic standards		bitbucket
https://fairsharing.org/1184	10.25504/FAIRsharing.6yNXVK	Plant Experimental Condition Ontology	https://github.com/Planteome/plant-experimental-conditions-ontology	standard	maintained	ready-to-use		All plant species		Semantic standards		github
https://fairsharing.org/2867	10.25504/FAIRsharing.8nLUyq	Plant Genome Integrative Explorer	https://plantgenie.org	database	maintained	ready-to-use		All plant species		Knowledgebase		Cornell University
https://fairsharing.org/1840	10.25504/FAIRsharing.391trx	Plant Genome Network	http://pgn.cornell.edu/	database				All plant species		Data repository		Cornell University
https://fairsharing.org/2195	10.25504/FAIRsharing.rf3m4g	Plant Genomics and Phenomics Research Data Repository	http://edal-pgp.ipk-gatersleben.de	database	maintained	ready-to-use		All plant species		Data repository		
https://fairsharing.org/1629	10.25504/FAIRsharing.rm1pxg	Plant Natural Antisense Transcripts Database	http://bis.zju.edu.cn/pnatdb/	database		ready-to-use		All plant species		Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/237	10.25504/FAIRsharing.3ngg40	Plant Ontology	http://plantontology.org/	standard	maintained	ready-to-use		All plant species		Semantic standards		
https://fairsharing.org/2133	10.25504/FAIRsharing.7k8zh0	Plant Promoter Database	http://ppdb.agr.gifu-u.ac.jp	database		ready-to-use		All plant species		Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/1721	10.25504/FAIRsharing.ysp7ke	Plant Resistance Gene Database	http://prgdb.org/prgdb4/	database		ready-to-use		All plant species		Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/1807	10.25504/FAIRsharing.ex3fqk	Plant Transcription Factor Database	http://plantfdb.cbi.pku.edu.cn	database	maintained	ready-to-use		All plant species		Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/2528	10.25504/FAIRsharing.k0Kcjw	Planteome	http://www.planteome.org	database	maintained	ready-to-use		All plant species		Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/1713	10.25504/FAIRsharing.fy2ebk	PlantRNA	http://plantrna.ibmp.cnrs.fr/	database		ready-to-use		All plant species		Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/2766	10.25504/FAIRsharing.w80ua0	PLAZA	https://bioinformatics.psb.ugent.be/plaza/	database	maintained	ready-to-use		All plant species		Knowledgebase	recommended	UGENT(Belgium)
https://fairsharing.org/3814	10.25504/FAIRsharing.23ac74	PlutoF	https://plutof.ut.ee/	database	maintained	ready-to-use			All species	Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/1671	10.25504/FAIRsharing.etqbej	Pocket Similarity Search using Multiple-Sketches	http://possum.cbrc.jp/PosSuM/	database	maintained	ready-to-use			All species	Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/1631	10.25504/FAIRsharing.tc6df8	Pocketome: an encyclopedia of small-molecule binding sites in 4D	http://pocketome.org	database					All species	Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/1632	10.25504/FAIRsharing.s9ztmp	Polbase	https://polbase.neb.com/	database		ready-to-use			All species	Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/1053	10.25504/FAIRsharing.vq28qp	Population and Community Ontology	https://github.com/PopulationAndCommunityOntology/pco	standard	maintained	ready-to-use			All species	Semantic standards		github
https://fairsharing.org/1684	10.25504/FAIRsharing.znvzhj	Predictive Networks	http://predictivenetworks.org/	database					All species	Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/2790	10.25504/FAIRsharing.22e3be	Princeton University MicroArray database	http://puma.princeton.edu	database		ready-to-use			All species	Data repository		
https://fairsharing.org/2099	10.25504/FAIRsharing.h8e843	PRINTS	http://www.bioinf.manchester.ac.uk/dbbrowser/PRINTS/PRINTS.html	database		ready-to-use	recommended		All species	Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/2232	10.25504/FAIRsharing.t6wjn7	probeBase	http://www.probebase.net	database	maintained	ready-to-use			All species	Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/1143	10.25504/FAIRsharing.v033mj	proBed	http://www.psidev.info/probed	standard	maintained				All species	Model/formats syntax:Format	or	
https://fairsharing.org/1532	10.25504/FAIRsharing.zve9cc	Proteasix Ontology	https://dx.doi.org/10.1186%2F13326-016-0078-9	standard					All species	Semantic standards		
https://fairsharing.org/1637	10.25504/FAIRsharing.wv5q9d	ProtoNet	http://www.protonet.cs.huji.ac.il/	database					All species	Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/1244	10.25504/FAIRsharing.dmhjcg	Quality Control Markup Language	http://www.psidev.info/groups/quality-control	standard	maintained		recommended		All species	Model/formats syntax:models/syntax	or	
https://fairsharing.org/2327	10.25504/FAIRsharing.txcn6k	RDF Portal	https://rdfportal.org	database	maintained	ready-to-use			All species	Knowledgebase		

FAIRsharing URL	FAIRsharing DOI	Record Name	Record homepage URL	Resource Type	Maintenance	Ready-to-use	FAIRorg recommended	plant accepted	species	Applied to	ELIXIR recommended	provider
https://fairsharing.org/1269	10.25504/FAIRsharing.a4wgws	Real-time PCR Data Markup Language	http://rdml.org/	standard	maintained	ready-to-use				All species	Model/formats or syntax:models/syntax	
https://fairsharing.org/2177	10.25504/FAIRsharing.pxnqyt	RepeatsDB	http://repeatsdb.bio.unipd.it/	database	maintained	ready-to-use				All species	Knowledgebase	
https://fairsharing.org/4548	10.25504/FAIRsharing.fa2cf3	Resource Identification Portal	https://scicrunch.org/resources	database		ready-to-use				All species	Knowledgebase	
https://fairsharing.org/2009	10.25504/FAIRsharing.9sb9qh	Restriction enzymes and methylases database	http://rebase.neb.com/rebase/rebase.html	database	maintained	ready-to-use				All species	Knowledgebase	
https://fairsharing.org/2396	10.25504/FAIRsharing.fex4c8	Rfam	http://rfam.xfam.org/	database	maintained	ready-to-use				All species	Knowledgebase	
https://fairsharing.org/2039	10.25504/FAIRsharing.tn11nn	RIKEN Bioresource Research Center	https://web.br.riken.jp/en/	database		ready-to-use	recommended		Arabidopsis	All species	Knowledgebase	
https://fairsharing.org/3200	10.25504/FAIRsharing.H3pwqc	RNA Atlas of Structure Probing	http://rasp.zhanglab.net	database	maintained	ready-to-use			Arabidopsis/rice	All species	Knowledgebase	
https://fairsharing.org/1640	10.25504/FAIRsharing.vobj4e	RNA Characterization of Secondary Structure Motifs	https://www.rnacssmos.com/index.php	database		ready-to-use				All species	Knowledgebase	
https://fairsharing.org/308	10.25504/FAIRsharing.e729c4	RNA Markup Language	http://www.lbit.iro.umontreal.ca/rnaml/	standard		ready-to-use				All species	Model/formats or syntax:models/syntax	
https://fairsharing.org/65	10.25504/FAIRsharing.kqt2h2	RNA Ontology	https://github.com/bgsu-ma/rnao	standard	maintained	ready-to-use				All species	Semantic standards	github
https://fairsharing.org/2891	10.25504/FAIRsharing.KcJL7	RNACentral	https://rnacentral.org/	database	maintained	ready-to-use				All species	Knowledgebase	
https://fairsharing.org/1739	10.25504/FAIRsharing.zzgvrv	RNAJunction	https://rnajunction.ncifcrf.gov/	database		ready-to-use				All species	Knowledgebase	
https://fairsharing.org/2853	10.25504/FAIRsharing.6mMhZp	rPredictor	https://rpredictor.elixir-czech.cz/	database	maintained	ready-to-use				All species	Knowledgebase	
https://fairsharing.org/1810	10.25504/FAIRsharing.x16th8	RTPrimerDB	http://medgen.ugent.be/rtprimerdb/	database						All species	Knowledgebase	UGENT (Belgium)
https://fairsharing.org/2231	10.25504/FAIRsharing.bb5rna	Sea scientific open data publication	https://www.seanoe.org/	database	maintained	ready-to-use	recommended			All species	Knowledgebase	
https://fairsharing.org/138	10.25504/FAIRsharing.k97zxh	Sequence Alignment Map	https://github.com/samtools/samtools	standard		ready-to-use				All species	Model/formats or syntax:Format	github
https://fairsharing.org/638	10.25504/FAIRsharing.6b7h9	Sequence Ontology	http://www.sequenceontology.org/	standard	maintained	ready-to-use				All species	Semantic standards	
https://fairsharing.org/22	10.25504/FAIRsharing.cnbjkn	Single Nucleotide Polymorphism Ontology	https://members.ioria.fr/ACoulet/files/snpontology1_6_description.html	standard	maintained	ready-to-use				All species	Semantic standards	
https://fairsharing.org/1673	10.25504/FAIRsharing.kq47fy	SpliceDisease	http://cmbi.bjmu.edu.cn/sdisease	database						All species	Knowledgebase	
https://fairsharing.org/2283	10.25504/FAIRsharing.ekj9zx	Standards for Reporting Enzymology Data Database	https://www.beilstein-strenda-db.org/strenda/	standard	maintained	ready-to-use	recommended			All species	Minimum reporting guidelines	
https://fairsharing.org/2057	10.25504/FAIRsharing.x93ckv	Stanford Microarray Database	http://smd.princeton.edu/	database						All species	Data repository	
https://fairsharing.org/1877	10.25504/FAIRsharing.q7bkqr	STING	http://sms.cbi.cnptia.embrapa.br/SMS/index_s.html	database						All species	Knowledgebase	
https://fairsharing.org/139	10.25504/FAIRsharing.dppg6t	Stockholm Multiple Alignment Format	http://sonhammer.sbc.us.se/Stockholm.html	standard		ready-to-use				All species	Model/formats or syntax:Format	
https://fairsharing.org/4524	N/A	Stress Knowledge Map	https://skm.nib.si/	database	maintained			All plant species			Knowledgebase	
https://fairsharing.org/1875	10.25504/FAIRsharing.9b7wvk	STRING	https://string-db.org/	database		ready-to-use				All species	Knowledgebase	
https://fairsharing.org/2239	10.25504/FAIRsharing.bya6z	Super-Enhancer Archive	http://sea.edbc.org/	database	maintained	ready-to-use				All species	Knowledgebase	
https://fairsharing.org/116	10.25504/FAIRsharing.mwmbpq	Browser Extensible Data Format	http://genome.ucsc.edu/FAQ/FAQformat.html#format1	standard	maintained	ready-to-use				All species	Model/formats or syntax:Format	UCSC(USA)
https://fairsharing.org/1952	10.25504/FAIRsharing.frryxv	SUPERFAMILY	http://supfam.org	database	maintained	ready-to-use				All species	Knowledgebase	
https://fairsharing.org/132	10.25504/FAIRsharing.gnga3t	Personal Genome SNP Format	http://genome.ucsc.edu/FAQ/FAQformat.html#format10	standard		ready-to-use				All species	Model/formats or syntax:Format	UCSC(USA)
https://fairsharing.org/32	10.25504/FAIRsharing.20df5w	ENCODE peak information Format	http://genome.ucsc.edu/FAQ/FAQformat.html#format13	standard		ready-to-use				All species	Model/formats or syntax:Format	UCSC(USA)
https://fairsharing.org/901	10.25504/FAIRsharing.9sdcx8	Multiple Alignment Format	http://genome.ucsc.edu/FAQ/FAQformat.html#format5	standard		ready-to-use				All species	Model/formats or syntax:Format	UCSC(USA)
https://fairsharing.org/98	10.25504/FAIRsharing.cjmt3	Binary sequence information Format	http://genome.ucsc.edu/FAQ/FAQformat.html#format7	standard	maintained	ready-to-use				All species	Model/formats or syntax:Format	UCSC(USA)
https://fairsharing.org/131	10.25504/FAIRsharing.wkh9j2	nucleotide information binary Format	http://genome.ucsc.edu/FAQ/FAQformat.html#format8	standard		ready-to-use				All species	Model/formats or syntax:Format	UCSC(USA)
https://fairsharing.org/148	10.25504/FAIRsharing.fe4pja	Gene Prediction File Format	http://genome.ucsc.edu/FAQ/FAQformat.html#format9	standard		ready-to-use				All species	Model/formats or syntax:Format	UCSC(USA)
https://fairsharing.org/1691	10.25504/FAIRsharing.se4zhk	SuperTarget	http://bioinformatics.charite.de/supertarget	database						All species	Knowledgebase	
https://fairsharing.org/1087	10.25504/FAIRsharing.cw44py	Synthetic Biology Open Language	https://sbolstandard.org/	standard	maintained	ready-to-use				All species	Model/formats or syntax:models/syntax	
https://fairsharing.org/3	10.25504/FAIRsharing.dg76vs	Synthetic Biology Open Language Visual	https://sbolstandard.org/visual/about/	standard	maintained	ready-to-use				All species	Model/formats or syntax:models/syntax	
https://fairsharing.org/1786	10.25504/FAIRsharing.9fz3g3	Tandem Repeats Database	http://tandem.bu.edu/cgi-bin/trdb/trdb.exe	database		ready-to-use				All species	Knowledgebase	
https://fairsharing.org/1773	10.25504/FAIRsharing.en9nnp	The Barcode of Life Data Systems	https://www.boldsystems.org/	database		ready-to-use				All species	Knowledgebase	
https://fairsharing.org/2381	10.25504/FAIRsharing.jsxqrk	The Department of Energy Systems Biology Knowledgebase	https://www.kbase.us	database	maintained	ready-to-use	recommended		All plant species		Knowledgebase	
https://fairsharing.org/1889	10.25504/FAIRsharing.afftff2	The Gene Index Project	http://complibio.dfci.harvard.edu/tgi/	database						All species	Knowledgebase	
https://fairsharing.org/2533	10.25504/FAIRsharing.8nq9t6	The Network Data Exchange	https://www.ndexbio.org	database	maintained	ready-to-use	recommended			All species	Knowledgebase	
https://fairsharing.org/4907	N/A	The Nucleic Acid Knowledgebase	http://nakb.org/	database		ready-to-use				All species	Knowledgebase	
https://fairsharing.org/1643	10.25504/FAIRsharing.6648ht	The SEQanswers wiki	https://www.seqanswers.com/	database	maintained					All species	Knowledgebase	
https://fairsharing.org/2736	10.25504/FAIRsharing.a1de61	The Track Hub Registry	https://www.trackhubregistry.org/	database		ready-to-use				All species	Knowledgebase	
https://fairsharing.org/482	10.25504/FAIRsharing.3pxg2f	Axt Alignment Format	http://genome.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/help/axt.html	standard		ready-to-use				All species	Model/formats or syntax:Format	UCSC(USA)
https://fairsharing.org/78	10.25504/FAIRsharing.hza1ec	Binary Alignment Map Format	http://genome.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/help/bam.html	standard		ready-to-use				All species	Model/formats or syntax:Format	UCSC(USA)
https://fairsharing.org/525	10.25504/FAIRsharing.vttygv	BEDgraph	http://genome.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/help/bedgraph.html	standard		ready-to-use				All species	Model/formats or syntax:Format	UCSC(USA)
https://fairsharing.org/666	10.25504/FAIRsharing.wzp79x	Big Chain	http://genome.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/help/bigChain.html	standard	maintained	ready-to-use				All species	Model/formats or syntax:Format	UCSC(USA)

FAIRsharing URL	FAIRsharing DOI	Record Name	Record homepage URL	Resource Type	Maintenance	Ready-to-use	FAIRorg recommended	plant accepted	species	Applied to species	Type	ELIXIR recommended	provider
https://fairsharing.org/660	10.25504/FAIRsharing.6eg9a3	Big Gene Prediction	http://genome.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/help/bigGenePred.html	standard	maintained	ready-to-use				All species	Model/formats syntax:Format	or	UCSC(USA)
https://fairsharing.org/615	10.25504/FAIRsharing.78make	Big Multiple Alignment Format	http://genome.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/help/bigMaf.html	standard	maintained	ready-to-use				All species	Model/formats syntax:Format	or	UCSC(USA)
https://fairsharing.org/517	10.25504/FAIRsharing.c9fakh	Big Pattern Space Layout	http://genome.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/help/bigPsl.html	standard	maintained	ready-to-use				All species	Model/formats syntax:Format	or	UCSC(USA)
https://fairsharing.org/518	10.25504/FAIRsharing.x9k6a1	bigWig Track Format	http://genome.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/help/bigWig.html	standard		ready-to-use				All species	Model/formats syntax:Format	or	UCSC(USA)
https://fairsharing.org/110	10.25504/FAIRsharing.72e4we	Chain Format for pairwise alignment	http://genome.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/help/chain.html	standard		ready-to-use				All species	Model/formats syntax:Format	or	UCSC(USA)
https://fairsharing.org/128	10.25504/FAIRsharing.evxcfb	net alignment annotation Format	http://genome.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/help/net.html	standard		ready-to-use				All species	Model/formats syntax:Format	or	UCSC(USA)
https://fairsharing.org/864	10.25504/FAIRsharing.2nrf9f	Wiggle Track Format	http://genome.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/help/wiggle.html	standard		ready-to-use				All species	Model/formats syntax:Format	or	UCSC(USA)
https://fairsharing.org/405	10.25504/FAIRsharing.9y3gv0	Enzyme Structure Function Ontology	http://sflid.rvbi.ucsf.edu/	standard		ready-to-use				All species	Semantic standards		UCSF(USA)
https://fairsharing.org/2641	N/A	Structure Function Linkage Database Archive	http://sflid.rvbi.ucsf.edu/	database						All species	Knowledgebase		UCSF(USA)
https://fairsharing.org/2873	10.25504/FAIRsharing.83jovl	T-psi-C	http://tpsic.igcz.poznan.pl/	database	maintained	ready-to-use				All species	Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/1360	10.25504/FAIRsharing.ylYlV	Transcription Factor Class Schema	http://www.edgar-wingender.de/TFClass_schema.html	standard	maintained	ready-to-use				All species	Semantic standards		
https://fairsharing.org/3655	10.25504/FAIRsharing.de533c	Translational Data Catalog	https://datacatalog.elixir-luxembourg.org/	database	maintained	ready-to-use				All species	Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/1903	10.25504/FAIRsharing.1nwy41	Transmembrane Helices in Genome Sequences	http://pranag.physics.iisc.ernet.in/thgs/	database						All species	Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/2022	10.25504/FAIRsharing.p3bzqb	Transporter Classification Database	https://tcdb.org/	database	maintained	ready-to-use				All species	Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/2072	10.25504/FAIRsharing.zcn4w4	TreeBase	https://www.treebase.org	database		ready-to-use	recommended			All species	Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/2338	10.25504/FAIRsharing.x6nr7d	Tropical Data Hub	https://tropicaldatahub.org/	database						All species	Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/935	10.25504/FAIRsharing.wf28wm	UniProt Taxonomy	http://www.uniprot.org/taxonomy/	standard	maintained	ready-to-use				All species	Semantic standards		
https://fairsharing.org/2264	10.25504/FAIRsharing.j97pjin	Validated Antibody Database	http://www.labome.com	database	maintained	ready-to-use				All species	Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/125	10.25504/FAIRsharing.cfz20h	Variant Call Format	https://www.ga4gh.org/product/genetic-variation-formats-vcf/	standard		ready-to-use				All species	Model/formats syntax:Format	or	
https://fairsharing.org/546	10.25504/FAIRsharing.65xkbs	Variation Ontology	http://variationontology.org	standard	maintained	ready-to-use				All species	Semantic standards		
https://fairsharing.org/2819	10.25504/FAIRsharing.EGn1ut	WALTZ-DB 2.0	http://waltzdb.switchlab.org	database	maintained	ready-to-use				All species	Knowledgebase		
https://fairsharing.org/710	10.25504/FAIRsharing.j4encb	XEML Environment Ontology	http://xeo.codeplex.com/	standard						All species	Semantic standards		
https://fairsharing.org/17	10.25504/FAIRsharing.3mpr8	XML for evolutionary biology and comparative genomics.	http://www.phyloxml.org/	standard		ready-to-use				All species	Model/formats syntax:models/syntax	or	

Annex 2. Examples of file format standards

FASTA

>Soly05g012020.2.1 Ripening Inhibitor (RIN) MADS-box transcription factor MADS-MC (AHRD V1 *-** Q8S4L5_SOLLC); contains Interpro domain(s) IPR002487 Transcription factor, K-box
TCATGATATATAGTAAACAAAAAGTCTTTATTCTCTTTCTTCTTGACTAGGGAACCATTAGATTTTAAAGACATTAA
ATCTATTACCCTTACCCTAAGAATAAGAAGATGTAAAGTAGAAGAGAAAACAACCAACCATATATACATATATATA
ATTACATTATATTGTCTTATAACATATAGTCTTTAAGGAAAAACAATTTAGAAAAAATAATATTATTTTACATTTT
TTTCTTCATACAATATGGGTAGAGGGAAAGTAGAATTGAAGAGAATTGAGAACAAAATAATAGACAAGTTACCTTTGCA

FASTQ

```
Instrument ID lane tile X Y barcode read# Header lines sequence quality scores
@HWI-EAS209_0006_FC706VJ:5:58:5894:21141#ATCAG/1
TTAATTGGTAAATAAACTCCTAATAGCTTAGATNTTACCTTNNNNNNNNNTAGTTCTTGAGATTTGTTGGGGGAGACATTTTGTGATTGCCCTTGAT
+HWI-EAS209_0006_FC706VJ:5:58:5894:21141#ATCAG/1
efcffffcfeefffcfffffdff`feed]`_Ba^_[YBBBBBBBBBRTT\]][] dddd`ddd^dddadd^BBBBBBBBBBBBBBBBBBBBBBBB
```

EMBL Format

ID X64011; SV 1; linear; genomic DNA; STD; PRO; 756 BP.
XX
AC X64011; S78972;
XX
SV X64011.1
XX
DT 28-APR-1992 (Rel. 31, Created)
DT 30-JUN-1993 (Rel. 36, Last updated, Version 6)
XX
DE *Listeria ivanovii* sod gene for superoxide dismutase
XX
KW sod gene; superoxide dismutase.
XX
OS *Listeria ivanovii*
OC Bacteria; Firmicutes; Bacillus/Clostridium group;
OC Bacillus/Staphylococcus group; *Listeria*.
XX
RN [1]
RX MEDLINE; 92140371.
RA Haas A., Goebel W.;
RT "Cloning of a superoxide dismutase gene from *Listeria ivanovii* by
RT functional complementation in *Escherichia coli* and characterization of the
RT gene product.";
RL Mol. Gen. Genet. 231:313-322(1992).
XX
RN [2]
RP 1-756
RA Kreft J.;
RT ;
RL Submitted (21-APR-1992) to the EMBL/GenBank/DDBJ databases.
RL J. Kreft, Institut f. Mikrobiologie, Universitaet Wuerzburg, Biozentrum Am
RL Hubland, 8700 Wuerzburg, FRG
XX
FH Key Location/Qualifiers
FH
FT source 1..756
FT /db_xref="taxon:1638"
FT /organism="Listeria ivanovii"
FT /strain="ATCC 19119"

```

FT          /mol_type="genomic DNA"
FT regulatory 95..100
FT          /gene="sod"
FT          /regulatory_class="ribosome_binding_site"
FT regulatory 723..746
FT          /gene="sod"
FT          /regulatory_class="terminator"
FT CDS       109..717
FT          /transl_table=11
FT          /gene="sod"
FT          /EC_number="1.15.1.1"
FT          /db_xref="GOA:P28763"
FT          /db_xref="HSSP:P00448"
FT          /db_xref="InterPro:IPR001189"
FT          /db_xref="UniProtKB/Swiss-Prot:P28763"
FT          /product="superoxide dismutase"
FT          /protein_id="CAA45406.1"
FT          /translation="MTYELPKLPYTYDALEPNFDKETMEIHYTEKHHNIYVTKLNEAVSG
FT          HAELASKPGEELVANLDSVPEEIRGAVRNHGGGHHANHTLFWSSLSPNGGGGAPTGNLKAA
FT          IESEFGTDFEFKEKFNAAAAARFGSGWAWLVVNNNGKLEIVSTANQDSPLSEGKTPVLGL
FT          DVWEHAYYLKFNRRPEYIDTFWNVINWDERNKRFDAAK"
XX
SQ Sequence 756 BP; 247 A; 136 C; 151 G; 222 T; 0 other;
   cgttatttaa ggtgttacat agttctatgg aaatagggtc tataccttc gcctacaat 60
   gtaattcct .....                120
//

```

GenBank Format

```

LOCUS LISOD 756 bp DNA linear BCT 30-JUN-1993
DEFINITION Listeria ivanovii sod gene for superoxide dismutase.
ACCESSION X64011 S78972
VERSION X64011.1 GI:44010
KEYWORDS sod gene; superoxide dismutase.
SOURCE Listeria ivanovii
  ORGANISM Listeria ivanovii
    Bacteria; Firmicutes; Bacillales; Listeriaceae; Listeria.
REFERENCE 1 (bases 1 to 756)
  AUTHORS Haas,A. and Goebel,W.
  TITLE Cloning of a superoxide dismutase gene from Listeria ivanovii by
  functional complementation in Escherichia coli and characterization
  of the gene product
  JOURNAL Mol. Gen. Genet. 231 (2), 313-322 (1992)
  MEDLINE 92140371
REFERENCE 2 (bases 1 to 756)
  AUTHORS Kreft,J.
  TITLE Direct Submission
  JOURNAL Submitted (21-APR-1992) J. Kreft, Institut f. Mikrobiologie,
  Universitaet Wuerzburg, Biozentrum Am Hubland, 8700 Wuerzburg, FRG
FEATURES Location/Qualifiers
  source 1..756
    /organism="Listeria ivanovii"
    /strain="ATCC 19119"
    /db_xref="taxon:1638"
    /mol_type="genomic DNA"
  regulatory 95..100
    /gene="sod"
    /regulatory_class="ribosome_binding_site"

```

```

gene      95..746
          /gene="sod"
CDS       109..717
          /gene="sod"
          /EC_number="1.15.1.1"
          /codon_start=1
          /transl_table=11
          /product="superoxide dismutase"
          /db_xref="GI:44011"
          /db_xref="GOA:P28763"
          /db_xref="InterPro:IPR001189"
          /db_xref="UniProtKB/Swiss-Prot:P28763"
          /protein_id="CAA45406.1"
          /translation="MTYELPKLPYTYDALEPNFDKETMEIHYTKHHNIYVTKLNEAVS
          GHAEELASKPGEELVANLDSVPPEIRGAVRNHGGGGHANHTLFWSSLSPNGGGAPTGNLK
          AAIESEFGTFDEFKEKFNAAAAARFGSGWAWLVVNNNGKLEIVSTANQDSPLSEGKTPV
          LGLDVWEHAYYLKFQRRRPEYIDTFWNVINWDERNKRFDAAK"
regulatory 723..746
          /gene="sod"
          /regulatory_class="terminator"
ORIGIN
1 cggtatttaa ggtgttacat agttctatgg aaatagggtc tataccttc gcctacaat
61 gtaatttctt .....
//

```

DDBJ flat file format

```

LOCUS   LISOD           756 bp  DNA   linear  BCT 30-JUN-1993
DEFINITION  Listeria ivanovii sod gene for superoxide dismutase.
ACCESSION  X64011 S78972
VERSION    X64011.1 GI:44010
KEYWORDS   sod gene; superoxide dismutase.
SOURCE     Listeria ivanovii
            ORGANISM  Listeria ivanovii
                Bacteria; Firmicutes; Bacillales; Listeriaceae; Listeria.
REFERENCE  1 (bases 1 to 756)
            AUTHORS   Haas,A. and Goebel,W.
            TITLE     Cloning of a superoxide dismutase gene from Listeria ivanovii by
                functional complementation in Escherichia coli and characterization
                of the gene product
            JOURNAL   Mol. Gen. Genet. 231 (2), 313-322 (1992)
            MEDLINE   92140371
REFERENCE  2 (bases 1 to 756)
            AUTHORS   KrefT,J.
            TITLE     Direct Submission
            JOURNAL   Submitted (21-APR-1992) J. KrefT, Institut f. Mikrobiologie,
                Universitaet Wuerzburg, Biozentrum Am Hubland, 8700 Wuerzburg, FRG
FEATURES   Location/Qualifiers
            source     1..756
                /organism="Listeria ivanovii"
                /strain="ATCC 19119"
                /db_xref="taxon:1638"
                /mol_type="genomic DNA"
            regulatory 95..100
                /gene="sod"
                /regulatory_class="ribosome_binding_site"
            gene       95..746
                /gene="sod"
            CDS        109..717

```

```

/gene="sod"
/EC_number="1.15.1.1"
/codon_start=1
/transl_table=11
/product="superoxide dismutase"
/db_xref="GOA:P28763"
/db_xref="HSSP:P00448"
/db_xref="InterPro:IPR001189"
/db_xref="UniProtKB/Swiss-Prot:P28763"
/protein_id="CAA45406.1"
/translation="MTYELPKLPYTYDALEPNFDKETMEIHYTEKHHNIYVTKLNEAVS
GHAELASKPGEELVANLDSVPEEIRGAVRNHGGGHANHTLFWSSLSPPNGGGAPTGNLK
AAIESEFGTFDEFKEKFNAAAAARFGSGWAWLVVNNNGKLEIVSTANQDSPLSEGKTPV
LGLDVWEHAYYLKFQRRRPEYIDTFWVNVINWDERNKRFDAAK"
regulatory 723..746
  /gene="sod"
  /regulatory_class="terminator"
BASE COUNT 247 a 136 c 151 g 222 t
ORIGIN
  1 cgttatttaa ggtgttacat agttctatgg aatagggtc tataccttc gcctacaat
  61 gtaattctt .....
//

```

SAM (from <https://www.samformat.info/sam-format-flag>)

Header section											
@HD VN:1.5 SO:coordinate											
@SQ SN:ref LN:45											
r001	99	ref	7	30	8M2I4M1D3M	=	37	39	TTAGATAAAGGATACTG	*	Alignment section
r002	0	ref	9	30	3S6M1P1I4M	*	0	0	AAAAGATAAGGATA	*	
r003	0	ref	9	30	5S6M	*	0	0	GCCTAAGCTAA	* SA:Z:ref,29,-,6H5M,17,0;	
r004	0	ref	16	30	6M14N5M	*	0	0	ATAGCTTCAGC	*	
r003	2064	ref	29	17	6H5M	*	0	0	TAGGC	* SA:Z:ref,9,+,5S6M,30,1;	
r001	147	ref	37	30	9M	=	7	-39	CAGCGGCAT	* NM:i:1	

Optional fields in the format of TAG:TYPE:VALUE
QUAL: read quality; * meaning such information is not available
SEQ: read sequence
TLEN: the number of bases covered by the reads from the same fragment. Plus/minus means the current read is the leftmost/rightmost read. E.g. compare first and last lines.
PNEXT: Position of the primary alignment of the NEXT read in the template. Set as 0 when the information is unavailable. It corresponds to POS column.
RNEXT: reference sequence name of the primary alignment of the NEXT read. For paired-end sequencing, NEXT read is the paired read, corresponding to the RNAME column.
CIGAR: summary of alignment, e.g. insertion, deletion
MAPQ: mapping quality
POS: 1-based position
RNAME: reference sequence name, e.g. chromosome/transcript id
FLAG: indicates alignment information about the read, e.g. paired, aligned, etc.
QNAME: query template name, aka. read ID

VCF format (from https://davetang.github.io/learning_vcf_file/)

Example

```

##fileformat=VCFv4.0
##fileDate=20100707
##source=VCFtools
##reference=NCBI36
##INFO=<ID=AA,Number=1,Type=String,Description="Ancestral Allele">
##INFO=<ID=H2,Number=0,Type=Flag,Description="HapMap2 membership">
##FORMAT=<ID=GT,Number=1,Type=String,Description="Genotype">
##FORMAT=<ID=GQ,Number=1,Type=Integer,Description="Genotype Quality (phred score)">
##FORMAT=<ID=GL,Number=3,Type=Float,Description="Likelihoods for RR,RA,AA genotypes (R=ref,A=alt)">
##FORMAT=<ID=DP,Number=1,Type=Integer,Description="Read Depth">
##ALT=<ID=DEL,Description="Deletion">
##INFO=<ID=SVTYPE,Number=1,Type=String,Description="Type of structural variant">
##INFO=<ID=END,Number=1,Type=Integer,Description="End position of the variant">
#CHROM POS ID REF ALT QUAL FILTER INFO FORMAT SAMPLE1 SAMPLE2
1 1 . ACG A,AT . PASS . GT:DP 1/2:13 0/0:29
1 2 rs1 C T,CT . PASS H2;AA=T GT:GQ 0/1:100 2/2:70
1 5 . A G . PASS . GT:GQ 1/0:77 1/1:95
1 100 T <DEL> . PASS SVTYPE=DEL;END=300 GT:GQ:DP 1/1:12:3 0/0:20
  
```

VCF header

- Mandatory header lines** (lines starting with ##)
- Optional header lines** (meta-data about the annotations in the VCF body)

Body

#CHROM	POS	ID	REF	ALT	QUAL	FILTER	INFO	FORMAT	SAMPLE1	SAMPLE2
1	1	.	ACG	A,AT	.	PASS	.	GT:DP	1/2:13	0/0:29
1	2	rs1	C	T,CT	.	PASS	H2;AA=T	GT:GQ	0/1:100	2/2:70
1	5	.	A	G	.	PASS	.	GT:GQ	1/0:77	1/1:95
1	100	.	T		.	PASS	SVTYPE=DEL;END=300	GT:GQ:DP	1/1:12:3	0/0:20

Annotations:

- Reference alleles (GT=0)**: A, C, A
- Alternate alleles (GT>0 is an index to the ALT column)**: AT, T, CT, G,
- Phased data** (G and C above are on the same chromosome): C, T, G
- Other event**: SVTYPE=DEL;END=300
- Structural Variants**: Deletion (T), Insertion (A, AT), Large SV (SVTYPE=DEL;END=300)
- SNP**: rs1

BED format

Track line

```

track name="ItemRGBDemo" description="Item RGB demonstration" itemRgb="On"
chr7 127471196 127472363 Pos1 0 + 127471196 127472363 255,0,0
chr7 127472363 127473530 Pos2 0 + 127472363 127473530 255,0,0
chr7 127473530 127474697 Pos3 0 + 127473530 127474697 255,0,0
chr7 127474697 127475864 Pos4 0 + 127474697 127475864 255,0,0
chr7 127475864 127477031 Neg1 0 - 127475864 127477031 0,0,255
chr7 127477031 127478198 Neg2 0 - 127477031 127478198 0,0,255
chr7 127478198 127479365 Neg3 0 - 127478198 127479365 0,0,255
chr7 127479365 127480532 Pos5 0 + 127479365 127480532 255,0,0
chr7 127480532 127481699 Neg4 0 - 127480532 127481699 0,0,255
  
```

Mandatory columns

Optional columns

BedGraph format

browser position chr19:49302001-49304701

browser hide all

browser pack refGene encodeRegions

browser full altGraph

300 base wide bar graph, autoScale is on by default == graphing

limits will dynamically change to always show full range of data

in viewing window, priority = 20 positions this as the second graph

Note, zero-relative, half-open coordinate system in use for bedGraph format

track type=bedGraph name="BedGraph Format" description="BedGraph format" visibility=full color=200,100,0

altColor=0,100,200 priority=20

chr19 49302000 49302300 -1.0

chr19 49302300 49302600 -0.75

chr19 49302600 49302900 -0.50

chr19 49302900 49303200 -0.25

chr19 49303200 49303500 0.0

chr19 49303500 49303800 0.25

chr19 49303800 49304100 0.50

chr19 49304100 49304400 0.75

chr19 49304400 49304700 1.00

GFF3/GTF format (from <https://bioinfogp.cnb.csic.es/tools/seqjoy/help/>)

GFF3

```
##gff-version 3
##source-version ttracklayer 1.57.0
##date 2022-07-14
1 . gene 3631 5899 . + .
1 . transcript 3631 5899 . + .
1 . exon 3631 3913 . + .
1 . five_prime_utr 3631 . +
1 . CDS 3760 3913 . + 0
1 . start_codon 3760 3762 . +
1 . exon 3996 4276 . + .
1 . CDS 3996 4276 . + 2
1 . exon 4486 4605 . + .
1 . CDS 4486 4605 . + 0
1 . exon 4706 5095 . + .
1 . CDS 4706 5095 . + 0
1 . exon 5174 5326 . + .
1 . CDS 5174 5326 . + 0
1 . exon 5439 5899 . + .
1 . CDS 5439 5627 . + 0
1 . stop_codon 5628 5630 . +
1 . three_prime_utr 5631 5899 . +
```

Columns 1 to 8 are identical

Pairs tag-value have slightly different aspect

Column 9 ("attributes")

```
gene_name="NAC001",gene_biotype="protein_coding",ID="AT1G01010;
gene_name="NAC001",transcript_biotype="protein_coding",ID="AT1G01010.1;Parent="AT1G01010;
gene_name="NAC001",exon_number=1,exon_id="AT1G01010.1.exon1",ID="exon_1;Parent="AT1G01010.1;
gene_name="NAC001",ID="five_prime_utr_1;Parent="AT1G01010.1;
gene_name="NAC001",exon_number=1,protein_id="AT1G01010.1.ID=CDS_1;Parent="AT1G01010.1;
gene_name="NAC001",exon_number=1,ID="start_codon_1;Parent="AT1G01010.1;
gene_name="NAC001",exon_number=2,exon_id="AT1G01010.1.exon2",ID="exon_2;Parent="AT1G01010.1;
gene_name="NAC001",exon_number=2,protein_id="AT1G01010.1.ID=CDS_2;Parent="AT1G01010.1;
gene_name="NAC001",exon_number=3,exon_id="AT1G01010.1.exon3",ID="exon_3;Parent="AT1G01010.1;
gene_name="NAC001",exon_number=3,protein_id="AT1G01010.1.ID=CDS_3;Parent="AT1G01010.1;
gene_name="NAC001",exon_number=4,exon_id="AT1G01010.1.exon4",ID="exon_4;Parent="AT1G01010.1;
gene_name="NAC001",exon_number=4,protein_id="AT1G01010.1.ID=CDS_4;Parent="AT1G01010.1;
gene_name="NAC001",exon_number=5,exon_id="AT1G01010.1.exon5",ID="exon_5;Parent="AT1G01010.1;
gene_name="NAC001",exon_number=5,protein_id="AT1G01010.1.ID=CDS_5;Parent="AT1G01010.1;
gene_name="NAC001",exon_number=6,exon_id="AT1G01010.1.exon6",ID="exon_6;Parent="AT1G01010.1;
gene_name="NAC001",exon_number=6,protein_id="AT1G01010.1.ID=CDS_6;Parent="AT1G01010.1;
gene_name="NAC001",exon_number=6,ID="stop_codon_1;Parent="AT1G01010.1;
gene_name="NAC001",ID="three_prime_utr_1;Parent="AT1G01010.1;
```

Hierarchy is expressed differently. In GTF "gene_id" and "transcript_id" are compulsory from transcript level. In GFF3, the use of "Parent" allows more flexibility to represent dependence relationships

GTF

```
#genome-build TAIR10
#genome-build-accession GCA_000001735.1
#genebuild-last-updated 2010-09
1 . gene 3631 5899 . + .
1 . transcript 3631 5899 . + .
1 . exon 3631 3913 . + .
1 . CDS 3760 3913 . + 0
1 . start_codon 3760 3762 . +
1 . exon 3996 4276 . + .
1 . CDS 3996 4276 . + 2
1 . exon 4486 4605 . + .
1 . CDS 4486 4605 . + 0
1 . exon 4706 5095 . + .
1 . CDS 4706 5095 . + 0
1 . exon 5174 5326 . + .
1 . CDS 5174 5326 . + 0
1 . exon 5439 5899 . + .
1 . CDS 5439 5627 . + 0
1 . stop_codon 5628 5630 . +
1 . five_prime_utr 3631 3759 . +
1 . three_prime_utr 5631 5899 . +
```

```
gene_id "AT1G01010"; gene_name "NAC001"; gene_biotype "protein_coding";
gene_id "AT1G01010"; transcript_id "AT1G01010.1"; gene_name "NAC001"; transcript_biotype "protein_coding";
gene_id "AT1G01010"; transcript_id "AT1G01010.1"; exon_number "1"; gene_name "NAC001"; exon_id "AT1G01010.1.exon1";
gene_id "AT1G01010"; transcript_id "AT1G01010.1"; exon_number "1"; gene_name "NAC001"; protein_id "AT1G01010.1";
gene_id "AT1G01010"; transcript_id "AT1G01010.1"; exon_number "1"; gene_name "NAC001";
gene_id "AT1G01010"; transcript_id "AT1G01010.1"; exon_number "2"; gene_name "NAC001"; exon_id "AT1G01010.1.exon2";
gene_id "AT1G01010"; transcript_id "AT1G01010.1"; exon_number "2"; gene_name "NAC001"; protein_id "AT1G01010.1";
gene_id "AT1G01010"; transcript_id "AT1G01010.1"; exon_number "3"; gene_name "NAC001"; exon_id "AT1G01010.1.exon3";
gene_id "AT1G01010"; transcript_id "AT1G01010.1"; exon_number "3"; gene_name "NAC001"; protein_id "AT1G01010.1.exon3";
gene_id "AT1G01010"; transcript_id "AT1G01010.1"; exon_number "4"; gene_name "NAC001"; exon_id "AT1G01010.1.exon4";
gene_id "AT1G01010"; transcript_id "AT1G01010.1"; exon_number "4"; gene_name "NAC001"; protein_id "AT1G01010.1.exon4";
gene_id "AT1G01010"; transcript_id "AT1G01010.1"; exon_number "5"; gene_name "NAC001"; exon_id "AT1G01010.1.exon5";
gene_id "AT1G01010"; transcript_id "AT1G01010.1"; exon_number "5"; gene_name "NAC001"; protein_id "AT1G01010.1.exon5";
gene_id "AT1G01010"; transcript_id "AT1G01010.1"; exon_number "6"; gene_name "NAC001"; exon_id "AT1G01010.1.exon6";
gene_id "AT1G01010"; transcript_id "AT1G01010.1"; exon_number "6"; gene_name "NAC001"; protein_id "AT1G01010.1.exon6";
gene_id "AT1G01010"; transcript_id "AT1G01010.1"; exon_number "6"; gene_name "NAC001";
gene_id "AT1G01010"; transcript_id "AT1G01010.1"; gene_name "NAC001";
gene_id "AT1G01010"; transcript_id "AT1G01010.1"; gene_name "NAC001";
```

Annex3. [Identifier.org](https://www.identifier.org/) ID schemes related to genetic data or their annotation

Accession	Database Name	Species	Accession	Description	URL	Accession	Database Name	Species	Accession	Description	URL	Accession	Database Name	Species	Accession	Description	URL	Accession	Database Name	Species	Accession	Description	URL	Accession	Database Name	Species	Accession	Description	URL	Accession	Database Name	Species	Accession	Description	URL	Accession	Database Name	Species	Accession	Description	URL
MR0000027	WormBase	worm	WormBase	WormBase is an online bioinformatics database of the biology and genome of the model organism <i>Caenorhabditis elegans</i> and other nematodes. It is used by the C. elegans research community as an information resource and a place to publish and distribute their results. The database references WormBase accessioned entries.	http://identifiers.org/wb	MR0000024	NCBI	USA	MR0000025	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000026	NCBI	USA	MR0000027	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000028	NCBI	USA	MR0000029	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000030	NCBI	USA	MR0000031	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000032	NCBI	USA	MR0000033	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000034	NCBI	USA	MR0000035	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK
MR0000036	Plan	All species	Plan	The Plan database contains information about protein domains and families. For each entry a protein sequence alignment and a hidden Markov Model is stored.	http://identifiers.org/plan	MR0000036	NCBI	USA	MR0000037	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000038	NCBI	USA	MR0000039	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000040	NCBI	USA	MR0000041	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000042	NCBI	USA	MR0000043	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000044	NCBI	USA	MR0000045	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000046	NCBI	USA	MR0000047	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK
MR0000048	Nucleotide Database	All species	Nucleotide Database	The International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration (INSDC) consists of a joint effort to collect and disseminate nucleotide sequence data and RNA sequences.	http://identifiers.org/insdc	MR0000048	NCBI	USA	MR0000049	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000050	NCBI	USA	MR0000051	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000052	NCBI	USA	MR0000053	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000054	NCBI	USA	MR0000055	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000056	NCBI	USA	MR0000057	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000058	NCBI	USA	MR0000059	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK
MR0000060	FlyBase	Drosophila	FlyBase	FlyBase is the database of the <i>Drosophila</i> Genome Projects and of associated literature.	http://identifiers.org/fly	MR0000060	NCBI	USA	MR0000061	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000062	NCBI	USA	MR0000063	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000064	NCBI	USA	MR0000065	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000066	NCBI	USA	MR0000067	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000068	NCBI	USA	MR0000069	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000070	NCBI	USA	MR0000071	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK
MR0000071	Wormmap	worm	Wormmap	Wormmap contains the predicted protein sets from the <i>Caenorhabditis elegans</i> genome sequencing project.	http://identifiers.org/wormmap	MR0000071	NCBI	USA	MR0000072	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000073	NCBI	USA	MR0000074	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000075	NCBI	USA	MR0000076	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000077	NCBI	USA	MR0000078	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000079	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000080	NCBI	USA	MR0000081	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK			
MR0000082	PROSITE	All species	PROSITE	PROSITE consists of documentation entries describing protein domains, families and functional sites as well as predicted patterns and profiles to identify them.	http://identifiers.org/prosite	MR0000082	NCBI	USA	MR0000083	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000084	NCBI	USA	MR0000085	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000086	NCBI	USA	MR0000087	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000088	NCBI	USA	MR0000089	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000090	NCBI	USA	MR0000091	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000092	NCBI	USA	MR0000093	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK
MR0000094	ArrayExpress	All species	ArrayExpress	ArrayExpress is a public repository for microarray data, which is aimed at storing and disseminating data in accordance with Microarray Gene Expression Data (MGED) recommendations.	http://identifiers.org/arrayexpress	MR0000094	NCBI	USA	MR0000095	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000096	NCBI	USA	MR0000097	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000098	NCBI	USA	MR0000099	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000100	NCBI	USA	MR0000101	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000102	NCBI	USA	MR0000103	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000104	NCBI	USA	MR0000105	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK
MR0000106	Mouse Genome Database	Mouse	Mouse Genome Database	The Mouse Genome Database (MGD) project includes data on gene characterization, nomenclature, mapping, gene homologues among mammals, sequence links, phenotypes, allelic variants and products, and gene data.	http://identifiers.org/mgd	MR0000106	NCBI	USA	MR0000107	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000108	NCBI	USA	MR0000109	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000110	NCBI	USA	MR0000111	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000112	NCBI	USA	MR0000113	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000114	NCBI	USA	MR0000115	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000116	NCBI	USA	MR0000117	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK
MR0000118	RefSeq	All species	RefSeq	The Reference Sequence (RefSeq) project aims to provide a comprehensive, integrated, non-redundant set of sequences, including genomic DNA, transcripts (RNA), and protein products.	http://identifiers.org/refseq	MR0000118	NCBI	USA	MR0000119	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000120	NCBI	USA	MR0000121	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000122	NCBI	USA	MR0000123	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000124	NCBI	USA	MR0000125	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000126	NCBI	USA	MR0000127	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000128	NCBI	USA	MR0000129	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK
MR0000130	Transport Database	All species	Transport Database	The Transport Classification (TC) system is a database containing non-redundant protein sequence information from many sources. Each unique sequence is given a name and unique identifier (ID) making it possible to identify the same protein from different source databases.	http://identifiers.org/transport	MR0000130	NCBI	USA	MR0000131	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000132	NCBI	USA	MR0000133	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000134	NCBI	USA	MR0000135	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000136	NCBI	USA	MR0000137	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000138	NCBI	USA	MR0000139	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000140	NCBI	USA	MR0000141	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK
MR0000142	MINT	All species	MINT	The Molecular Interaction database (MINT) stores, in a structured format, information about molecular interactions by extracting experimental details from web-published or peer-reviewed journals.	http://identifiers.org/mint	MR0000142	NCBI	USA	MR0000143	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000144	NCBI	USA	MR0000145	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000146	NCBI	USA	MR0000147	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000148	NCBI	USA	MR0000149	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000150	NCBI	USA	MR0000151	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000152	NCBI	USA	MR0000153	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK
MR0000154	Signaling Gateway	All species	Signaling Gateway	The Signaling Gateway provides information on mammalian proteins involved in cellular signaling.	http://identifiers.org/signaling-gateway	MR0000154	NCBI	USA	MR0000155	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000156	NCBI	USA	MR0000157	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000158	NCBI	USA	MR0000159	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000160	NCBI	USA	MR0000161	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000162	NCBI	USA	MR0000163	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000164	NCBI	USA	MR0000165	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK
MR0000166	Rat Genome Database	rat	Rat Genome Database	Rat Genome Database seeks to collect, curate, and integrate rat genomic and genetic data with related functional and physiological data and make these data widely available to the scientific community. This collection references genes.	http://identifiers.org/rat	MR0000166	NCBI	USA	MR0000167	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000168	NCBI	USA	MR0000169	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000170	NCBI	USA	MR0000171	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000172	NCBI	USA	MR0000173	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000174	NCBI	USA	MR0000175	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000176	NCBI	USA	MR0000177	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK
MR0000178	Rat Protein	Aradidopsis	Rat Protein	The Arabidopsis Information Resource (TAIR) maintains a database of general and molecular biology data for the model higher plant <i>Arabidopsis thaliana</i> . This provides protein information for a given gene, and also provides links to other databases.	http://identifiers.org/tair-protein	MR0000178	NCBI	USA	MR0000179	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000180	NCBI	USA	MR0000181	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000182	NCBI	USA	MR0000183	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000184	NCBI	USA	MR0000185	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000186	NCBI	USA	MR0000187	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000188	NCBI	USA	MR0000189	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK
MR0000190	Rat Gene	Aradidopsis	Rat Gene	The Arabidopsis Information Resource (TAIR) maintains a database of general and molecular biology data for the model higher plant <i>Arabidopsis thaliana</i> . This is a reference gene model for a given gene.	http://identifiers.org/tair-gene	MR0000190	NCBI	USA	MR0000191	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000192	NCBI	USA	MR0000193	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000194	NCBI	USA	MR0000195	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000196	NCBI	USA	MR0000197	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000198	NCBI	USA	MR0000199	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000200	NCBI	USA	MR0000201	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK
MR0000202	Rat Locus	Aradidopsis	Rat Locus	The Arabidopsis Information Resource (TAIR) maintains a database of general and molecular biology data for the model higher plant <i>Arabidopsis thaliana</i> . This is a reference gene model for a given gene.	http://identifiers.org/tair-locus	MR0000202	NCBI	USA	MR0000203	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000204	NCBI	USA	MR0000205	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000206	NCBI	USA	MR0000207	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000208	NCBI	USA	MR0000209	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000210	NCBI	USA	MR0000211	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	MR0000212	NCBI	USA	MR0000213	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK

Accession	Species	Database	Description	Category	URL	ID	Accession	URL	Institution	Location	Official	ResourceType	Build	Accession	ResourceURL	Gene Expression Database	
MIR0000054	ECO	All species	The Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO) is a public, open resource for gene expression data browsing, query and retrieval.	gene	http://identifiers.org/geo	0	accessURL	geo	National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI)	USA	False	nbi	GDS1234	Fluorescent growth factor receptor 3 RGD5 mutation	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/		
MIR0000057	Saccharomyces genome database	yeast	Curated biochemical pathways for Saccharomyces genome database (SGD).	pathways	http://identifiers.org/gt/pathways	0	accessURL	sgd	SGD, Stanford University	USA	False	Pathway	PWY0-214	tryptophan degradation	http://pathway.yeastgenome.org/		
MIR0000058	bioGRID	yeast	BioGRID is a database of physical and genetic interactions in Saccharomyces cerevisiae, Caenorhabditis elegans, Drosophila melanogaster, Homo sapiens, and Schistosoma mansoni.	binding	http://identifiers.org/bioGRID	0	accessURL	bio	Ontario Cancer Institute	Canada	False	localid	11621	TAR2V	http://thebiogrid.org/		
MIR0000060	PANTHER Family	All species	PANTHER Family is a resource that classifies genes by their functions, using published scientific experimental evidence and evolutionary relationships to predict biological functions. PANTHER is a part of a broader effort to characterize a protein family as diagnostic protein identified by iterative scanning of a SWISS-PROT/TrEMBL composite. Study the PANTHER Family.	protein family	http://identifiers.org/pantther-family	0	accessURL	pfam	PANTHER Family at USC (Los Angeles)	USA	False	localid	P1812345	membrane trafficking regulatory protein	http://www.panttherdb.org/		
MIR0000061	PRINTS	All species	PRINTS is a database of protein fingerprints. A protein family is diagnostic protein identified by iterative scanning of a SWISS-PROT/TrEMBL composite. Study the PRINTS database.	prints	http://identifiers.org/prints	0	accessURL	prints	University of Manchester	United Kingdom	False	PROSITE	PROSITE00001	Signalase factor G4 domain signature	http://www.bioinf.manchester.ac.uk/000001/prints/		
MIR0000062	NCBI Gene	All species	Enter Gene is the NCBI's database for gene-specific information, focusing on completely sequenced genomes, those with an active research community, or those that are idealized for interest sequence analysis.	ncbi gene	http://identifiers.org/ncbigene	0	accessURL	ncbi	National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI)	USA	True	nbi	10010	repressed sequence AAG8556	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/gene/		
MIR0000070	KEGG Genes	All species	KEGG GENES is a collection of gene catalogs for all complete genomes and for many prokaryotic genomes, generated from publicly available resources.	kegg genes	http://identifiers.org/kegg.genes	0	accessURL	kegg	KEGG GENES Database	Japan	True	gn	gn:ncr501	glycylcholine S59 subunit alpha	http://www.genome.jp/kegg/genes.html		
MIR0000071	BRENDA	All species	BRENDA is a database of enzyme function and enzyme activity. Data on enzyme function are extracted directly from the primary literature. The database covers information on classification and enzyme kinetics.	enzyme	http://identifiers.org/brenda	0	accessURL	brenda	Technical University Braunschweig, Institute for Bioinformatics and Biotechnology	Germany	False	1.1.1.1	alcohol dehydrogenase	http://www.brenda-enzyme.org/			
MIR0000073	Pathway Commons	human	Pathway Commons is a database of biological pathway information collected from public domain databases, which can be browsed or searched. It is a collection of publicly available pathways from multiple organisms.	pathwaycommons	http://identifiers.org/pathwaycommons	0	accessURL	pc	Memorial Sloan-Kettering Cancer Center	USA	False	KEGG	KEGG01001	Nucleic Recombination	http://www.pathwaycommons.org/		
MIR0000074	HOVERGEN	vertebrate	HOVERGEN is a database of homology-annotated genes that allows one to select sets of homologous genes among vertebrate species, and to visualize multiple alignments and phylogenetic trees.	homolog	http://identifiers.org/hovergen	0	accessURL	hover	Laboratoire de Biochimie, Génétique et Biologie des Populations	France	False	HOVERGEN	HOVERGEN001	HOVERGEN001 gene family	http://bioinf.ucl.ac.uk/000001/hovergen/		
MIR0000075	Molecular Molecular Map Project Biomaps	human	A collection of molecular interaction maps and pathways involved in cancer development and progression with a focus on oncogenes.	mmmp biomaps	http://identifiers.org/mmmp.biomaps	0	accessURL	mmmp	Molecular Molecular Map Project	USA	True	PT	PT:phosphatidylinositol-3-kinase	Equilibrium of Akt in PI3K phosphorylation	http://www.mmmp.org/MMMP/publications		
MIR0000076	miRBase Sequence	All species	miRBase is a database of published miRNA sequences and annotations. The data were previously provided by the miRNA Registry. Each entry in the miRNA Sequence Database represents a predicted mature miRNA.	miRbase	http://identifiers.org/mirbase	0	accessURL	mi	miRBase Sequence Database	UK	False	MI000001	miR-1	miR-1	http://www.mirbase.org/		
MIR0000077	ZFIN Diversity	zebrafish	ZFIN serves as the zebrafish model organism database. This collection includes all zebrafish biological entities in ZFIN.	zfin	http://identifiers.org/zfin	0	accessURL	zfin	ZFIN at University of Oregon	USA	True	ZFIN	ZFIN-GENE-041118-11	zfin2412	http://zfin.org/		
MIR0000080	HNC	human	The HNCI HNCI Gene Nomenclature Committee provides an approved gene name and symbol (short name/abbreviation) for each known human gene. All approved symbols are stored in the HNCI database, and each symbol in other HNCI identifiers refer to records in the HNCI symbol database.	hnci	http://identifiers.org/hnci	0	accessURL	hnci	HNCI Gene Nomenclature Committee	UK	True	ncbi	2074	CC548842	https://www.genenames.org/		
MIR0000081	Sequence Ontology	All species	The Sequence Ontology (SO) is a structured controlled vocabulary for the parts of genetic annotation. It provides a common set of terms and definitions to facilitate the exchange, analysis, and management of genomic data.	ontology	http://identifiers.org/so	1	accessURL	so	Department of Molecular and Cellular Biology, University of California, Berkeley	USA	False	SO	SO:000001	necessary to encode a functional transcript.	http://www.sequenceontology.org/		
MIR0000082	UniPathway	All species	UniPathway is a manually curated resource of metabolic pathways for the UniProt database. UniPathway provides a structured controlled vocabulary to describe the role of a gene in a metabolic pathway.	unipathway	http://identifiers.org/unipathway	0	accessURL	unipathway	Gene Institute of Bioinformatics (GIB) and French National Institute for Research in Computer Science and Control	Netherlands	False	Pathway	UP000206	ethanol fermentation	http://www.genecode.org/unipathway/		
MIR0000083	PharmGKB Pathways	human	PharmGKB Pathways is a repository for genetic, genomic, molecular and cellular phenotype data and clinical information about people who have participated in pharmacogenetics research studies. The data includes, but is not limited to:	pharmgkb pathways	http://identifiers.org/pharmgkb.pathways	0	accessURL	pharmgkb	Department of Genetics, School of Medicine, Stanford University, Stanford, California	USA	False	Pathway	PA14133006	Cocaine and Morphine	http://www.pharmgkb.org/		
MIR0000087	BioSystems	All species	The NCBI BioSystems database curates and integrates existing systems databases, increasing their utility and accessibility by integrating their pathways and systems into NCBI BioSystems.	bioSystems	http://identifiers.org/biosystems	0	accessURL	bio	National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI)	USA	False	nbi	1	1	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/biosystems/		
MIR0000090	TCO Gene	human	The TCO Gene is a database of transcription factor binding sites (TFBS) identified, reviewed and curated information on transcription, relevant genes and proteins, and their interactions in vertebrates and invertebrates. It integrates sequence information from various sources.	tcogene	http://identifiers.org/tcogene	0	accessURL	tcogene	Comparative Transcription Database (TCO)	USA	False	TCO	TCO:000001	ADAM metalloprotease domain	http://tcobase.org/		
MIR0000106	GenDB	human pathogen	GenDB is a database of genomic and proteomic data for the pathogen group at the Wellcome Trust Sanger Institute and other collaborating institutions.	genDB	http://identifiers.org/genDB	0	accessURL	genDB	Pathogen Genomics, Sanger Institute and European Bioinformatics Institute	UK	False	localid	G1535c - GeneDB	G1535c - GeneDB	http://www.genedb.org/		
MIR0000109	Molecular Interactions	All species	The Molecular Interactions (MI) database forms a structured controlled vocabulary for the annotation of experimental interactions, with protein-protein interactions, MI is developed by the HNCI/Protein Standards Initiative.	mi	http://identifiers.org/mi	1	accessURL	mi	European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	False	mi	MI	MI:000001	MI:000001	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/infobo/mi/	
MIR0000116	KEGG Orthology	All species	KEGG Orthology (KO) consists of manually defined, gene-based orthology groups that correspond to KEGG pathway nodes and KEGG taxonomy nodes in all organisms.	kegg orthology	http://identifiers.org/kegg.orthology	0	accessURL	kegg	Department of Computational Biology, University of Tokyo, Tokyo	Japan	True	KEGG	KEGG01001	alcohol dehydrogenase	http://www.genome.jp/kegg/orthology/		
MIR0000118	SMART	All species	The Simple Modular Architecture Research Tool (SMART) is an online tool for the identification and annotation of protein domains, and the analysis of domain architectures.	smart	http://identifiers.org/smart	0	accessURL	smart	EMBL, Heidelberg	Germany	False	SMART	SMART00001	chromatin binding motif	http://smart.embl-heidelberg.de/		

Accession	Database Name	Species	Accession	Description	URL	Organization	Location	Official	Local	Web	FTP	Other	Notes
MIR0000119	Conserved Domain Database	All species	%04%05%5	The Conserved Domain Database (CDD) is a collection of multiple sequence alignments and domain databases (see) models, which represent protein domains conserved in molecular evolution.	http://identifiers.org/cdd	NCBI	USA	official	ncbi	ncbi	ncbi	ncbi	The CDD database
MIR0000120	Relation Ontology	Human	%04%07%5	The OBO Relation Ontology provides semantic and classification formal notations of the relational expressions used in biological ontologies.	http://identifiers.org/ro	University of Michigan Medical School (UM), Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory (CN) and Science Commons (US)	USA	official	local	local	local	local	collection of like units arranged in a linear order
MIR0000121	Molecular Modeling Database	All species	%11%5	The Molecular Modeling Database (MMDb) is a database of experimentally determined structures obtained from the Protein Data Bank (PDB). Since structures are not known for a large fraction of all protein families, structure homology modeling is used to generate predicted structures.	http://identifiers.org/mmdb	EMBL European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, Cambridge	UK	official	local	local	local	local	collection of like units arranged in a linear order
MIR0000124	Microbial Protein Interaction Database	Microbial organisms	%14%5	The Microbial Protein Interaction Database (MPID) provides physical interaction data. The interactions are manually curated from the literature or reported from other databases, and are linked to supporting experimental evidence, as well as evidence based on supporting experimental protein complex formation.	http://identifiers.org/mpid	Crang Venter Institute, Maryland	USA	official	local	local	local	local	Structural Basis of Action
MIR0000127	Ontology for Biomedical Investigations	Human	%08%14%07%5%08%14%07%5	The Ontology for Biomedical Investigations (OBI) project is developing an integrated ontology for the description of biological and clinical investigations. The ontology will represent the design of investigations, the protocols and instrumentation used, the material used, the data generated and the type of analysis performed on it. Currently OBI is being built under the Basic Formal Ontology (BFO).	http://identifiers.org/obi	University of Michigan Medical School (UM), Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory (CN) and Science Commons (US)	USA	official	local	local	local	local	A planned process with the objective to produce
MIR0000132	SubWiki	Bacillus subtilis	%10%14%05%5	SubWiki is a subwiki for the Bacillus subtilis genome. It provides comprehensive information on all genes and their proteins and RNA products, as well as information related to the current investigation of the gene/protein. New information is added as it becomes available.	http://identifiers.org/subwiki	University of Göttingen, Department for General Microbiology	Germany	official	local	local	local	local	private kinase, glyoxylate enzyme
MIR0000133	NCI Pathway Interaction Database	Human	%14%5	The Pathway Interaction Database (PID) is a highly structured, curated collection of information about known human molecular interactions and by which pathways assembled into signaling pathways. The database provides access to pathway information.	http://identifiers.org/pid/pathway	National Cancer Institute, Rockville, Maryland	USA	official	local	local	local	local	Class I PKC signaling events
MIR0000142	SNK	Animal	%14%5	SNK is a database of genes, inherited disorders, and traits in animal species (other than human and mouse).	http://identifiers.org/snka	Repigen, Faculty of Veterinary Science, University of Sydney	Australia	official	local	local	local	local	Skin colour, albinism
MIR0000143	Candida Genome Database	Candida	%04%07%5	The Candida Genome Database (CGD) provides access to genomic sequence data and manually curated functional information about genes and proteins of the human pathogen Candida albicans, 21 related gene forms, and others, and associated biological processes.	http://identifiers.org/cgd	Stanford University	USA	official	local	local	local	local	Heat Shock Protein
MIR0000144	KnoxBDB	Eukaryotic pathogens	%03%14%5	The KnoxBDB (http://knoxbdb.org) provides access to genomic sequence data and manually curated functional information about genes and proteins of the genera Cryptosporidium, Giardia, Isospora, Neospora, Plasmodium, and Toxoplasma.	http://identifiers.org/knoxbdb	Center for Tropical & Emerging Global Diseases, University of Georgia	USA	official	local	local	local	local	phosphatidylinositol-3-OH kinase
MIR0000145	CryptIDB	Eukaryotic pathogens	%14%5	The CryptIDB (http://cryptidb.org) provides access to genomic sequence data and manually curated functional information about genes and proteins of the genera Cryptosporidium, Giardia, Isospora, Neospora, Plasmodium, and Toxoplasma.	http://identifiers.org/cryptidb	Center for Tropical & Emerging Global Diseases, University of Georgia	USA	official	local	local	local	local	Cryptosporidium parvum ssp. 1
MIR0000151	PlasmoDB	Eukaryotic pathogens	%14%5	The PlasmoDB (http://plasmodb.org) provides access to genomic sequence data and manually curated functional information about genes and proteins of the genera Cryptosporidium, Giardia, Isospora, Neospora, Plasmodium, and Toxoplasma.	http://identifiers.org/plasmodb	Center for Tropical & Emerging Global Diseases, University of Georgia	USA	official	local	local	local	local	apical membrane antigen 1
MIR0000152	GiardiDB	Eukaryotic pathogens	%14%5	The GiardiDB (http://giardidb.org) provides access to genomic sequence data and manually curated functional information about genes and proteins of the genera Cryptosporidium, Giardia, Isospora, Neospora, Plasmodium, and Toxoplasma.	http://identifiers.org/giardidb	Center for Tropical & Emerging Global Diseases, University of Georgia	USA	official	local	local	local	local	Plasma membrane calcium-transporting ATPase 2
MIR0000153	MicrosporidDB	Eukaryotic pathogens	%14%5	The MicrosporidDB (http://microsporiddb.org) provides access to genomic sequence data and manually curated functional information about genes and proteins of the genera Cryptosporidium, Giardia, Isospora, Neospora, Plasmodium, and Toxoplasma.	http://identifiers.org/microsporiddb	Center for Tropical & Emerging Global Diseases, University of Georgia	USA	official	local	local	local	local	TUBULIN BETA CHAIN
MIR0000154	ToxIDB	Eukaryotic pathogens	%14%5	The ToxIDB (http://toxidb.org) provides access to genomic sequence data and manually curated functional information about genes and proteins of the genera Cryptosporidium, Giardia, Isospora, Neospora, Plasmodium, and Toxoplasma.	http://identifiers.org/toxidb	Center for Tropical & Emerging Global Diseases, University of Georgia	USA	official	local	local	local	local	importer alpha-n-exporter, putative
MIR0000155	TrichIDB	Eukaryotic pathogens	%14%5	The TrichIDB (http://trichidb.org) provides access to genomic sequence data and manually curated functional information about genes and proteins of the genera Cryptosporidium, Giardia, Isospora, Neospora, Plasmodium, and Toxoplasma.	http://identifiers.org/trichidb	Center for Tropical & Emerging Global Diseases, University of Georgia	USA	official	local	local	local	local	Class III, family MZA, aminopeptidase F-like metalloprotease
MIR0000156	TritypDB	Eukaryotic pathogens	%14%5	The TritypDB (http://tritypdb.org) provides access to genomic sequence data and manually curated functional information about genes and proteins of the genera Cryptosporidium, Giardia, Isospora, Neospora, Plasmodium, and Toxoplasma.	http://identifiers.org/tritypdb	Wellcome Trust Sanger Institute, Hinxton	UK	official	local	local	local	local	Trypanosoma brucei TRIC27
MIR0000157	SDP mutation DB	Drosophila	%14%5	SDP gene disruption collection provides a public resource of gene disruptions of Drosophila genes using a single transposon element.	http://identifiers.org/sdp/mutation	SDP Gene Disruption Project	USA	official	local	local	local	local	SDP gene disruption
MIR0000158	BerkeleyDB	Trichostema	%04%07%5	The BerkeleyDB (http://berkeleydb.org) provides access to genomic sequence data and manually curated functional information about genes, proteins, genetic markers, expressed sequence tags, and other biological features.	http://identifiers.org/berkeleydb	Berkeley at Kansas State University	USA	official	local	local	local	local	positions 17,144,698
MIR0000159	BOLD Taxonomy	All species	%14%5	The BOLD Taxonomy (http://www.boldsystems.org) provides access to genomic sequence data and manually curated functional information about genes, proteins, genetic markers, expressed sequence tags, and other biological features.	http://identifiers.org/bold-taxonomy	Canadian Centre for DNA Barcoding, Biodiversity Institute of Ontario	Canada	official	local	local	local	local	colibactin

Accession	Symbol	Species	Accession	Symbol	Species	Description	URL	Accession	Symbol	Species	Description	URL	Accession	Symbol	Species	Description	URL	Accession	Symbol	Species	Description	URL
MIR0000179	33A Gene	All species	146-5	33A	gene	33A gene	http://identifiers.org/ncbi-gene	MIR0000179	33A	gene	33A gene	http://identifiers.org/ncbi-gene	MIR0000179	33A	gene	33A gene	http://identifiers.org/ncbi-gene	MIR0000179	33A	gene	33A gene	http://identifiers.org/ncbi-gene
MIR0000179	33A Exp1	All species	146-5	33A Exp1	experiment	33A Exp1	http://identifiers.org/ncbi-expt	MIR0000179	33A Exp1	experiment	33A Exp1	http://identifiers.org/ncbi-expt	MIR0000179	33A Exp1	experiment	33A Exp1	http://identifiers.org/ncbi-expt	MIR0000179	33A Exp1	experiment	33A Exp1	http://identifiers.org/ncbi-expt
MIR0000185	PhosphoKinase	human	146-5	PhosphoKinase	protein	PhosphoKinase	http://identifiers.org/uniprot-kinase	MIR0000185	PhosphoKinase	protein	PhosphoKinase	http://identifiers.org/uniprot-kinase	MIR0000185	PhosphoKinase	protein	PhosphoKinase	http://identifiers.org/uniprot-kinase	MIR0000185	PhosphoKinase	protein	PhosphoKinase	http://identifiers.org/uniprot-kinase
MIR0000186	PhosphoProtein	human	146-5	PhosphoProtein	protein	PhosphoProtein	http://identifiers.org/uniprot-protein	MIR0000186	PhosphoProtein	protein	PhosphoProtein	http://identifiers.org/uniprot-protein	MIR0000186	PhosphoProtein	protein	PhosphoProtein	http://identifiers.org/uniprot-protein	MIR0000186	PhosphoProtein	protein	PhosphoProtein	http://identifiers.org/uniprot-protein
MIR0000188	33Aorf10	All species	146-5	33Aorf10	protein	33Aorf10	http://identifiers.org/uniprot-orf	MIR0000188	33Aorf10	protein	33Aorf10	http://identifiers.org/uniprot-orf	MIR0000188	33Aorf10	protein	33Aorf10	http://identifiers.org/uniprot-orf	MIR0000188	33Aorf10	protein	33Aorf10	http://identifiers.org/uniprot-orf
MIR0000192	hGAD	human	146-5	hGAD	gene	hGAD	http://identifiers.org/hgnc	MIR0000192	hGAD	gene	hGAD	http://identifiers.org/hgnc	MIR0000192	hGAD	gene	hGAD	http://identifiers.org/hgnc	MIR0000192	hGAD	gene	hGAD	http://identifiers.org/hgnc
MIR0000193	gphdbase Transcript	aphis	146-5	gphdbase Transc	transcript	gphdbase Transc	http://identifiers.org/gphdbase-transcript	MIR0000193	gphdbase Transc	transcript	gphdbase Transc	http://identifiers.org/gphdbase-transcript	MIR0000193	gphdbase Transc	transcript	gphdbase Transc	http://identifiers.org/gphdbase-transcript	MIR0000193	gphdbase Transc	transcript	gphdbase Transc	http://identifiers.org/gphdbase-transcript
MIR0000195	Trasfam	animal	146-5	Trasfam	protein	Trasfam	http://identifiers.org/trasfam	MIR0000195	Trasfam	protein	Trasfam	http://identifiers.org/trasfam	MIR0000195	Trasfam	protein	Trasfam	http://identifiers.org/trasfam	MIR0000195	Trasfam	protein	Trasfam	http://identifiers.org/trasfam
MIR0000197	Sub db	vertebrates	146-5	Sub db	database	Sub db	http://identifiers.org/subdb	MIR0000197	Sub db	database	Sub db	http://identifiers.org/subdb	MIR0000197	Sub db	database	Sub db	http://identifiers.org/subdb	MIR0000197	Sub db	database	Sub db	http://identifiers.org/subdb
MIR0000198	REAL	146-5	REAL	database	REAL	http://identifiers.org/real	MIR0000198	REAL	database	REAL	http://identifiers.org/real	MIR0000198	REAL	database	REAL	http://identifiers.org/real	MIR0000198	REAL	database	REAL	http://identifiers.org/real	
MIR0000200	GLD genome	All species	146-5	GLD genome	genome	GLD genome	http://identifiers.org/gld-genome	MIR0000200	GLD genome	genome	GLD genome	http://identifiers.org/gld-genome	MIR0000200	GLD genome	genome	GLD genome	http://identifiers.org/gld-genome	MIR0000200	GLD genome	genome	GLD genome	http://identifiers.org/gld-genome
MIR0000206	VarO	All species	146-5	VarO	ontology	VarO	http://identifiers.org/varo	MIR0000206	VarO	ontology	VarO	http://identifiers.org/varo	MIR0000206	VarO	ontology	VarO	http://identifiers.org/varo	MIR0000206	VarO	ontology	VarO	http://identifiers.org/varo
MIR0000208	APD	146-5	APD	database	APD	http://identifiers.org/apd	MIR0000208	APD	database	APD	http://identifiers.org/apd	MIR0000208	APD	database	APD	http://identifiers.org/apd	MIR0000208	APD	database	APD	http://identifiers.org/apd	
MIR0000209	TFAM	All species	146-5	TFAM	protein	TFAM	http://identifiers.org/ncbi-protein	MIR0000209	TFAM	protein	TFAM	http://identifiers.org/ncbi-protein	MIR0000209	TFAM	protein	TFAM	http://identifiers.org/ncbi-protein	MIR0000209	TFAM	protein	TFAM	http://identifiers.org/ncbi-protein
MIR0000210	Fungal Barcode	fungi	146-5	Fungal Barcode	barcode	Fungal Barcode	http://identifiers.org/fungal-barcode	MIR0000210	Fungal Barcode	barcode	Fungal Barcode	http://identifiers.org/fungal-barcode	MIR0000210	Fungal Barcode	barcode	Fungal Barcode	http://identifiers.org/fungal-barcode	MIR0000210	Fungal Barcode	barcode	Fungal Barcode	http://identifiers.org/fungal-barcode
MIR0000214	Agg2D locus	Aspergillus	146-5	Agg2D locus	locus	Agg2D locus	http://identifiers.org/agg2d-locus	MIR0000214	Agg2D locus	locus	Agg2D locus	http://identifiers.org/agg2d-locus	MIR0000214	Agg2D locus	locus	Agg2D locus	http://identifiers.org/agg2d-locus	MIR0000214	Agg2D locus	locus	Agg2D locus	http://identifiers.org/agg2d-locus
MIR0000215	Agg2D Protein	Aspergillus	146-5	Agg2D Protein	protein	Agg2D Protein	http://identifiers.org/agg2d-protein	MIR0000215	Agg2D Protein	protein	Agg2D Protein	http://identifiers.org/agg2d-protein	MIR0000215	Agg2D Protein	protein	Agg2D Protein	http://identifiers.org/agg2d-protein	MIR0000215	Agg2D Protein	protein	Agg2D Protein	http://identifiers.org/agg2d-protein
MIR0000215	AutDB	human	146-5	AutDB	database	AutDB	http://identifiers.org/autdb	MIR0000215	AutDB	database	AutDB	http://identifiers.org/autdb	MIR0000215	AutDB	database	AutDB	http://identifiers.org/autdb	MIR0000215	AutDB	database	AutDB	http://identifiers.org/autdb
MIR0000216	BackMap	bacteria	146-5	BackMap	map	BackMap	http://identifiers.org/backmap	MIR0000216	BackMap	map	BackMap	http://identifiers.org/backmap	MIR0000216	BackMap	map	BackMap	http://identifiers.org/backmap	MIR0000216	BackMap	map	BackMap	http://identifiers.org/backmap
MIR0000217	Ripe family	animal	146-5	Ripe family	family	Ripe family	http://identifiers.org/ripe-family	MIR0000217	Ripe family	family	Ripe family	http://identifiers.org/ripe-family	MIR0000217	Ripe family	family	Ripe family	http://identifiers.org/ripe-family	MIR0000217	Ripe family	family	Ripe family	http://identifiers.org/ripe-family
MIR0000218	Ripe gene	animal	146-5	Ripe gene	gene	Ripe gene	http://identifiers.org/ripe-gene	MIR0000218	Ripe gene	gene	Ripe gene	http://identifiers.org/ripe-gene	MIR0000218	Ripe gene	gene	Ripe gene	http://identifiers.org/ripe-gene	MIR0000218	Ripe gene	gene	Ripe gene	http://identifiers.org/ripe-gene
MIR0000219	PANTHER Component	All species	146-5	PANTHER Component	component	PANTHER Component	http://identifiers.org/pantHER-component	MIR0000219	PANTHER Component	component	PANTHER Component	http://identifiers.org/pantHER-component	MIR0000219	PANTHER Component	component	PANTHER Component	http://identifiers.org/pantHER-component	MIR0000219	PANTHER Component	component	PANTHER Component	http://identifiers.org/pantHER-component
MIR0000220	hGAD	human	146-5	hGAD	gene	hGAD	http://identifiers.org/hgnc	MIR0000220	hGAD	gene	hGAD	http://identifiers.org/hgnc	MIR0000220	hGAD	gene	hGAD	http://identifiers.org/hgnc	MIR0000220	hGAD	gene	hGAD	http://identifiers.org/hgnc

Accession	Project Name	Organism	Database	URL	Accession	Project Name	Organism	Database	URL	Accession	Project Name	Organism	Database	URL
MIR000014	Phytozone locus	Plant species	Phytozone locus	http://identifiers.org/phytozone	MIR000014	Phytozone locus	Plant species	Phytozone locus	http://identifiers.org/phytozone	MIR000014	Phytozone locus	Plant species	Phytozone locus	http://identifiers.org/phytozone
MIR000033	Subtilisin	Bacteria	Subtilisin	http://identifiers.org/subtilisin	MIR000033	Subtilisin	Bacteria	Subtilisin	http://identifiers.org/subtilisin	MIR000033	Subtilisin	Bacteria	Subtilisin	http://identifiers.org/subtilisin
MIR000037	WtGenes	All species	WtGenes	http://identifiers.org/wtgenes	MIR000037	WtGenes	All species	WtGenes	http://identifiers.org/wtgenes	MIR000037	WtGenes	All species	WtGenes	http://identifiers.org/wtgenes
MIR000038	Broad Fungal Genome Initiative	Fungi	Broad Fungal Genome Initiative	http://identifiers.org/broad	MIR000038	Broad Fungal Genome Initiative	Fungi	Broad Fungal Genome Initiative	http://identifiers.org/broad	MIR000038	Broad Fungal Genome Initiative	Fungi	Broad Fungal Genome Initiative	http://identifiers.org/broad
MIR000042	CoatWili	Fish	CoatWili	http://identifiers.org/coatwili	MIR000042	CoatWili	Fish	CoatWili	http://identifiers.org/coatwili	MIR000042	CoatWili	Fish	CoatWili	http://identifiers.org/coatwili
MIR000048	ABC	Insect	ABC	http://identifiers.org/abc	MIR000048	ABC	Insect	ABC	http://identifiers.org/abc	MIR000048	ABC	Insect	ABC	http://identifiers.org/abc
MIR000049	VirZone	Insect	VirZone	http://identifiers.org/virzone	MIR000049	VirZone	Insect	VirZone	http://identifiers.org/virzone	MIR000049	VirZone	Insect	VirZone	http://identifiers.org/virzone
MIR000050	Gene Ontology Reference	All species	Gene Ontology Reference	http://identifiers.org/go/ref	MIR000050	Gene Ontology Reference	All species	Gene Ontology Reference	http://identifiers.org/go/ref	MIR000050	Gene Ontology Reference	All species	Gene Ontology Reference	http://identifiers.org/go/ref
MIR000051	Eni Genome Database (Ei)	Eni	Eni Genome Database (Ei)	http://identifiers.org/eni	MIR000051	Eni Genome Database (Ei)	Eni	Eni Genome Database (Ei)	http://identifiers.org/eni	MIR000051	Eni Genome Database (Ei)	Eni	Eni Genome Database (Ei)	http://identifiers.org/eni
MIR000053	DOOR	Prokaryotes	DOOR	http://identifiers.org/door	MIR000053	DOOR	Prokaryotes	DOOR	http://identifiers.org/door	MIR000053	DOOR	Prokaryotes	DOOR	http://identifiers.org/door
MIR000054	Regatome Database	Mammalian	Regatome Database	http://identifiers.org/regatome	MIR000054	Regatome Database	Mammalian	Regatome Database	http://identifiers.org/regatome	MIR000054	Regatome Database	Mammalian	Regatome Database	http://identifiers.org/regatome
MIR000055	DBD	All species	DBD	http://identifiers.org/dbd	MIR000055	DBD	All species	DBD	http://identifiers.org/dbd	MIR000055	DBD	All species	DBD	http://identifiers.org/dbd
MIR000056	DATF	Archaea	DATF	http://identifiers.org/datf	MIR000056	DATF	Archaea	DATF	http://identifiers.org/datf	MIR000056	DATF	Archaea	DATF	http://identifiers.org/datf
MIR000058	YFC FOR	Yeast	YFC FOR	http://identifiers.org/yfcfor	MIR000058	YFC FOR	Yeast	YFC FOR	http://identifiers.org/yfcfor	MIR000058	YFC FOR	Yeast	YFC FOR	http://identifiers.org/yfcfor
MIR000060	Yeast Intron Database v1	Yeast	Yeast Intron Database v1	http://identifiers.org/yid	MIR000060	Yeast Intron Database v1	Yeast	Yeast Intron Database v1	http://identifiers.org/yid	MIR000060	Yeast Intron Database v1	Yeast	Yeast Intron Database v1	http://identifiers.org/yid
MIR000061	YeastBase Fly	Drosophila	YeastBase Fly	http://identifiers.org/yeastbase-fly	MIR000061	YeastBase Fly	Drosophila	YeastBase Fly	http://identifiers.org/yeastbase-fly	MIR000061	YeastBase Fly	Drosophila	YeastBase Fly	http://identifiers.org/yeastbase-fly
MIR000062	YeastBase Human	Human	YeastBase Human	http://identifiers.org/yeastbase-human	MIR000062	YeastBase Human	Human	YeastBase Human	http://identifiers.org/yeastbase-human	MIR000062	YeastBase Human	Human	YeastBase Human	http://identifiers.org/yeastbase-human
MIR000063	YeastBase Mouse	Mouse	YeastBase Mouse	http://identifiers.org/yeastbase-mouse	MIR000063	YeastBase Mouse	Mouse	YeastBase Mouse	http://identifiers.org/yeastbase-mouse	MIR000063	YeastBase Mouse	Mouse	YeastBase Mouse	http://identifiers.org/yeastbase-mouse
MIR000064	YeastBase Yeast	Yeast	YeastBase Yeast	http://identifiers.org/yeastbase-yeast	MIR000064	YeastBase Yeast	Yeast	YeastBase Yeast	http://identifiers.org/yeastbase-yeast	MIR000064	YeastBase Yeast	Yeast	YeastBase Yeast	http://identifiers.org/yeastbase-yeast
MIR000065	YdPM	Yeast	YdPM	http://identifiers.org/ydpm	MIR000065	YdPM	Yeast	YdPM	http://identifiers.org/ydpm	MIR000065	YdPM	Yeast	YdPM	http://identifiers.org/ydpm
MIR000066	YormBase RNA	Worm	YormBase RNA	http://identifiers.org/yormbase	MIR000066	YormBase RNA	Worm	YormBase RNA	http://identifiers.org/yormbase	MIR000066	YormBase RNA	Worm	YormBase RNA	http://identifiers.org/yormbase
MIR000067	YoutCat	All species	YoutCat	http://identifiers.org/youtcat	MIR000067	YoutCat	All species	YoutCat	http://identifiers.org/youtcat	MIR000067	YoutCat	All species	YoutCat	http://identifiers.org/youtcat
MIR000069	Yseberg element	Bacteria	Yseberg element	http://identifiers.org/yseberg-element	MIR000069	Yseberg element	Bacteria	Yseberg element	http://identifiers.org/yseberg-element	MIR000069	Yseberg element	Bacteria	Yseberg element	http://identifiers.org/yseberg-element
MIR000070	Yseberg family	Bacteria	Yseberg family	http://identifiers.org/yseberg-family	MIR000070	Yseberg family	Bacteria	Yseberg family	http://identifiers.org/yseberg-family	MIR000070	Yseberg family	Bacteria	Yseberg family	http://identifiers.org/yseberg-family
MIR000072	YFCB Gene	Bacteria	YFCB Gene	http://identifiers.org/yfcb-gene	MIR000072	YFCB Gene	Bacteria	YFCB Gene	http://identifiers.org/yfcb-gene	MIR000072	YFCB Gene	Bacteria	YFCB Gene	http://identifiers.org/yfcb-gene

MSI-00000563	GTEx	human	1-14-15	The Genotype-Tissue Expression (GTEx) project aims to provide to the scientific community a resource with which to study human gene expression and regulation and its relationship to genetic variation.	gene	http://identifiers.org/gtex	0	id	accessURL	info	institution	location	official	locid	resourceURL			
									MSI-00100881 https://www.gtexportal.org/home/gene/556	The GTEx Project	The Broad Institute of MIT and Harvard	USA	False	BRP1	https://www.gtexportal.org			
MSI-00000564	RegulatorDB Gene	yeast	12/01/2011-12/01/2015	RegulatorDB is a comprehensive regulatory database on yeast. It is a genome-wide database of transcription factors and their targets. It was developed on yeast using ChIP, FACS and GFPs to facilitate genomic regulatory analysis and gene identification.	transcription gene	http://identifiers.org/regdb.gene	0	id	accessURL	info	institution	location	official	locid	resourceURL			
									MSI-00100882 http://bio.yu.edu.cn/regdb/geneidetail.php?id=10	RegulatorDB	College of Life Sciences, Zhejiang University	China	False	LOC_Ch0149190.1	http://bio.yu.edu.cn/regdb/			
MSI-00000565	RegulatorDB Protein	yeast	12/01/2011-12/01/2015	RegulatorDB is a comprehensive regulatory database on yeast. It is a genome-wide database of transcription factors and their targets. It was developed on yeast using ChIP, FACS and GFPs to facilitate genomic regulatory analysis and gene identification.	transcription protein	http://identifiers.org/regdb.protein	0	id	accessURL	info	institution	location	official	locid	resourceURL			
									MSI-00100883 http://bio.yu.edu.cn/regdb/proteinidetail.php?id=10	RegulatorDB	College of Life Sciences, Zhejiang University	China	False	LOC_Ch0149190	http://bio.yu.edu.cn/regdb/			
MSI-00000566	RegulatorDB mRNA	yeast	12/01/2011-12/01/2015	RegulatorDB is a comprehensive regulatory database on yeast. It is a genome-wide database of transcription factors and their targets. It was developed on yeast using ChIP, FACS and GFPs to facilitate genomic regulatory analysis and gene identification.	transcription mRNA	http://identifiers.org/regdb.mrna	0	id	accessURL	info	institution	location	official	locid	resourceURL			
									MSI-00100886 http://bio.yu.edu.cn/regdb/mRNAidetail.php?id=10	RegulatorDB mRNA	College of Life Sciences, Zhejiang University	China	False	nc-mR-606	http://bio.yu.edu.cn/regdb/			
MSI-00000575	Adigene Plasmid Repository	plasmid	10/9/2014-11/20/2015	Adigene is a non-profit plasmid repository. Adigene facilitates the exchange of genetic material between laboratories by offering plasmids and their associated cloning data to not-for-profit laboratories around the world.	adigene	http://identifiers.org/adigene	0	id	accessURL	info	institution	location	official	locid	resourceURL			
									MSI-00100889 http://adigene.org/545	Adigene Plasmid Repository	Adigene	USA	False	DSB3	http://adigene.org/			
MSI-00000576	Bacterial Diversity Metadatabase	Diversity	10/9/14	BacDive—the Bacterial Diversity Metadatabase—provides structural taxonomic information on the different hosts of bacterial and archaeal biodiversity.	bacterial diversity	http://identifiers.org/bacdive	0	id	accessURL	info	institution	location	official	locid	resourceURL			
									MSI-00100900 https://bacdiv.dsmz.de/home/545	Bacterial Diversity Metadatabase	Leibniz-Institut DSMZ-Deutsche Sammlung von Mikroorganismen und Zellkulturen	Germany	False	131362	https://bacdiv.dsmz.de/			
MSI-00000579	The dbPortal for Cancer Genomics	human	14-05-14-15	The dbPortal for Cancer Genomics provides visualization, analysis and download of large-scale cancer genomics data sets.	dbportal	http://identifiers.org/dbportal	0	id	accessURL	info	institution	location	official	locid	resourceURL			
									MSI-00100909 http://www.dbportal.org/study/94-C6dSummary	The dbPortal for Cancer Genomics	Memorial Sloan Kettering Cancer Center	USA	False	ncm_rhg_pdb	http://www.dbportal.org			

Annex4 List of plant genomes stored in Ensembl Plants

Name	Classification	Taxon ID	Assembly	Accession	Variation database	Regulation database	Whole genome alignments	Other alignments	In peptide compara	In pan-taxonomic compara
<i>Actinidia chinensis</i>	eudicotyledons	1590841	Red5_PS1_1.69.0	GCA_003024255.1	-	-		-		-
<i>Aegilops tauschii</i>	Liliopsida	200361	Aet_v4.0	GCA_002575655.1	-	-		-		-
<i>Amborella trichopoda</i>	Amborellales	13333	AMTR1.0	GCA_000471905.1	-	-		-		-
<i>Ananas comosus</i>	Liliopsida	4615	F153	GCA_902162155.1	-	-		-		-
<i>Arabidopsis halleri</i>	eudicotyledons	63677	Ahal2.2	GCA_900078215.1	-	-		-		-
<i>Arabidopsis lyrata</i>	eudicotyledons	81972	v.1.0	GCA_000004255.1	-	-		-		-
<i>Arabidopsis thaliana</i>	eudicotyledons	3702	TAIR10	GCA_000001735.1	-	-		-		-
<i>Arabis alpina</i>	eudicotyledons	50452	A_alpina_V4	GCA_000733195.1	-	-		-		-
<i>Asparagus officinalis</i>	Liliopsida	4686	Aspof.V1	GCA_001876935.1	-	-		-		-
<i>Avena sativa OT3098</i>	Liliopsida	4498	Oat_OT3098_v2	GCA_022788535.1	-	-		-		-
<i>Avena sativa Sang</i>	Liliopsida	4498	Asativa_sang.v1.1	GCA_910574605.1	-	-		-		-
<i>Beta vulgaris</i>	eudicotyledons	3555	RefBeet-1.2.2	GCA_000511025.2	-	-		-		-
<i>Brachypodium distachyon</i>	Liliopsida	15368	Brachypodium_distachyon_v3.0	GCA_000005505.4	-	-		-		-
<i>Brassica juncea</i>	eudicotyledons	3707	ASM1870372v1	GCA_018703725.1	-	-		-		-
<i>Brassica napus</i>	eudicotyledons	3708	AST_PRJEB5043_v1	GCA_000751015.1	-	-		-		-
<i>Brassica oleracea</i>	eudicotyledons	109376	BOL	GCA_000695525.1	-	-		-		-
<i>Brassica rapa</i>	eudicotyledons	3711	Brapa_1.0	GCA_000309985.1	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Brassica rapa R-o-18</i>	eudicotyledons	1813537	SCU_BraROA_2.3	GCA_017639395.1	-	-		-		-
<i>Cajanus cajan (pigeon pea) - GCA_000340665.1</i>	eudicotyledons	3821	C.cajan_V1.0	GCA_000340665.1	-	-		-		-
<i>Camelina sativa</i>	eudicotyledons	90675	Cs	GCA_000633955.1	-	-		-		-
<i>Cannabis sativa female</i>	eudicotyledons	3483	cs10	GCA_900626175.1	-	-		-		-
<i>Capsicum annuum</i>	eudicotyledons	4072	ASM51225v2	GCA_000512255.2	-	-		-		-
<i>Chara braunii</i>	Streptophyta	69332	Cbr_1.0	GCA_003427395.1	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Chenopodium quinoa</i>	eudicotyledons	63459	ASM168347v1	GCA_001683475.1	-	-		-		-
<i>Chlamydomonas reinhardtii</i>	Chlorophyta	3055	Chlamydomonas_reinhardtii_v5.5	GCA_000002595.3	-	-		-		-
<i>Chondrus crispus</i>	Rhodophyta	2769	ASM35022v2	GCA_000350225.2	-	-		-		-
<i>Citullus lanatus</i>	eudicotyledons	3654	Cla97_v1	GCA_000238415.2	-	-		-		-
<i>Citrus clementina</i>	eudicotyledons	85681	Citrus_clementina_v1.0	GCA_000493195.1	-	-		-		-
<i>Coffea canephora</i>	eudicotyledons	49390	AUK_PRJEB4211_v1	GCA_900059795.1	-	-		-		-
<i>Corchorus capsularis</i>	eudicotyledons	210143	CCACVL1_1.0	GCA_001974805.1	-	-		-		-
<i>Corylus avellana</i>	eudicotyledons	13451	CavTom2PMs-1.0	GCA_901000735.2	-	-		-		-
<i>Corymbia citriodora</i>	eudicotyledons	360336	Ccitriondora_v2_1	GCA_014858505.1	-	-		-		-
<i>Cucumis melo</i>	eudicotyledons	3656	Melonv4	GCA_902497455.1	-	-		-		-
<i>Cucumis sativus</i>	eudicotyledons	3659	ASM407v2	GCA_000004075.2	-	-		-		-
<i>Cyanidioschyzon merolae</i>	Rhodophyta	280699	ASM9120v1	GCA_000091205.1	-	-		-		-
<i>Cynara cardunculus</i>	eudicotyledons	59895	CcrdV1	GCA_001531365.1	-	-		-		-
<i>Daucus carota</i>	eudicotyledons	79200	ASM162521v1	GCA_001625215.1	-	-		-		-
<i>Digitaria exilis</i>	Liliopsida	1010633	Fonio_CM05836	GCA_902859565.1	-	-		-		-
<i>Dioscorea rotundata</i>	Liliopsida	55577	TDr96_F1_v2_PseudoChromosome	GCA_009730915.1	-	-		-		-
<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i>	Liliopsida	90397	ec_v3	GCA_020466025.1	-	-		-		-
<i>Eragrostis curvula</i>	Liliopsida	38414	CERZOS_E.curvula1.0	GCA_007726485.1	-	-		-		-
<i>Eragrostis tef</i>	Liliopsida	110835	Salk_teff_dabbi_3.0	GCA_024500355.1	-	-		-		-
<i>Eucalyptus grandis</i>	eudicotyledons	71139	Egrandis1_0	GCA_000612305.1	-	-		-		-
<i>Eutrema salsugineum</i>	eudicotyledons	72664	Eutsalg1_0	GCA_000478725.1	-	-		-		-
<i>Ficus carica</i>	eudicotyledons	3494	UNIP1_FiCari_1.0	GCA_009761775.1	-	-		-		-
<i>Fraxinus excelsior</i>	eudicotyledons	38873	BATG-0.5	GCA_900149125.1	-	-		-		-
<i>Galdieria sulphuraria</i>	Rhodophyta	130081	ASM34128v1	GCA_000341285.1	-	-		-		-
<i>Glycine max</i>	eudicotyledons	3847	Glycine_max_v2.1	GCA_000004515.4	-	-		-		-
<i>Gossypium raimondii</i>	eudicotyledons	29730	Graimondii2_0_v6	GCA_000327365.1	-	-		-		-
<i>Helianthus annuus</i>	eudicotyledons	4232	HanXRQr2.0-SUNRISE	GCA_002127325.2	-	-		-		-
<i>Hordeum vulgare</i>	Liliopsida	112509	MorexV3_pseudomolecules_assembly	GCA_904849725.1	-	-		-		-
<i>Hordeum vulgare GoldenPromise</i>	Liliopsida	112509	GPv1	GCA_902500625.1	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Hordeum vulgare TRITEX</i>	Liliopsida	112509	Morex_V2_scaf	GCA_903813605.1	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Ipomoea triloba</i>	eudicotyledons	35885	ASM357664v1	GCA_003576645.1	-	-		-		-
<i>Juglans regia</i>	eudicotyledons	51240	Walnut_2.0	GCA_001411555.2	-	-		-		-

Name	Classification	Taxon ID	Assembly	Accession	Variation database	Regulation database	Whole genome alignments	Other alignments	In peptide compara	In pan-taxonomic compara
<i>Kalanchoe fedtschenkoi</i>	eudicotyledons	63787	K_fedtschenkoi_M2_v1	GCA_002312845.1	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Lactuca sativa</i>	eudicotyledons	4236	Lsat_Salinas_v7	GCA_002870075.2	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Leersia perrieri</i>	Liliopsida	77586	Lperr_V1.4	GCA_000325765.3	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Lolium perenne</i>	Liliopsida	4522	MPB_Lper_Kyuss_1697	GCA_019359855.1	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Lupinus angustifolius</i>	eudicotyledons	3871	LupAngTanjil_v1.0	GCA_001865875.1	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Malus domestica</i> Golden	eudicotyledons	3750	ASM211411v1	GCA_002114115.1	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Manihot esculenta</i>	eudicotyledons	3983	Manihot_esculenta_v6	GCA_001659605.1	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Marchantia polymorpha</i>	Embryophyta	3197	Marchantia_polymorpha_v1	GCA_003032435.1	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Medicago truncatula</i>	eudicotyledons	3880	MedtrA17_4.0	GCA_000219495.2	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Musa acuminata</i>	Liliopsida	214687	Musa_acuminata_v2	GCA_904845865.1	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Nicotiana attenuata</i>	eudicotyledons	49451	NIATTr2	GCA_001879085.1	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Nymphaea colorata</i>	Embryophyta	210225	ASM883128v1	GCA_008831285.1	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Olea europaea</i>	eudicotyledons	158383	OLEA9	GCA_902713445.1	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Olea europaea</i> var. <i>syvestris</i>	eudicotyledons	158386	O_europaea_v1	GCA_002742605.1	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Oryza barthii</i>	Liliopsida	65489	O.barthii_v1	GCA_000182155.2	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Oryza brachyantha</i>	Liliopsida	4533	Oryza_brachyantha.v1.4b	GCA_000231095.2	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Oryza glaberrima</i>	Liliopsida	4538	Oryza_glaberrima_V1	GCA_000147395.1	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Oryza glumipatula</i>	Liliopsida	40148	Oryza_glumaepatula_v1.5	GCA_000576495.1	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Oryza longistaminata</i>	Liliopsida	4528	O_longistaminata_v1.0	GCA_000789195.1	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Oryza meridionalis</i>	Liliopsida	40149	Oryza_meridionalis_v1.3	GCA_000338895.2	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Oryza nivara</i>	Liliopsida	4536	Oryza_nivara_v1.0	GCA_000576065.1	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Oryza punctata</i>	Liliopsida	4537	Oryza_punctata_v1.2	GCA_000573905.1	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Oryza rufipogon</i>	Liliopsida	4529	OR_W1943	GCA_000817225.1	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Oryza sativa</i> (Geng/Japonica-sbtrp var. Chao Meo)	Liliopsida	1736656	Os132278RS1	GCA_009831315.1	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Oryza sativa</i> (Geng/Japonica-trop1 var. Azucena)	Liliopsida	1736656	AzucenaRS1	GCA_009830595.1	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Oryza sativa</i> (Geng/Japonica-trop2 var. Ketan Nangka)	Liliopsida	1736656	Os128077RS1	GCA_009831275.1	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Oryza sativa</i> (Xian/Indica-1A var. Zhenshan 97)	Liliopsida	39946	ZS97RS3	GCA_001618795.1	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Oryza sativa</i> (Xian/Indica-1B1 var. IR64)	Liliopsida	39946	OsIR64RS1	GCA_009914875.1	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Oryza sativa</i> (Xian/Indica-1B2 var. PR106)	Liliopsida	39946	Os127742RS1	GCA_009831045.1	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Oryza sativa</i> (Xian/Indica-2A var. Gobol Sail)	Liliopsida	39946	Os132424RS1	GCA_009831025.1	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Oryza sativa</i> (Xian/Indica-2B var. Larha Mugad)	Liliopsida	39946	Os125619RS1	GCA_009831355.1	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Oryza sativa</i> (Xian/Indica-3A var. Lima)	Liliopsida	39946	Os127564RS1	GCA_009829395.1	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Oryza sativa</i> (Xian/Indica-3B1 var. Khao Yai Guang)	Liliopsida	39946	Os127518RS1	GCA_009831295.1	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Oryza sativa</i> (Xian/Indica-3B2 var. Liu Xu)	Liliopsida	39946	Os125827RS1	GCA_009829375.1	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Oryza sativa</i> (Xian/Indica-adm var. Minghui 63)	Liliopsida	39946	MH63RS2	GCA_001618785.1	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Oryza sativa</i> (circum-Aus1 var. N22)	Liliopsida	1736659	OsN22RS2	GCA_001952365.2	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Oryza sativa</i> (circum-Aus2 var. Natel Boro)	Liliopsida	1736659	Os127652RS1	GCA_009831335.1	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Oryza sativa</i> (circum-Basmati var. ARC 10497)	Liliopsida	1736658	Os117425RS1	GCA_009831255.1	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Oryza sativa</i> Indica Group	Liliopsida	39946	ASM465v1	GCA_000004655.2	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Oryza sativa</i> Japonica Group	Liliopsida	39947	IRGSP-1.0	GCA_001433935.1	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Ostreococcus lucimarinus</i>	Chlorophyta	436017	ASM9206v1	GCA_000092065.1	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Panicum hallii</i> FIL2	Liliopsida	206008	PHallii_v3.1	GCA_002211085.2	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Panicum hallii</i> HAL2	Liliopsida	1504633	PHalliiHAL_v2.1	GCA_003061485.1	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Papaver somniferum</i>	Embryophyta	3469	ASM357369v1	GCA_003573695.1	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Phaseolus vulgaris</i>	eudicotyledons	3885	PhaVulg1_0	GCA_000499845.1	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Physcomitrium patens</i>	Embryophyta	3218	Phypa_V3	GCA_000002425.2	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Pistacia vera</i>	eudicotyledons	55513	PisVer_v2	GCA_008641045.1	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Pisum sativum</i>	eudicotyledons	3888	Pisum_sativum_v1a	GCA_900700895.2	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Populus trichocarpa</i>	eudicotyledons	3694	Pop_tri_v4	GCA_000002775.4	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Prunus avium</i>	eudicotyledons	42229	PAV_r1.0	GCA_002207925.1	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Prunus dulcis</i>	eudicotyledons	3755	ALMONDv2	GCA_902201215.1	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Prunus persica</i>	eudicotyledons	3760	Prunus_persica_NCBiv2	GCA_000346465.2	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Quercus lobata</i>	eudicotyledons	97700	ValleyOak3.0	GCA_001633185.2	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Quercus suber</i>	eudicotyledons	58331	CorkOak1.0	GCA_002906115.4	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Rosa chinensis</i>	eudicotyledons	74649	RchiOBHm-V2	GCA_002994745.2	-	-	-	-	-	-

Name	Classification	Taxon ID	Assembly	Accession	Variation database	Regulation database	Whole genome alignments	Other alignments	In peptide compara	In pan-taxonomic compara
Saccharum spontaneum	Liliopsida	62335	Sspon.HiC_chr_asm	GCA_003544955.1	-	-		-		-
Secale cereale	Liliopsida	4550	Rye_Lo7_2018_v1p1p1	GCA_902687465.1	-	-		-		-
Selaginella moellendorffii	Embryophyta	88036	v1.0	GCA_000143415.1	-	-				
Sesamum indicum	eudicotyledons	4182	S_indicum_v1.0	GCA_000512975.1	-	-		-		-
Setaria italica	Liliopsida	4555	Setaria_italica_v2.0	GCA_000263155.2	-	-				-
Setaria viridis	Liliopsida	4556	Setaria_viridis_v2.0	GCA_005286985.1	-	-		-		-
Solanum lycopersicum	eudicotyledons	4081	SL3.0	GCA_000188115.3						
Solanum tuberosum	eudicotyledons	4113	SoITub_3.0	GCA_000226075.1	-	-				-
Solanum tuberosum RH89-039-16	eudicotyledons	4113	ASM1418947v1	GCA_014189475.1			-	-	-	-
Sorghum bicolor	Liliopsida	4558	Sorghum_bicolor_NCBIV3	GCA_000003195.3	-	-				-
Theobroma cacao Belizian Criollo B97-61/B2	eudicotyledons	3641	Criollo_cocoa_genome_V2	GCA_000208745.2	-	-	-	-	-	-
Theobroma cacao Matina 1-6	eudicotyledons	3641	Theobroma_cacao_20110822	GCA_000403535.1	-	-				-
Trifolium pratense	eudicotyledons	57577	Trpr	GCA_900079335.1	-	-				-
Triticum aestivum	Liliopsida	4565	IWGSC	GCA_900519105.1						-
Triticum aestivum Arinalfor	Liliopsida	4565	PGSBv2.1	GCA_903993985.1	-	-		-		-
Triticum aestivum Cadenza	Liliopsida	4565	Elv1.1	GCA_902810645.1	-	-	-	-	-	-
Triticum aestivum Claire	Liliopsida	4565	Elv1.1	GCA_902810655.1	-	-	-	-	-	-
Triticum aestivum Jagger	Liliopsida	4565	PGSBv2.1	GCA_903993795.1	-	-		-		-
Triticum aestivum Julius	Liliopsida	4565	PGSBv2.1	GCA_903994195.1	-	-		-		-
Triticum aestivum Kariega	Liliopsida	4565	Tae_Kariega_v1	GCA_910594105.1	-	-	-	-	-	-
Triticum aestivum Lancer	Liliopsida	4565	PGSBv2.1	GCA_903993975.1	-	-		-		-
Triticum aestivum Landmark	Liliopsida	4565	PGSBv2.1	GCA_903995565.1	-	-		-		-
Triticum aestivum Mace	Liliopsida	4565	PGSBv2.1	GCA_903994175.1	-	-		-		-
Triticum aestivum Norin61	Liliopsida	4565	PGSBv2.1	GCA_904066035.1	-	-		-		-
Triticum aestivum Paragon	Liliopsida	4565	Elv1.1	GCA_902810665.1	-	-	-	-	-	-
Triticum aestivum Refseqv2	Liliopsida	4565	IWGSC_RefSeq_v2.1	GCA_018294505.1	-	-	-	-	-	-
Triticum aestivum Renan	Liliopsida	4565	Triticum_aestivum_Renan_v2.1	GCA_937894285.1	-	-	-	-	-	-
Triticum aestivum Robigus	Liliopsida	4565	Elv1.1	GCA_902810685.1	-	-	-	-	-	-
Triticum aestivum Stanley	Liliopsida	4565	PGSBv2.2	GCA_903994155.1	-	-		-		-
Triticum aestivum Sy Mattis	Liliopsida	4565	PGSBv2.1	GCA_903994185.1	-	-	-	-	-	-
Triticum aestivum Weebill	Liliopsida	4565	WeebillV1	GCA_902810675.1	-	-	-	-	-	-
Triticum dicoccoides	Liliopsida	85692	WEWSeq_v.1.0	GCA_002162155.1	-	-				-
Triticum spelta	Liliopsida	58933	PGSBv2.0	GCA_903994165.1	-	-	-	-	-	-
Triticum turgidum	Liliopsida	4567	Svevo.v1	GCA_900231445.1	-	-		-		-
Triticum urartu	Liliopsida	4572	IGDB	GCA_003073215.1	-	-				-
Vigna angularis	eudicotyledons	3914	Vigan1.1	GCA_001190045.1	-	-				-
Vigna radiata	eudicotyledons	3916	Vradiata_ver6	GCA_000741045.2	-	-				-
Vigna unguiculata	eudicotyledons	3917	ASM411807v1	GCA_004118075.1	-	-		-		-
Vitis vinifera	eudicotyledons	29760	PN40024.v4	GCA_910591555.1				-		-
Zea mays	Liliopsida	4577	Zm-B73-REFERENCE-NAM-5.0	GCA_902167145.1				-		-

Annex5 Minimum information required for each each MlXs v6.0 checklist

TYPE OF INFORMATION			DESCRIPTOR DEFINITION AND SYNTAX										CHECKLIST REQUIREMENT (M:mandatory; C:conditional mandatory;X:optional; E:Environment dependent; -: not applicable)										
Type	Section	sub-section	MIXS ID	Structured name	comment	Item (rdfs:label)	Definition	Expected value	Value syntax	Example	Preferred unit	Occurrence	migs_eu	migs_ba	migs_pl	migs_vl	migs_org	mims	mimarks_s	mimarks_c	misag	mimag	miuvig
Sample, Environmental Context and investigation	environment	Environmental Parameters	MIXS:000014	env_medium		environmental medium	Report the environmental material(s) immediately surrounding the sample or specimen at the time of sampling. We recommend using subclasses of "environmental material" (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/ENVO_00010483). EnvO documentation about how to use the field: https://github.com/EnvironmentOntology/specieskit/blob/ENVO_sam/ENVO_Terms from other OBO ontologies are permissible as long as they reference mass/volume nouns (e.g. air, water, blood) and not discrete, countable entities (e.g. a tree, a leaf, a table top).	The material displaced by the entity at time of sampling. (Recommend subclasses of environmental material [ENVO:00010483])	{termLabel} [termID]	soil [ENVO:00001958]; Annotating a fish swimming in the upper 100 m of the Atlantic Ocean, consider: ocean water [ENVO:00002151]. Example: Annotating a duck on a pond consider: pond water [ENVO:00002228]jar [ENVO_0002005]		1	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M
Sample, Environmental Context and investigation	nucleic acid sequence source	Biological Source	MIXS:000020	subspec_gen_lin		subspecific lineage	Information about the genetic distinctness of the sequenced organism below the subspecies level, e.g., serovar, serotype, biotype, ecotype, or any relevant genetic typing schemes like Group I plasmid. Subspecies should not be recorded in this term, but in the NCBI taxonomy. Supply both the lineage name and the lineage rank separated by a colon, e.g., biovar:abc123.	Genetic lineage below lowest rank of NCBI taxonomy, which is (rank name)(text) e.g. serovar, biotype, ecotype, variety, cultivar.	{rank name}(text)	serovar:Newport		1	C	C	C	C	C	-	-	C	-	-	-
Sample, Environmental Context and investigation	nucleic acid sequence source	Biological Source	MIXS:000021	ploidy		ploidy	The ploidy level of the genome (e.g. allopolyploid, haploid, diploid, triploid, tetraploid). It has implications for the downstream study of duplicated gene and regions of the genomes (and perhaps for difficulties in assembly). For terms, please select terms listed under class ploidy (PATO:001374) of Phenotypic Quality Ontology (PATO), and for a browser of PATO (v.2018-03-27) please refer to http://purl.bioontology.org/ontology/PATO	PATO	{termLabel} [termID]	allopolyploidy [PATO:0001379]		1	X	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Sample, Environmental Context and investigation	nucleic acid sequence source	Biological Source	MIXS:000022	num_replcons		number of replicons	Reports the number of replicons in a nuclear genome of eukaryotes, in the genome of a bacterium or archaea or the number of segments in a segmented virus. Always applied to the haploid chromosome count of a eukaryote	for eukaryotes and bacteria: chromosomes (haploid count); for viruses: segments	{integer}	2		1	X	M	-	C	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Sample, Environmental Context and investigation	nucleic acid sequence source	Biological Source	MIXS:000023	extrachrom_elements		extrachromosomal elements	Do plasmids exist of significant phenotypic consequence (e.g. ones that determine virulence or antibiotic resistance). Megaplasmsids? Other plasmids (borrelia has 15+ plasmids)	number of extrachromosomal elements	{integer}	5		1	X	C	-	-	C	-	-	X	-	-	-
Sample, Environmental Context and investigation	nucleic acid sequence source	Biological Source	MIXS:000024	estimated_size		estimated size	The estimated size of the genome prior to sequencing. Of particular importance in the sequencing of (eukaryotic) genome which could remain in draft form for a long or unspecified period.	number of base pairs	{integer} bp	30000 bp		1	X	X	X	X	X	-	-	-	-	-	X
Sample, Environmental Context and investigation	nucleic acid sequence source	Biological Source	MIXS:000025	ref_biomaterial		reference for biomaterial	Primary publication if isolated before genome publication; otherwise, primary genome report.	PMID, DOI or URL	{PMID}[DOI][URL]	doi:10.1016/j.yajm.2018.01.009		1	X	M	X	X	X	X	-	-	X	X	X
Sample, Environmental Context and investigation	nucleic acid sequence source	Biological Source	MIXS:000026	source_mat_id		source material identifiers	A unique identifier assigned to a material sample (as defined by http://rs.tdwg.org/dw/terms/materialSampleID , and as opposed to a particular digital record of a material sample) used for extracting nucleic acids, and subsequent sequencing. The identifier can refer either to the original material collected or to any derived sub-samples. The INSDC qualifiers (specimen_voucher, bio_material, or culture_collection may or may not share the same value as the source_mat_id field. For instance, the (specimen_voucher) qualifier and source_mat_id may both contain "UAM:Herps14", referring to both the specimen voucher and sampled tissue with the same identifier. However, the (culture_collection) qualifier may refer to a value from an initial culture (e.g. ATCC:11775) while source_mat_id would refer to an identifier from some derived culture from which the nucleic acids were extracted (e.g. xalc123 or ark:2154/R2).	for cultures of microorganism s. identifiers for two culture collections; for other material a unique arbitrary identifier	{text}	MPD12345		m	C	C	C	C	C	C	C	C	C	C	C
Sample, Environmental Context and investigation	nucleic acid sequence source	Biological Source	MIXS:000027	pathogenicity		known pathogenicity	To what is the entity pathogenic	names of organisms that the entity is pathogenic to	{text}	human, animal, plant, fungi, bacteria		1	C	C	-	C	-	-	-	-	-	-	X
Sample, Environmental Context and investigation	nucleic acid sequence source	Biological Source	MIXS:000028	biotic_relationship		observed relationship	Description of relationship(s) between the subject organism and other organism(s) it is associated with. E.g., parasite on species X; mutualist with species Y. The target organism is the subject of the relationship, and the other organism(s) is the object	enumeration	{free living}[parasitism][commensalism][mutualism]	free living		1	X	C	-	X	-	-	-	-	C	-	X
Sample, Environmental Context and investigation	nucleic acid sequence source	Biological Source	MIXS:000029	specific_host		host scientific name	Report the host's taxonomic name and/or NCBI taxonomy ID.	host scientific name, and/or NCBI taxonomy ID	{text}[NCBI taxid]	Homo sapiens and/or 9606		1	X	C	C	C	-	-	-	-	-	-	X
Sample, Environmental Context and investigation	nucleic acid sequence source	Biological Source	MIXS:000030	host_spec_range		host specificity or range	The range and diversity of host species that an organism is capable of infecting, defined by NCBI taxonomy identifier.	NCBI taxid	{integer}	9606		m	X	X	X	C	-	-	-	-	-	-	X
Sample, Environmental Context and investigation	nucleic acid sequence source	Biological Source	MIXS:000031	host_disease_stat		host disease status	List of diseases with which the host has been diagnosed; can include multiple diagnoses. The value of the field depends on host: for humans the terms should be chosen from the DO (Human Disease Ontology) at https://www.disease-ontology.org ; non-human host diseases are free text	disease name or Disease Ontology term	{termLabel} [termID][text]	rabies [DOID:11260]		m	X	C	-	C	-	-	-	-	-	-	C

TYPE OF INFORMATION			DESCRIPTOR DEFINITION AND SYNTAX										CHECKLIST REQUIREMENT (M:mandatory; C:conditional mandatory;X:optional; E:Environment dependent; -: not applicable)											
Type	Section	sub-section	MIXS ID	Structured name	comment	Item (rdfs:label)	Definition	Expected value	Value syntax	Example	Preferred unit	Occurrence	migs_eu	migs_ba	migs_pl	migs_vl	migs_org	mims	minmarks_s	minmarks_c	misag	mimag	miuvig	
Sample, Environmental Context and investigation	nucleic acid sequence source	Biological Source	MIXS:0000035	source_uvig		source of UVIGs	Type of dataset from which the UVIG was obtained	enumeration	[metagenome (not targeted)]viral fraction metagenome (virome)sequen- nce-targeted metagenome metatranscriptome (not viral targeted)viral fraction RNA metagenome (RNA virome)sequen- nce-targeted RNA metagenome] microbial single amplified genome (SAG)viral single amplified genome (vSAG)isolate microbial genome[other]	viral fraction metagenome (virome)		1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	M	
Sample, Environmental Context and investigation	nucleic acid sequence source	Biological Source	MIXS:0000036	virus_enrich_appr		virus enrichment approach	List of approaches used to enrich the sample for viruses, if any	enumeration	[filtration]ultrafiltration[centrifuga- tion]ultrafena- tion[ultrafena- tion]PEG Precipitation[e- ci Precipitation]e- ci dena- gradient(DNAse)RNAse[targeted sequence capture]other[none]	filtration + FeCl ₃ Precipitation + ultracentrifuga- tion + DNase		1	-	-	C	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	M
Sequencing and Experimental Details	sequencing	Library Preparation	MIXS:0000037	nucd_acid_ext		nucleic acid extraction	A link to a literature reference, electronic resource or a standard operating procedure (SOP), that describes the material separation to recover the nucleic acid fraction from a sample	PMID, DOI or URL	[PMID]([DOI]) [https://mobio.caculmed3.kyushu-u.ac.jp/protocols/cels12888.pdf]			1	C	C	C	C	C	C	C	C	C	C	C	
Sequencing and Experimental Details	sequencing	Library Preparation	MIXS:0000038	nucd_acid_amp		nucleic acid amplification	A link to a literature reference, electronic resource or a standard operating procedure (SOP), that describes the enzymatic amplification (PCR, TMA, NASBA) of specific nucleic acids	PMID, DOI or URL	[PMID]([DOI]) [https://bhylogics.com/microbiotics/16s-rrna-protocol/]			1	C	C	C	C	C	C	C	C	C	C	C	
Sequencing and Experimental Details	sequencing	Library Preparation	MIXS:0000039	lib_size		library size	Total number of clones in the library prepared for the project	number of clones (integer)	50			1	X	X	X	X	X	C	C	-	C	C	C	
Sequencing and Experimental Details	sequencing	Library Preparation	MIXS:0000040	lib_reads_seqd		library reads sequenced	Total number of clones sequenced from the library	number of reads sequenced (integer)	20			1	X	X	X	X	X	C	C	-	C	C	C	
Sequencing and Experimental Details	sequencing	Library Preparation	MIXS:0000041	lib_layout		library layout	Specify whether to expect single, paired, or other configuration of reads	enumeration	[paired]single[vector]other	paired		1	X	X	X	X	X	C	C	-	C	C	C	
Sequencing and Experimental Details	sequencing	Library Preparation	MIXS:0000042	lib_vector		library vector	Cloning vector type(s) used in construction of libraries	vector (text)	Bacteriophage P1			1	X	X	X	X	X	C	C	-	C	C	C	
Sequencing and Experimental Details	sequencing	Library Preparation	MIXS:0000043	lib_screen		library screening strategy	Specific enrichment or screening methods applied before and/or after creating libraries	screening strategy name (text)	enriched, screened, normalized			1	X	X	X	X	X	C	C	-	C	C	C	
Sequencing and Experimental Details	sequencing	sequencing	MIXS:0000044	target_gene		target gene	Targeted gene or locus name for marker gene studies	gene name (text)	16S rRNA, 16S rRNA, nit, atox, tps			1	-	-	-	-	-	-	M	M	-	-	-	
Sequencing and Experimental Details	sequencing	sequencing	MIXS:0000045	target_subfragment		target subfragment	Name of subfragment of a gene or locus. Important to e.g. identify special regions on marker genes like V6 on 16S rRNA	gene fragment name (text)	V6, V9, ITS			1	-	-	-	-	-	-	C	C	-	-	-	
Sequencing and Experimental Details	sequencing	sequencing	MIXS:0000046	pcr_primers		pcr primers	PCR primers that were used to amplify the sequence of the targeted gene, locus or subfragment. This field should contain all the primers used for a single PCR reaction if multiple forward or reverse primers are present in a single PCR reaction. The primer sequence should be reported in uppercase letters	FWD: forward primer sequence;REV: reverse primer sequence (dna)	FWD:GTGCCAGCAGCCGGGTTAAAGGCTACGAGGACTACGAGGGTWTCTAAT			1	-	-	-	-	-	-	C	C	-	-	-	
Sequencing and Experimental Details	sequencing	sequencing	MIXS:0000047	mid		multiplex identifiers	Molecular barcodes, called Multiplex Identifiers (MIDs), that are used to specifically tag unique samples in a sequencing run. Sequence should be reported in uppercase letters	multiplex identifier sequence (dna)	GTGAATAT			1	-	-	-	-	-	-	C	C	-	C	C	
Sequencing and Experimental Details	sequencing	sequencing	MIXS:0000048	adapters		adapters	Adapters provide priming sequences for both amplification and sequencing of the sample-library fragments. Both adapters should be reported; in uppercase letters	adapter A and B sequence (dna),(dna)	AATGATACGCGACCCAGAGATCTACACCGCTCAAGCAGAGACGCGATACGAGAT			1	C	C	C	C	C	C	C	-	C	C	C	
Sequencing and Experimental Details	sequencing	sequencing	MIXS:0000049	pcr_cond		pcr conditions	Description of reaction conditions and components of PCR in the form of 'initial denaturation:94degC,1.5min; annealing:degrees_minutes; extension:degrees_minutes; final elongation:degrees_minutes;total cycles	initial denaturation:degrees_minutes; annealing:degrees_minutes; extension:degrees_minutes; final elongation:degrees_minutes;total cycles	initial denaturation:94.3;annealing:degrees_minutes:1.0;extension:72.1.5;final elongation:72.10.35;total cycles			1	-	-	-	-	-	-	C	C	-	-	-	
Sequencing and Experimental Details	sequencing	sequencing	MIXS:0000050	seq_meth		sequencing method	Sequencing machine used. Where possible the term should be taken from the OBI list of DNA sequencers (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/OBI_0400103).	Text or OBI [term]([text])	454 Genome Sequencer FLX [OBI:0000702]			1	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	
Bioinformatics and Data Processing	sequencing	sequencing	MIXS:0000051	seq_quality_check		sequence quality check	Indicate if the sequence has been called by automatic systems (none) or undergone a manual editing procedure (e.g. by inspecting the raw data or chromatograms). Applied only for sequences that are not submitted to SRA/ENA or DRA	none manually edited or [none]manually edited	none			1	-	-	-	-	-	-	C	C	-	-	-	
Bioinformatics and Data Processing	sequencing	sequencing	MIXS:0000052	chimera_check		chimera check software	Tool(s) used for chimera checking, including version number and parameters, to discover and remove chimeric sequences. A chimeric sequence is comprised of two or more phylogenetically distinct parent sequences.	version and software parameters used (software) (version) (parameters)	uchime:v4.1;d default parameters			1	-	-	-	-	-	-	C	C	-	-	-	

TYPE OF INFORMATION			DESCRIPTOR DEFINITION AND SYNTAX										CHECKLIST REQUIREMENT (M:mandatory; C:conditional mandatory;X:optional; E:Environment dependent; -: not applicable)											
Type	Section	sub-section	MIXS ID	Structured name	comment	Item (rdfs:label)	Definition	Expected value	Value syntax	Example	Preferred unit	Occurrence	migs_eu	migs_ba	migs_pt	migs_vl	migs_org	mims	mimarks_s	mimarks_c	misag	mimag	miuvig	
Bioinformatics Processing	and	Data sequencing	sequencing	MIXS:0000053	tax_ident	taxonomic identity marker	The phylogenetic marker(s) used to assign an organism name to the SAG or MAG	enumeration	[16S rRNA gene multi-marker approach other: gene]	rpob		1	C	C	C	C	C	-	-	M	M	X		
Bioinformatics Processing	and	Data sequencing	data processing	MIXS:0000056	assembly_qual	assembly quality	The assembly quality category is based on sets of criteria outlined for each assembly quality category. For MISAG/MIMAG: Finished: Single, validated, contiguous sequence per replicon without gaps or ambiguities with a consensus error rate equivalent to Q50 or better. High Quality Draft: Multiple fragments where gaps span repetitive regions. Presence of the 23S, 16S and SS rRNA genes and at least 18 rRNAs. Medium Quality Draft: Many fragments with little to no review of assembly other than reporting of standard assembly statistics. Low Quality Draft: Many fragments with little to no review of assembly other than reporting of standard assembly statistics. Assembly statistics include, but are not limited to total assembly size, number of contigs, contig N50/L50, and maximum contig length. For MIUVIG: Finished: Single, validated, contiguous sequence per replicon without gaps or ambiguities, with extensive manual review and editing to annotate putative gene functions and transcriptional units. High-quality draft genome: One or multiple fragments, totaling ≥ 90% of the expected genome or replicon sequence or predicted complete. Genome fragment(s): One or multiple fragments, totaling < 90% of the expected genome or replicon sequence, or for which no genome size could be estimated.	enumeration	[Finished genome High-quality draft genome Medium-quality draft genome Low-quality draft genome Genome fragment(s)]	High-quality draft genome		1	M	M	X	X	X	C	-	-	M	M	M	
Bioinformatics Processing	and	Data sequencing	data processing	MIXS:0000057	assembly_name	assembly name	Name/version of the assembly provided by the submitter that is used in the genome browsers and in the community	name and version of assembly	[text] [text]	HuRef_JCVI_ISG_1.0		1	C	C	C	C	C	C	-	-	C	C	C	
Bioinformatics Processing	and	Data sequencing	data processing	MIXS:0000058	assembly_software	assembly software	Tool(s) used for assembly, including version number and parameters	name and version of software, parameters used	[software] (version) (parameters)	metaSPAdes:3.11.0.kmer: set 21,33,55,77,99,121, default parameters otherwise		1	M	M	M	M	M	C	C	-	-	M	M	M
Bioinformatics Processing	and	Data sequencing	data processing	MIXS:0000059	annot	annotation	Tool used for annotation, or for cases where annotation was provided by a community jamboree or model organism database rather than by a specific submitter	name of tool or pipeline used, or annotation source description	[text]	prokka		1	C	C	C	C	C	C	-	-	X	X	X	
Bioinformatics Processing	and	Data sequencing	data processing	MIXS:0000060	number_contig	number of contigs	Total number of contigs in the cleaned/submitted assembly that makes up a given genome, SAG, MAG, or UVIG	value	[integer]	40		1	M	M	X	X	X	C	-	-	X	X	M	
Bioinformatics Processing	and	Data sequencing	data processing	MIXS:0000061	feat_pred	feature prediction	Method used to predict UVIGs features such as ORFs, integration site, etc.	names and versions of software(s), parameters used	[software] (version) (parameters)	Prodigal:2.6.3, default parameters		1	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	-	-	X	X	C
Bioinformatics Processing	and	Data sequencing	data processing	MIXS:0000062	ref_db	reference database(s)	List of database(s) used for ORF annotation, along with version number and reference to website or publication	names, versions, and references of databases	[database] (version) (reference)	pVOGs:5/http://dmk-brain.ecn.uio.no/edu/pVOGs/ Grazziolin et al. 2017 doi:10.1093/nar/njw075		1	X	X	X	X	X	X	-	-	X	X	C	
Bioinformatics Processing	and	Data sequencing	data processing	MIXS:0000063	sim_search_meth	similarity search method	Tool used to compare ORFs with database, along with version and cutoffs used	names and versions of software(s), parameters used	[software] (version) (parameters)	HMMER3.1b 2/hmmsearch, cutoff of 50 on score		1	X	X	X	X	X	X	-	-	X	X	C	
Bioinformatics Processing	and	Data sequencing	data processing	MIXS:0000064	tax_class	taxonomic classification	Method used for taxonomic classification, along with reference database used, classification rank, and thresholds used to classify new genomes	classification method, database name, and other parameters	[text]	vConTACT2 (reference from NCBI RefSeq v83, genus rank classification, default parameters)		1	X	X	X	X	X	X	-	-	X	X	C	
Bioinformatics Processing	and	Data sequencing	data processing	MIXS:0000065	16s_recover	16S recovered	Can a 16S gene be recovered from the submitted SAG or MAG?	boolean	[boolean]	yes		1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	X	X	-	
Bioinformatics Processing	and	Data sequencing	data processing	MIXS:0000066	16s_recover_software	16S recovery software	Tools used for 16S rRNA gene extraction	names and versions of software(s), parameters used	[software] (version) (parameters)	rambl.v2.default parameters		1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	X	X	-
Bioinformatics Processing	and	Data sequencing	data processing	MIXS:0000067	trnas	number of standard tRNAs extracted	The total number of tRNAs identified from the SAG or MAG	value from 0-21	[integer]	18		1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	X	X	X	
Bioinformatics Processing	and	Data sequencing	data processing	MIXS:0000068	trna_ext_software	tRNA extraction software	Tools used for tRNA identification	names and versions of software(s), parameters used	[software] (version) (parameters)	infernal.v2.default parameters		1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	X	X	X
Bioinformatics Processing	and	Data sequencing	data processing	MIXS:0000069	compl_score	completeness score	Completeness score is typically based on either the fraction of markers found as compared to a database or the percent of a genome found as compared to a closely related reference genome. High Quality Draft: >90%, Medium Quality Draft: >50%, and Low Quality Draft: < 50% should have the indicated completeness scores	quality:percent completeness	[high med low] (percentage)	med:60%		1	X	X	X	X	X	-	-	-	M	M	C	
Bioinformatics Processing	and	Data sequencing	data processing	MIXS:0000070	compl_software	completeness software	Tools used for completeness estimate, i.e. checkm, anv'o, busco	names and versions of software(s) used	[software] (version)	checkm		1	X	X	X	X	X	-	-	-	M	M	X	
Bioinformatics Processing	and	Data sequencing	data processing	MIXS:0000071	compl_appr	completeness approach	The approach used to determine the completeness of a given genomic assembly, which would typically make use of a set of conserved marker genes or a closely related reference genome. For UVIG completeness, include reference genome or group used, and contig feature suggesting a complete genome	text	[marker gene reference base other]	other: UVIG length compared to the average length of reference genomes from the PZZ virus genus (NCBI RefSeq v83)		1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	X	X	C	
Bioinformatics Processing	and	Data sequencing	data processing	MIXS:0000072	contam_score	contamination score	The contamination score is based on the fraction of single-copy genes that are observed more than once in a query genome. The following scores are acceptable for: High Quality Draft: < 5%, Medium Quality Draft: < 10%, Low Quality Draft: < 10%. Contamination must be below 5% for a SAG or MAG to be deposited into any of the public databases	value	[float] (percentage)	1%		1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	M	M	-	
Bioinformatics Processing	and	Data sequencing	data processing	MIXS:0000005	contam_screen_input	contamination screening input	The type of sequence data used as input	enumeration	[reads] (contigs)	contigs		1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	X	X	-
Bioinformatics Processing	and	Data sequencing	data processing	MIXS:0000073	contam_screen_param	contamination screening parameters	Specific parameters used in the decontamination software, such as reference database, coverage, and kmers. Combinations of these parameters may also be used, i.e. kmer and coverage, or reference database and kmer	enumeration: kmer or name	[ref database coverage combination] (text) (integer)	kmer		1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	X	X	-	
Bioinformatics Processing	and	Data sequencing	data processing	MIXS:0000074	decontam_software	decontamination software	Tool(s) used in contamination screening	enumeration	[checkm refine ntam obroad get bitools decontaminate.sh acid combination]	env'o		1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	X	X	-

